
Surface processes in response to tectonic and climatic forcing in the Pamir

- Insights into the evolution on the Panj river network -

To the Faculty of Geoscience, Geoengineering and Mining
of the Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg
is submitted this

THESIS

to attain the academic degree of
Doctor rerum naturalium
(Dr. rer. nat.)
submitted

by

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born on the 2 Dec 1979 in Oschatz

Freiberg, 4 July 2014

Abstract

The interplay between topographic, tectonic, and climatic factors has fundamental relevance for understanding the mechanisms of mountain evolution and their susceptibility to changes. This thesis combines geomorphometric analyses with geochronological techniques to determine the distribution and rates of surface processes in the Pamir. Positioned in a transitional setting between the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon, the Pamir provide ideal conditions to explore surface processes with respect to variable climatic conditions, and to compare such results with those found in other actively deforming high mountains. Depending on the scale and setting, either uplift or precipitation is most commonly discussed as the dominant control factor. In this context, this thesis addresses four main issues - (1) the distribution of tectonic and climatic factors in the Pamir, and their effects on geomorphometry; (2) the challenge of accurate sediment dating for precise process rates in high mountains; (3) the variability of fluvial incision and its implications for the evolution of the Pamir river network; and (4) which factors control erosion, and how erosion rates relate to local lowering of base levels.

Chapter 2.2 discusses how the collinearity of the major tectonic structures, mountain ranges, and the river network exert long-term control on flow orientation and local base levels. Due to the dry climate on the Pamir Plateau, fluvial activity is low, and glacial processes are restricted to high altitudes. High topographic variability and fluctuating local base levels at the Pamir margins indicate rapid landscape change. These intense surface processes coincide with both neotectonic activity along orogenic bounding faults and orographic precipitation from the Westerlies. The trunk stream, the Panj River, indicates major re-organizations of the river network. Successive river captures across the Pamir domes suggest dominant structural control accompanied by possible re-activation of dome bounding faults.

Luminescence dating is of paramount importance for decoding the sedimentation histories, but material in high mountains is challenging due to differential bleaching histories and post-depositional sediment mixing. To address this, Chapter 3.2 describes a transparent, reproducible analysis routine in three data processing templates using the **R** package 'Luminescence'. The challenges posed by properties of high mountain materials are addressed in Chapter 3.3, comparing multiple grain and single grain techniques applied to quartz, K-feldspar and plagioclase. These methods allow us to identify prominent events in sediment deposition without interference from bleaching and sediment mixing, or signal loss due to anomalous fading.

Chapter 4.2 applies optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) methods to quantify the variations in fluvial incision along the Panj River. Paleo-glaciations during Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 2 and MIS 1/2 may have triggered the deposition of terrace sediments, but the rate of incision is primarily consistent with terrace location, rather than time of formation. Where the Panj cuts across the Shakh dara Dome in the southern Pamir, high incision rates of 7–10 mm/yr indicate intense river adjustment. Lower incision rates of 2–4 mm/yr are consistent with sections of the Panj parallel to southern dome boundaries, where the river profile suggests local base levels. To the north-east, the Panj incision reflects transient conditions - only the increased incision of ~6 mm/yr marks the river response across the Darvaz Fault Zone. These data highlight the structural control of sudden base level drop due to successive river captures,

while climatic factors - as well as rock erodibility and drainage architecture - are of secondary importance.

Chapter 5.2 complements the indications from geomorphometry and fluvial incision with cosmogenic nuclide (CN)-based basin-wide erosion rates. Results suggest a rapid average topographic evolution in the Pamir. However, the pace of erosion at the Pamir Plateau shows a strong contrast to the Pamir margins. High erosion rates of 0.55–1.43 mm/yr integrate over millennial scale conditions at the western Pamir margin, whereas lower rates of 0.05–0.17 mm/yr at the Pamir Plateau also integrate effects of the MIS 1/2 deglaciation. The correlation of erosion with steep slopes (R^2 of 0.82) defines the precondition for high erosion in the Pamir. The influence of precipitation only becomes evident in multiple linear regression analyses, explaining erosion as function of slope and precipitation (R^2 of 0.93). The almost ten-fold discrepancy between fluvial incision rates along the Panj River and basin-wide erosion rates reflects the transience of the landscape with the Panj incising faster than hillslopes adjust. The rate of adjustment increases where the Westerlies supply moisture during winter. This suggests that an efficient sediment transport relates to seasonal peak discharge during the melting season.

The methods and results described, highlight the dominance of tectonic structures in controlling surface processes. In contrast to the southern escarpment of the Himalayas where the Indian Summer Monsoon provides intensive rainfalls, precipitation in the Pamir is limited and hence, work as a restricting factor for hillslope adjustment to fluvial incision. Major re-organisations of the Pamir River network highlight river captures as an important trigger of high surface response rates due to the sudden drop in base levels.

Kurzfassung

Dem Zusammenspiel topografischer, tektonischer und klimatischer Faktoren kommt fundamentale Bedeutung zu, wenn es um das Verständnis der Entwicklung von Gebirgen und deren Anfälligkeit für Umweltveränderungen geht. Diese Arbeit kombiniert geomorphometrische Analysen mit geochronologischen Techniken um die Oberflächenprozesse im Pamir qualitativ und quantitativ zu bestimmen. Gelegen inmitten des Einflussbereichs von Westwindzone und indischem Sommermonsun, stellt der Pamir ideale Voraussetzungen, um Oberflächenprozesse unter unterschiedlichen klimatischen Einflüssen zu studieren und gewonnene Ergebnisse mit solchen aus anderen Hochgebirgen, die Deformation erfahren, zu vergleichen. Abhängig vom der Dimension und von den Rahmenbedingungen werden meist Niederschlag oder Hebungsraten als die kontrollierenden Faktoren für Gebirgsevolution diskutiert. Hierauf aufbauend beschäftigt sich die vorliegende Arbeit mit den vier wesentlichen Punkten: (1) Räumliche Verteilung und Auswirkung von tektonischen und klimatischen Faktoren auf die Geomorphometrie; (2) Herausforderungen bei der akkuraten Sediment-Datierung zur genauen Prozessraten-Bestimmung im Hochgebirge; (3) Variabilität fluvialer Einschneidung und daraus resultierender Implikationen für die Entwicklung des Flussnetzwerks im Pamir; (4) Bestimmung der Erosion-beeinflussenden Faktoren und die Abhängigkeit von Erosionsraten zu lokalen Veränderungen der Erosionsbasis.

Kapitel 2.2 diskutiert wie die Kollinearität der wesentlichen tektonischen Strukturen, Bergketten und des Flussnetzwerks langfristig kontrollierenden Einfluss auf die Entwicklung der Fließrichtung und der lokalen Erosionsbasis ausübt. Durch das aride Klima des Pamir-Plateaus herrscht geringe fluviale Aktivität und glaziale Prozesse sind auf extreme Höhenlagen beschränkt. Starke Variabilität der Topografie und fluktuierende lokale Erosionsbasen an den Rändern des Pamirs weisen auf rapide Landschaftsveränderungen hin. Stark ausgeprägte Oberflächenprozesse überschneiden sich mit neotektonischer Aktivität entlang von Störungzonen des Orogens und mit Westwind-induziertem orographischem Niederschlag. Der Panj als Hauptfluss weist auf eine Neuordnung des Flussnetzwerkes hin. Sukzessive Flussanzapfung durch die Dome des Pamirs hindurch verweisen auf dominant strukturelle Regulierung möglicherweise zusammen mit einer Reaktivierung der Störungzonen entlang der Domgrenzen.

Lumineszenz-Datierung ist von besonderer Wichtigkeit bei der Entschlüsselung von Sedimentarchiven. Allerdings stellt Material aus Hochgebirgen eine besondere Herausforderung durch differentielles Bleichen und nachträglicher Sediment-Vermischung dar. Dieses Problem wird in Kapitel 3.2 bearbeitet, welches eine transparente und reproduzierbare Analyse-Prozedur in Form von Skripten für das **R** Paket 'Luminescence' vorstellt. Die Herausforderung, die Material aus Hochgebirgen mit sich bringt, wird in Kapitel 3.3 adressiert, in dem Techniken zur Analyse von mehreren und einzelnen Körnern von Quarz, Kalifeldspat und Plagioklas verglichen werden. Diese Methoden ermöglichen die Identifizierung der dominanten Sedimentationsereignisse und Abgrenzung von Störungen durch Bleichen, Sediment-Vermischung oder anormaler Signalreduzierung.

In Kapitel 4.2 werden Methoden zur optisch stimulierten Lumineszenz (OSL) genutzt um die Variationen der fluvialen Einschneidung entlang des Pans zu quantifizieren. Paläo-Vergletscherungen während der Sauerstoff-Isotopenstufen (MIS) 2 und MIS 1/2 könnten die Ablagerung von Sediment-

Terrassen ausgelöst haben, jedoch zeigen Einschneidungsraten keinen Zusammenhang mit dem Zeitpunkt der Ablagerung, sondern sind konsistent mit der räumlichen Lage der Terrassen. Dort wo der Panj den Shakh dara-Dom im Süd-Pamir schneidet, weisen hohe Einschneidungsraten von 7–10 mm/yr auf erhebliche Veränderungen der Flussläufe hin. Geringere Raten von 2–4 mm/yr zeigen sich, wo der Panj parallel zur südlichen Domgrenze fließt und das Flussprofil eine lokale Erosionsbasis vermuten lässt. Im Nordosten spiegeln die Einschneidungsraten des Pans einen Übergangszustand wider - einzige Ausnahme ist die Reaktion des Flusses entlang der Darvasz-Störung mit erhöhten Einschneidungsraten von ~ 6 mm/yr. Die Ergebnisse verdeutlichen die strukturelle Regulierung von plötzlichen Erosionsbasis-Verringerungen aufgrund von sukzessiver Flussanzapfung. Klimatische Faktoren, als auch Erodibilität und Flusslauf-Architektur haben eine untergeordnete Rolle.

Kapitel 5.2 ergänzt die Resultate zur Geomorphometrie und fluvialen Einschneidungsraten mit Flusseinzugsgebiet-Erosionsraten, die auf kosmogenen Nuklid-Messungen (CN) basieren. Ergebnisse deuten auf eine rapide Entwicklung der Topographie des Pamirs hin. Jedoch sind starke Unterschiede bei der Geschwindigkeit der Erosionsprozesse zwischen dem Plateau und den Randbereichen zu sehen. Hohe Erosionsraten von 0.55–1.43 mm/yr über tausendjährige Zeiträume an den Gebirgrändern stehen niedrigen Raten von 0.05–0.17 mm/yr auf dem Pamir Plateau über Zeiträume, die die Abschmelzung während MIS 1/2 integrieren, gegenüber. Die Korrelation von Erosion mit steilen Hangneigungen (R^2 of 0.82) definiert die Voraussetzung für hohe Erosionsraten im Pamir. Der Einfluss von Niederschlag wird erst durch eine multiple lineare Regressions-Analyse ersichtlich, in der Erosion als Funktion von Hangneigung und Niederschlag erklärt wird (R^2 of 0.93). Der mehr als zehnfache Unterschied zwischen fluvialer Einschneidung entlang des Panjs und den Flusseinzugsgebiet-Erosionsraten reflektiert den Übergang der Landschaft, in der sich der Panj schneller einschneidet, als die Hänge adaptieren können. Mit zunehmender Wasserverfügbarkeit, bereitgestellt durch die Westwinde als Winterniederschlag, beschleunigt sich diese Adaption. Dies lässt darauf schließen, dass effektiver Sedimenttransport von saisonalen Spitzenabflüssen während der Schmelzperiode abhängt.

Die beschriebenen Methoden und Ergebnisse heben den dominanten Einfluss der tektonischen Strukturen auf die Regulierung der Oberflächenprozesse hervor. Im Gegensatz zum südlichen Vorlands des Himalaya, wo der indische Sommermonsun starke Regenfälle bringt, ist Niederschlag im Pamir sehr limitiert und wirkt deshalb als einschränkender Faktor bei der Reaktion von Hängen auf fluviale Einschneidung. Wesentliche Neuordnungen des Panj-Flussnetzwerks heben die Bedeutung von Flussanzapfungen hervor. Diese verursachen eine plötzliche Verringerung der Erosionsbasis und führen zu intensivierten Oberflächenprozessen.

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List of Abbreviations

- D_e Equivalent dose in Gy; $1\text{Gy} = \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}}$
- R** Name of the numerical programming language R (here written in bold letters)
- a.r.l. Above river level
- a.s.l. Above sea level
- ASTER Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer
- CN Cosmogenic nuclide(s)
- CRAN Comprehensive R Archive Network
- DEM Digital elevation model(s)
- DFZ Darvaz Fault Zone
- ELA Equilibrium line altitude
- FMM Finite mixture model
- GMT Generic Mapping Tool
- GPS Global positioning system
- GSZ Gunt Shear Zone
- IRSL Infrared (light) stimulated luminescence
- ISM Indian Summer Monsoon
- KD Kurgovat Dome
- KDE Kernel density estimates
- KFZ Karakoram Fault Zone
- KS Kunlun Suture
- kyr Thousand years
- MAM Minimum age model
- MD Muskol Dome
- MIS Marine Isotope Stage

MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
MPT	Main Pamir Thrust
Myr	Million years
OSL	Optically stimulated luminescence
RPS	Rushan–Pshart suture
SAD	Shakhdara-Alichur Dome
SAR	Single aliquot regenerative (-dose protocol)
SD	Sarez Dome
SPD	Shatput Dome
SPSZ	Southern Pamir Shear Zone
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
TS	Tanymas suture
v_{DR}	Coefficient of variation describing the standard deviation of equivalent doses against the recovery dose
VSR	Valley shape ratios
YD	Yazgulom Dome
yr	Years

1 Introduction

1.1 Surface processes in high mountains

The evolution of high mountains exemplifies the complexity of interactions that constantly shape our planet (e.g., Molnar and England, 1990; Willett, 1999; Montgomery and Brandon, 2002; Burbank et al., 2003; Champagnac et al., 2009; Godard et al., 2014). Located at the joints of the earth's crust, modulating global atmospheric circulations, they provide us with a showcase of the fundamental mechanisms of landscape evolution, condensed in space and time. Active tectonic uplift and deformation provoke erosive response processes because of lifting material above base levels (e.g., Willett, 1999; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007). Resulting altitude gradients and sudden local strain releases in form of, for example, landslides, constitute highly dynamic preconditions and, by implication, high rates of landscape adjustment (e.g., Burbank et al., 1996; Burbank, 2002; Montgomery and Brandon, 2002). The interactions of topography and climate lead to precipitation and temperature gradients. The variability within short horizontal distance is comparable to climatic regimes across latitudinal belts (e.g., Beniston, 2005). Both climatic factors exert important control on material erosion and transport by regulating the availability of water in a landscape (e.g., Reiners et al., 2003; Bookhagen et al., 2005; Burbank et al., 2012). The complex tectonic-climatic preconditions define the sensitivity of surface processes to change. Related mass transfer by sediment and water discharge effects not only the evolution of the orogen itself (e.g., Willett, 1999; Champagnac et al., 2009), but also the evolution of regional and continental landscapes.

Understanding the interplay between control factors and surface response processes is important for understanding landscape configuration and its sensitivity to change. Our motivation to understand is not only driven by intrinsic human curiosity, however; understanding these processes is also essential to resource assessment and risk prediction. Earth sciences can provide essential knowledge on issues such as thresholds of mass wasting processes or mechanisms of runoff generation relevant to landslides and flood events (e.g., Ouimet et al., 2009; Korup et al., 2010; DiBiase and Whipple, 2011). The sensitivity to climatic change effects precipitation, behavior of glaciers and fluvial discharge with consequences for large scale water resources (e.g., Bookhagen et al., 2005; Bookhagen, 2012). Assessing stability and fragility in landscapes also has implications in engineering; from water and risk management to securing technical infrastructure.

The following chapters give a general introduction to the complexity of the relationship between control factors and surface response, as well as how those relations can be measured. The general introduction to research and theoretical debate on high mountain evolution is then focussed towards the Pamir region, elaborating on the main research objectives and how those objectives are addressed in this thesis.

1.2 General background

Relating surface processes to certain configurations of control factors provides essential information on the evolution of high mountains. Classical models of mountain evolution (Davis, Penck, Hack, Fig. 1.1, summarized in Burbank and Anderson 2001) focus on the interplay between plate tectonics and erosion. These models describe the topographic change as a function of rock uplift, and its destructive counterpart - erosion (Burbank and Anderson, 2001). The mass transfer causes, in turn, crustal unloading and isostatic rebound (Burbank, 2002). The topographic growth is limited by the finite strength of rock, and hence, reaches a dynamic

Figure 1.1: Classical models of mountain evolution with focus on the interplay of tectonic uplift and erosional response according to Davis (top), Penck (middle) and Hack (bottom). The conceptual models illustrate the dependence of landscape evolution on the duration and rate of rock uplift (Burbank and Anderson, 2001).

equilibrium depending on the duration and frequency of tectonic forcing Burbank (2002).

Such rather conceptual models are concerned with large scale processes of mountain ranges, and demand evaluation in the natural context. Studies of the surface processes of high mountains in various settings underscore the importance of climate in modulating the efficiency of erosion and unloading. In particular, orographic precipitation and the development of glaciers at high altitudes were found to trigger highly erosive mechanisms (e.g., Burbank, 2002; Bookhagen et al., 2005; Gabet et al., 2008; Champagnac et al., 2009). The differing explanations of variable erosion are the subject of an ongoing debate on the relative importance of active tectonics versus precipitation in driving large-scale landscape evolution (e.g., Burbank et al., 2003; Reiners et al., 2003; Bookhagen et al., 2005; Burbank et al., 2012; Godard et al., 2014).

The debate on the coupling and feedback between uplift, climate, and topography was intensified by evidence of accelerated erosion found in Quaternary sediment records (Fig. 1.2, Molnar and England 1990; Molnar 2004; Willenbring and von Blanckenburg 2010). The indicated dramatic increase of erosion at the Pliocene-Pleistocene transition correlates with global cooling cycles. Although Pleistocene glaciations are synchronous with variations in the Earth's orbit, the global increase in erosion is also discussed as a consequence of large-scale tectonic uplift (Raymo and Ruddiman, 1992). Evidence such as lowered atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and paleobotanic indicators of warmer climate at high altitudes are ambiguous as these can result either from uplift or cooling. Mountain formation can cool the climate through prolonged snow cover and high albedo, through the effect on atmospheric circulation systems, and through increased weathering absorbing carbon dioxide (summarized in Molnar and England 1990). Based on these physical arguments, climatic cooling could result from late Cenozoic

Figure 1.2: Late Cenozoic terrigenous sediment supply to oceans (yellow bars) and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations based on several independent proxies (purple band: planktonic foraminifera, green band: C₃ plants, blue band: alkenones, thin black line: ice cores) (Willenbring and von Blanckenburg, 2010).

mountain formation and increased erosion.

However, the strong coupling and indirect indication of uplift, climate, and erosion effects complicate the resolution of this 'chicken or egg' argument (Molnar and England, 1990). Molnar and England (1990) argued that much of the inferred late Cenozoic uplift could well be caused by climatic change, rather than climate change being the consequence of it. A cooler climate can cause apparent uplift due to increased erosion and related isostatic rebound (Molnar and England, 1990). Increased glaciation and lower sea levels are not exclusively responsible for the increased erosion during the Quaternary. Moreover, the high Pleistocene erosion seems to be related to large climatic oscillations and the dynamic adjustment of the landscape towards new equilibria (Molnar, 2004). Pronounced erosion exerts a positive feedback with further cooling through increased mean and peak altitudes which allow longer ice and snow cover, and through carbon dioxide consumption due to silicate weathering (Molnar and England, 1990).

Willenbring and von Blanckenburg (2010) question the actual occurrence of the accelerated erosion. The inferred four-fold increase in erosion would lead to a sedimentary carbon dioxide burial that is not apparent in proxies of atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. Furthermore, the ¹⁰Be/⁹Be ratio dissolved in ocean water does not show any increase in weathering fluxes. The sediment records used as evidence may be biased due to higher completeness of younger deposits and related effects of hiatus, and due to compaction by overburden and re-mobilization (Sadler, 1981; Molnar, 2004; Willenbring and von Blanckenburg, 2010). While the link between erosion and atmospheric CO₂ concentration is primarily based on silicate weathering, the contribution of weathering to erosion can vary considerably between different settings. Burial and storage in the form of organic matter also affects atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (Summerfield and Hulton, 1994; Anderson et al., 2009; Hovius et al., 2011).

This debate illustrates the complexity of interactions on a global scale, while local landscapes may respond differently. An improved understanding of the erosive mechanisms relies on investigations directly at the site of material removal, i.e. at the high mountain belts. The relationship between contributing factors may vary. Certain factors cause no continuous response behavior, but instead depend on minimum values such as threshold slopes, or on magnitude-frequency effects such as landslides (e.g., Burbank, 2002; Korup, 2012). Such thresholds highlight that processes are not present everywhere, but operate in certain process domains. Numerical data on process rates, and their evaluation in the context of local conditions, is essential to the resolution of the debate on the underlying factors driving landscape evolution. The development of suitable analytical tools enables a wide range of geomorphological analyses. Analyses must focus on measures of erosion and fluvial incision in order to address the central mechanisms of material removal and transport. With this aim, the following chapter 1.3 gives an overview of numeric measures of erosion and fluvial incision.

1.3 Measures of process rates and patterns

Measures of surface processes provide qualitative and quantitative keys to understand how landscapes respond to a certain configuration of control factors. Their pattern and rates enable to verify the relations found between tectonic and climatic drivers in various geographic settings. The specific conditions represented by the patterns and rates depend on the scale of applied measure and the time scale of process response. Two types of measures are available to describe surface processes:

- Indirect estimates: Morphometric patterns (Chapter 1.3.1)
- Direct estimates: Surface process rates (Chapter 1.3.2 and 1.3.3)

Morphometric patterns illustrate the topographic variability in a landscape as a result of inherited process imprints and as the precondition for ongoing processes (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001). Gradual or abrupt changes enable to identify typical process domains and may be related to the location of tectonic structures or the distribution of climatic factors. Information on time scales rely on relative indications via the magnitude and persistence of morphometric features.

The rate at which surface processes erode uplifted mountains results from the geomorphological work of fluvial incision and denudation (e.g., DiBiase and Whipple, 2011; Kirby and Whipple, 2012). Quantitative data on the efficiency of those erosive mechanisms require suitable geo-markers and their geochronological decoding. The measurement of fluvial incision and denudation rates provide important insights into the ability of rivers to lower the local minimum altitudes that determine the local base levels for hillslope adjustment (e.g., Burbank, 2002; DiBiase and Whipple, 2011). Consequently, respective rates deliver quantitative estimates on the coupling of hillslope sediment fluxes and fluvial transport depending on the spatial and temporal scale of the chosen geo-marker and geochronological technique.

1.3.1 Morphometric analyses

The orogen's morphometry describes the spatial pattern of altitudes in order to reveal the style and relative magnitude of the erosive processes at work (e.g., Ahnert, 1970; Burbank and

Anderson, 2001). Analyses of morphometry delivers information on the two essential drivers of surface processes, the local base levels and the kinematic energy available for the surface processes. The local base levels determine the altitudes to which fluvial incision responds, and distinguish between fluvial incision and sedimentation (Bull, 2007). Such minimum altitudes define the dominant material pathways, and have many consequences on flow orientation and related accumulation area that guide the organization of the *drainage architecture*. Variations in altitudes above the local base level of a certain area regulate the potential energy available for the hillslope response as a result and driver of ongoing surface processes (e.g., Kirby and Whipple, 2012).

The characteristics of morphometric patterns largely depend on the scale of measurement. Typical scales for analyses range from local slopes, to *topographic profiles* across valleys up to orogen-wide transects, while *longitudinal profiles* along selected rivers record changes in local base levels itself. Morphometric analyses based on field measurements and printed topographic maps are limited to small-scale areas or are rather time consuming. The main advantage of digital topographic data lies in that they offer complete and homogeneous spatial coverage. Such spatially continuous data allow a wide range of quantitative analyses and models applied to large-scale or multiple areas (e.g., Schwanghart and Kuhn, 2010; Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011a; Kirby and Whipple, 2012). Consequently, many morphometric measures base on digital elevation models (DEM) derived from satellite data.

The widely used Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM, www.glcf.umd.edu/data/srtm/) or Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER, www.glcf.umd.edu/data/aster/) data sets offer spatial resolution between 15 m and 1 km. But depending on the research questions and area of interest, also data sets of higher resolutions may be selected from the various satellites of steadily improving data quality. Concurrently, the tools for data processing flourish as add-ons for different software or programming environments with varying focus and computational flexibility. Examples are TecDEM (Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011a,b), TopoToolbox (Schwanghart and Kuhn, 2010), and numerous packages and scripts for Quantum GIS (QGIS Development Team), GRASS GIS (GRASS Development Team) and R (R Core Team), while the full range of solutions remains outnumbered. Apart from various applications for spatial numerical analysis, those tools include algorithms for DEM pre-processing, such as to fill missing values or reduce noise by smoothing procedures.

- **Drainage basins** reveal units of surface dynamics based on topography (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007; Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011b). The relation between minimum and maximum altitudes predicts the potential location of rivers and related drainage divides (Fig. 1.3). The increasing accumulation area scales with river length and distance to drainage divide, and induces a timelag in morphodynamic response (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007; Demoulin, 2011). Signals from perturbations propagate first along the fluvial system until increasing process rates of adjacent hillslopes, and finally transmitting changes to the drainage divides (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Demoulin, 2011).

The resulting shape of basins and their drainage network offer various parameters for analyzing the control from active tectonic structures, lithology and climate (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011b). Tools such as TecDEM (Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011b,a) or GRASS GIS (GRASS Development Team) provide sets of functions for comprehensive basin analyses. Determining, for example, the drainage den-

Figure 1.3: Exemplary analyses of the drainage architecture of the Gunt basin in the Pamir, illustrating basin shape and Strahler orders (Strahler, 1952) of the river network, and using a DEM (3m resolution), the matlab-based toolbox TecDEM (Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011b,a) and plotting tools of the Generic Mapping Tool (GMT, Wessel and Smith 1991).

sity, basin symmetry or basin hypsometry involves pre-processing of DEM data for flow orientation and accumulation area. Streams can then be extracted depending on a certain minimum accumulation area. It is convenient to assign Strahler orders (Strahler, 1952) to respective stream segments for analyses of the architecture of the river network, and comparison between reaches or rivers (Fig. 1.3). River offsets or deflections in flow orientations deliver, among other indications, straightforward identifiers for the location of active tectonic displacement, while, for example, the drainage density reveals the feedbacks from lithologic and climatic controls (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007). The response mechanisms within basins may be further investigated based on comparing basin elements such as area, drainage density and channel steepness from study regions of different control factors. Systematic variations in response patterns elucidate the process feedbacks within basins, especially between the fluvial domain of the river network and the denudation domain at adjacent hillslopes.

- **Topographic profiles** provide a straightforward overview of altitude variations, gradients and local base levels along a chosen transect. The interpretation of landscape features is primary dependent on the resolution of the primary data set in use, and the scale of the profile. For example, the analysis of valley morphology requires a high resolution of spatial data (e.g., DEM of 30 m pixel width) to provide appropriate estimates of the true depth of valleys or width of the valley floors. Represented features depend also on a careful selection of the profile line position. In the case of valley profiles (Fig. 1.4), the profile lines lie perpendicular to the river course, reach from one drainage divide to the other, but try to avoid bias from side valleys (Fig. 1.4A). Unwanted cutting of side valleys, for example, leads to misinterpretations such as widened valley morphology or stacked valley generation.

The extracted altitude data can then be processed according to individual research need. Descriptive valley morphology parameters include valley depth and valley width (Fig. 1.4B). The ratio between both, the valley shape ratio (VSR), provides an estimator for the long-term relation between fluvial incision, hillslope response and evolution of the

Figure 1.4: Valley morphometry characterized by topographic profiles. A: Selection of profile line for altitude extraction from DEM data (ASTER data set, 30 m resolution, exemplary map excerpt of the Panj river in the Pamir). B: Exemplary topographic profile extracted along a single profile line. Possible descriptive parameters include valley depth and width, and related valley shape ratios (VSR). C: Exemplary swath profile extracted at a similar position as the topographic profile (B). Altitudes represent mean values (solid line) and topographic variation (grey shaded area) within a distance of 10 km from both sides of the central profile line.

drainage divide (Burbank and Anderson, 2001).

Swath profiles reduce the ‘noise’ from local features by integrating altitude values within a certain distance perpendicular to a chosen central profile line. Altitude variations along swath profiles display the general trends in morphometry according to selected descriptive statistics, for example, the mean, maximum and minimum altitudes within the given swath width (Fig. 1.4C). The latter deliver estimates of local base levels for erosion, while the difference to maximum altitudes reveals the hypsometry within the swath width.

- **Longitudinal river profiles** are topographic profiles that follow the course of a river. Representing a succession of local base levels, river profiles dictate the topographic evolution within and transmit changes through the respective morphodynamic response unit (e.g., Hack, 1957; Whipple and Tucker, 1999; Snyder et al., 2000; Demoulin, 2011; Kirby and Whipple, 2012). Longitudinal profiles characterize rivers based on the channel slope and its proportionality to the upstream drainage area, river length or size of material in its channel (Hack, 1957). Analyses of those relation reveal the capacity of the stream to transport the products of erosion in a basin of a certain configuration (Hack, 1957; Snyder et al., 2000), and enables to determine local perturbations or changes of control factors over time (e.g., Wobus et al., 2006; Kirby and Whipple, 2012; Cyr et al., 2014).

Rivers under constant tectonic and climatic conditions are expected to develop a smooth, concave longitudinal profile (Hack, 1973; Whipple and Tucker, 1999; Snyder et al., 2000; Cyr et al., 2014). The slope of that equilibrated channel can be predicted from the upstream drainage area by the power-function relation (Hack, 1957, 1973; Snyder et al., 2000; Wobus et al., 2006):

$$S = k_s A^{-\theta} \quad (1.1)$$

Figure 1.5: Schematic evolution of longitudinal river profiles in transient landscapes illustrating the fluvial response to an increase in rock uplift. A knickpoint delineates the upstream reach that does not yet respond to the changed conditions but keeps the initial profile shape at a higher elevation (Kirby and Whipple, 2012).

with θ and k_s describing the channel concavity and steepness, respectively. Both parameters depend on the uplift rate, the bedrock erodibility of the basin and the climate-related fluvial discharge (Hack, 1957, 1973; Snyder et al., 2000; Whipple and Tucker, 1999; Cyr et al., 2014).

Breaks in the channel slope - drainage area scaling (knickpoints, Fig. 1.5) evidence disequilibrium conditions, and are used to delineate tectonic or lithologic boundaries (Hack, 1957; Wobus et al., 2006; Cyr et al., 2014). Fig. 1.5 gives an example of a river profile experiencing an increase in rock uplift and the upstream propagating fluvial response. Log-log plots of the channel slope - drainage area relation can be used to determine changes in the channel concavity and steepness by linear regression (Snyder et al., 2000; Wobus et al., 2006), but often high data scatter (mainly due to the DEM resolution) causes uncertainties in the best fit of parameters (Snyder et al., 2000). Additionally, the scaling is only valid for channels dominated by the same process and shows breaks from colluvial to fluvial and to alluvial channels

Quantitative measures of the variations in the slope - area relation, and related local changes in the power of a river to transport material provides the Hack index, also referred to as gradient index or stream length (SL) gradient index (Hack, 1957, 1973; Snyder et al., 2000; Singh and Awasthi, 2010). The Hack index relates the channel slope at a point of a longitudinal profile to the distance from the river source by:

$$SL = \frac{\Delta H \times L}{\Delta L} \quad (1.2)$$

Analyses of the relations between channel steepness, uplift rate and erosivity show channel steepness correlated with tectonic uplift, while bedrock erosivity indicates a dynamic adjustment to the tectonic conditions (Snyder et al., 2000). The dynamic adjustment involves complex feedbacks with channel steepness, width and sediment loads, and is strongly dependent on the lithologic, tectonic and climatic conditions Snyder et al. (2000). Accordingly, variations in channel steepness (or Hack index) were successfully used to identify active tectonics, and when combined with geochronological markers, also rates of displacement in numerous studies (e.g., Kirby, 2003; Wobus et al., 2006; Singh and Awasthi, 2010; Kirby and Whipple, 2012). However, also lithologic changes may be evident and can be distinguished from tectonics using, for example, independent estimates of basin-wide erosion rates (e.g., Cyr et al., 2014).

1.3.2 Fluvial incision rates

Fluvial incision rates determine how fast rivers lower minimum altitudes in a landscape. The rates of local base level lowering have many implications for the interpretation of longitudinal river profiles and of hillslope response processes in drainage basins. The quantitative data provide key evidences on response patterns to tectonic and climatic factors, and on the evolution of the river system (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001).

Determining rates implies to relate a quantity of fluvial incision to a certain time interval. This can be performed based on geomarkers of paleo-river levels above the present river. The *heights above the present river* and the *age of the geomarker* represent the absolute amount of vertical incision, and the elapsed time until the river reached its present level. Normalizing the incision rate estimates to yr (or multiples of that) enables straightforward comparison between river reaches or generations of geomarkers. But it needs to be remembered that those rates represent averages that integrate over the conditions since the formation of the geomarker. The time scale dependence induces a transient signature in the incision rates that becomes evident when averaging over long time spans such as $10^4 - 10^7$ yr as steady-state of tectonic and climatic conditions becomes less likely (Finnegan et al., 2014).

- **Fluvial terraces** provide suitable geomarkers for incision rate calculations in erosional landscapes such as high mountains. Terrace altitudes above a modern river record periods of fluvial stability followed by incision (e.g. Burbank et al., 1996; Vandenberghe et al., 2011). The changes in the fluvial dynamic relate to tectonic and climatic factors. Their respective roles on triggering sediment deposition (or strath formation), terrace abandonment and subsequent incision may be discussed based on spatial and temporal correlations of terrace altitudes (e.g., Pazzaglia et al., 1998; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Formento-Trigilio et al., 2002; Bridgland and Westaway, 2008; Carcaillet et al., 2009; Pan et al., 2009).

Global comparison of fluvial terraces indicates complex feedbacks between tectonic uplift combined with cyclic climate (e.g., Bridgland and Westaway, 2008; Westaway et al.,

2009). Regionally consistent development of terrace staircases reveal links to the cyclic glaciations during the Quaternary as the primary drivers of sediment generation and water discharge (e.g., Hancock and Anderson, 2002; Formento-Trigilio et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2009). Terrace incision and preservation essentially rely on tectonic uplift and related relative base level lowering (e.g., Bridgland and Westaway, 2008; Pan et al., 2009; Vandenberghe et al., 2011). Without relative base level lowering, fluvial sediments rather form stacked or over- and onlapping deposits as observed, for example, in sedimentary basins (Vandenberghe et al., 2011). Differential uplift may further cause small-scale variations in stream power across tectonic units that lead to the formation of localized terraces between areas of relative subsidence (Vandenberghe et al., 2011). However, the interpretation of incision rates in terms of relative bedrock uplift rates or climatic control remains debated (e.g., Leland et al., 1998; Formento-Trigilio et al., 2002; Carcaillet et al., 2009; Pan et al., 2009). It requires careful evaluation of intrinsic effects of the studied fluvial systems. Timescale dependencies relate to process response times (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007) and preservation of records over time (Sadler effect, Sadler 1981). Prolonged incision further induces effects on the river evolution by, for example, channel narrowing or drainage re-organization in concert with thresholds of hillslope response (e.g., Burbank et al., 1996; Ouimet et al., 2009; Vandenberghe et al., 2011; Finnegan et al., 2014).

Dating of fluvial terraces is possible by several geochronological methods, but the selection of a suitable technique depends primarily on the material that builds the terrace. Strath terraces represent flat surfaces of carved bedrock, while sedimentary terraces result from fluvial sediment aggradation (e.g., Anderson, 2010).

- **Bedrock exposure ages** can be calculated based on *cosmogenic nuclide (CN) techniques* (e.g., Nishiizumi et al., 1989; Cerling and Craig, 1994; Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Granger et al., 2013). The physical process behind is in situ production of CN in surface rocks by the cosmic ray flux and the related increase of the CN concentration proportional to time (e.g., Granger et al., 2013). When the rate of CN production at a location and the accumulated CN concentration are known, one can calculate the exposure age for the studied site (e.g., Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Dunai, 2010; Granger et al., 2013). Solving the age-equation based on the ratio between CN concentration (C_{total}) and production rate (P_i , with i denoting the different production pathways for a given CN) additionally relies on the nuclide in use. Many geo-scientific studies employ the radionuclides ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al . To account for radioactive decay, calculations need to include the nuclide-specific decay constant λ :

$$C_{total} = \sum_i \frac{P_i}{\lambda} (1 - e^{-t\lambda}) \quad (1.3)$$

Of main concerns for the applicability to bedrock surfaces are the presence of suitable target minerals, and the stability of the rock surface. A well explored target mineral, for example, for ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al would be quartz (e.g., Lal and Arnold, 1985; Gosse and Phillips, 2001). The production rates of CN in quartz are measured at reference sites

of well known exposure histories. Such sea level high latitude references require scaling to the site of study as the rate of CN production depends on the position within the earth's geo-magnetic field and on the altitude (e.g., Cerling and Craig, 1994; Gosse and Phillips, 2001). For this purpose, several scaling schemes were introduced (e.g., Lal, 1991; Stone, 2000; Dunai, 2001; Lifton et al., 2005; Desilets et al., 2006) that are now routinely integrated in available calculation tools such as CRONUS (Balco et al., 2008) or in various script-based analytical routines such as for matlab (Hidy et al., 2010). Or one combines available concepts in individual **R** or GRASS GIS-based routines to allow full control of each calculation step and adjustment of parameters in case new physical results on nuclide behavior demand recognition in calculations. This was the case, for example, for the radionuclide ^{10}Be with a new half-life of (1.387 ± 0.012) Myr (Korschinek et al., 2010). Depending on the time of exposure, also variations of the geo-magnetic field affect the CN production and hence, require integration for older surfaces (e.g., Dunai, 2001). Production rates further require correction for shielding against the 'open sky' cosmic particle flux due to topography, snow or vegetation cover (e.g., Codilean, 2006; Norton and Vanacker, 2009; Dunai, 2010). Shielding even may prevent surface dating when the strath terrace is mantled by fluvial sediment layers from change in fluvial dynamic, aeolian caps of specific climatic periods or mass movements from adjacent hillslopes.

The required stability of the rock surface refers to inheritance of CN inventories from the earlier exposure history. The inventory is only zeroed when surface processes eroded the mean penetration depth of the cosmogenic particle flux before the fresh surface is again exposed (Dunai, 2010). But also erosion during the time of exposure affect age results when not detected as the production declines exponentially when penetrating into rock material. Then erosion of the rock surface where most CN are produced, can result in significant age underestimation. Among others, Gosse and Phillips (2001), Dunai (2010), and Granger et al. (2013) provide concise overviews on CN techniques and their application.

New is the possibility to *date bedrock exposures by luminescence signals*. The approach is still in the explorative stage (Sohbati et al., 2012). The observation behind is that the depth of the bleaching front migrates from freshly exposed surfaces into the rock dependent on time. First successful ages were estimated by measuring the luminescence signals depth-resolved to a depth of >10 mm and calibrating against a bleaching-depth profile of known age.

- **Sedimentation ages** of fluvial terraces are delivered by *luminescence dating techniques*. In certain cases it may be adequate to use ^{14}C -dating techniques, but one needs to make sure about the synchronicity between the sedimentation process and the start of the ^{14}C -clock for dead organic material (e.g., Anderson, 2010). In this respect, luminescence techniques are superior as they directly date the time since the sediment is shielded from sun light (e.g., Aitken, 1998; Preusser et al., 2008). The method is based on the time-dependent accumulation of a luminescence signal in certain minerals (dosimeter) such as quartz and feldspar. The signal represents excited charges of the mineral's crystal lattice, induced by natural ionizing radiation from radioactive nuclides (basically ^{238}U , ^{235}U , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K) and cosmic rays (primary electromagnetic soft component and muonic hard component, Prescott and Hutton e.g., 1994, 1995). The energy is stored stably at geologic timescales, until the next event of light exposure (bleaching) or heating

Figure 1.6: The principle behavior of luminescence signals in a dosimeter used for dating showing the cycles of signal growth during burial times and signal reset during sediment transport and corresponding light exposure according to Bailey and Arnold (2006). Short light exposure or low bleaching rates cause residual signals, while differences in the growth rate of the burial dose (e.g., due to variations in sensitivity or microdosimetry) may induce additional variability of measured signals.

stimulates the emission of the accumulated signal in form of light (e.g., Aitken, 1998). The emitted luminescence signal is proportional to the amount of absorbed energy (dose, given in Gy). Luminescence ages can then be calculated based on the absorbed dose of the dosimeter (paleodose) and the rate of dose delivered by natural radiation (dose rate):

$$t = \frac{\text{paleodose}}{\text{dose rate}} \quad (1.4)$$

The applicability of luminescence techniques for dating fluvial terrace in high mountains depends basically on the luminescence properties (sensitivity, reproducibility) of the used dosimeter, and the sufficiency of signal reset before sedimentation (Fig. 1.6). Low sensitization of sediments in high mountains relates to few sedimentation cycles (Pietsch et al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012) and may result especially for quartz in problematic luminescence signals (Preusser et al., 2006). Advantageous is the fast optical bleaching of quartz (e.g., Wallinga, 2002) for fast, short-distance and turbulent processes in mountain areas. Feldspar shows generally brighter luminescence signals, probably also due to the additional dose rate from the internal ^{40}K (Huntley and Baril, 1997).

However, the ability to absorb doses is primarily defined by the availability of defects in the crystal lattice (impurities or holes) that allow the storage of excited charges. The depth of those defects (traps) represents the stimulation energy needed to release the stored charges and directly relates to the emission spectrum of the luminescence signal. The mineral-specific wavelengths for stimulation and detection are summarized by Krbetschek et al. (1997). Suitable stimulation wavelengths require a minimum energy to address a stable signal component, and a clear difference from the detection wavelength. Those preconditions have many implications for the measurement of the luminescence signal.

Choosing between feldspar and quartz decides whether infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) or optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) is preferred, and which respective optical filter is needed for detection (Krbetschek et al., 1997; Aitken, 1998, e.g.). Available measurement systems (e.g., RisøTL/OSL readers, Lexyg system) provide typical stimulation units for blue OSL (470 nm), green OSL (532 nm) and IRSL (830 nm) but may be adjusted to explore further stimulation-detection windows. For example, luminescence signals from yellow stimulated luminescence (590 nm) of feldspar have shown reliable results in laboratory tests and dating application (Lauer et al., 2012).

The energy needed to address stable signal components implies that unstable charges in low traps are also released and measured. Preheat eliminates the unstable trapped charges before signal measurement (Aitken, 1998; Murray and Wintle, 2000). The temperature sensitivity of the luminescence signals is further used during signal stimulation. Elevated temperatures (e.g., 125 °C for quartz OSL, 50 °C for feldspar) support emission and prevent re-trapping of charges during stimulation (Aitken, 1998; Murray and Wintle, 2000). The fact that higher preheat temperatures result in more and more stable charges left, is used in investigations especially on the dating limits of luminescence methods, and led to the introduction of procedures that measure an elevated temperature signal directly after the standard measurement (e.g., postIR-IR techniques, e.g., Buylaert et al. 2009; Thiel et al. 2011).

Feldspar is prone to an anomalous signal loss (fading) causing a systematic underestimation of IRSL ages (Wintle, 1973; Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). Several studies evidence anomalous fading dependent on temperature (e.g., Thomsen et al., 2008). Krause et al. (1997) found no fading in their samples from Antarctica. Low fading in sediments from high mountain areas was shown, for example, in the Swiss Alps and foreland (Preusser et al., 2001, 2003; Preusser and Schlüchter, 2004). Storage tests confirmed no significant signal loss (Gaar and Preusser, 2012; Lowick et al., 2012). The signals of feldspar indicate negligible effects from anomalous fading when deeper traps are addressed by the high preheat (320 °C) and stimulation temperatures (290 °C) of postIR-IR measurements (Thiel et al., 2011). The measurement of a stable signal from feldspar was further achieved using yellow stimulated luminescence (Lauer et al., 2012).

Determining the dose equivalent to the measured luminescence signal (equivalent dose) requires to assess the dose-response behavior of the sample (Aitken, 1998; Murray and Wintle, 2000). The relation varies also between individual grains, and so do luminescence signals although the absorbed doses may be similar. Hence, equivalent doses rely on the comparison of the natural signal to those measured after irradiation with known laboratory doses. A widely used and adapted standard measurement protocol is the single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol introduced by Murray and Wintle (2000). The protocol comprises a sequence of measurement cycles of preheating and luminescence stimulation of natural signal, regenerated-dose signals and test dose signals. The regenerated doses intend to bracket that of the natural signal, and additional cycles of zero and repeated doses record the signal's recuperation and reproducibility (Fig. 1.7). Applying the same measurement protocol to sets of sub-samples or grains reveals the distribution of equivalent doses within a sample. Data scatter results from the material's luminescence properties, and from instrumental, and dose rate uncertainties (e.g., Aitken, 1998; Cunningham et al., 2011). The scatter increases when the material experienced

Figure 1.7: Exemplary single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol applied to an quartz OSL sample (TA110817N13-14) from the Pamir. The measured OSL signals reveals the natural luminescence response to known laboratory doses and enable to determine the specific dose-response curve (or growth curve) of an aliquot/grain in order to estimate the equivalent dose of the natural signal (plots were generated using the R package 'Luminescence', Kreutzer et al. 2012).

differential bleaching, or sediment mixing incorporated older or younger material. In this context, also the aliquot size matters because only single grain measurements can detect the actual range of equivalent doses, while multiple grain measurement yield averaged signals (Duller, 2008; Cunningham et al., 2011; Arnold et al., 2012). But single grain signals are susceptible for additional variations that may arise from inhomogeneities of the radiation and stimulation units (Duller, 2008), and in quartz analyses only few grains contribute to the signal of multiple grain aliquots (e.g., Heer et al., 2012).

Statistical analyses of the dose distribution represent the key to determine the portion of well bleached signals, and select the appropriate age model for paleodose calculation (e.g. Olley et al., 1998; Bailey and Arnold, 2006; Arnold et al., 2007; Galbraith and Roberts, 2012). Non-skewed distributions indicate well bleaching, and paleodose calculation is based on simple measures such as the arithmetic mean or median, or on the central age model (CAM) or common age model (COM), introduced by Galbraith et al. (1999). Differential bleaching results in skewed distributions with higher values increasingly affected by residual signal components. The minimum age model (MAM, Galbraith et al. 1999) and several statistical approaches (e.g., Olley et al., 1998; Fuchs and Lang, 2001; Lepper and McKeever, 2002) showed successful detection and exclusion of residual signals by results in agreement with independent age control. Sediment mixing causes multi-modal distributions induced by different age populations in the sample. Un-mixing of dose populations is possible using the finite mixture model (FMM, Galbraith and Green 1990), but requires single grain measurements. Signal averaging of multiple grain measurements causes phantom populations inadequate for age estimation (Arnold and Roberts, 2009; Arnold et al., 2012).

CN depth profiles enable to date the exposure time of sediments forming the terrace

surface (e.g., Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Dunai, 2010; Granger et al., 2013). The difference to CN-based bedrock dating lies in the fact that sedimentary surfaces are less stable compared to bedrock terrace surfaces, and the sediment may have acquired already CN before deposition (e.g., Granger et al., 2013). The method uses the declining CN production equivalent to the attenuation of the cosmic ray flux when penetrating the Earth's surface. The CN concentration at the surface reveals robust exposure ages, when measured values decline approximately exponential with depth, no hiatus indicates erosion or sedimentation, and negligible signals at the profile bottom show no inheritance (Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Hidy et al., 2010). The combined analyses of two nuclides enables to evaluate results based on different half-lives and production rates of nuclides, for example, of ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al (Gosse and Phillips, 2001). However, the application to fluvial terraces in high mountains is complicated by low surface-stability and alteration of fluvial layers may limit the depth of consistent sediment that can be analyzed for inheritance. Depth profiles across different sediment layers are less adequate as the material potentially differs also in its sedimentation history and consequently, in its inheritance, or requires time consuming analyses of many samples to distinguish inheritance and sedimentation cycles (e.g., Hidy et al., 2010).

1.3.3 Basin-averaged erosion rates

Erosion rates averaged over a certain drainage area are used in studies of tectonic-climatic-feedbacks and landscape evolution. Estimates of erosion rates reveal surface response patterns dependent on the time scale of the chosen method (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001; Garzanti et al., 2007; Lupker et al., 2012). Thermochronology indicates to the long-term erosion at the scale of 10^6 yr, CN techniques average conditions at the order of 10^4 yr, and river sediment loads reveal variations within 10^1 yr (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001; von Blanckenburg, 2005).

- **Thermochronology-based erosion** can be constrained from the cooling history of rocks during exhumation through the upper crust of the Earth (Kirchner et al., 2001; Reiners and Brandon, 2006). The exhumation provides the reference for the mass removed from the surface, at rates corresponding to the age-depth path of the rocks. The method uses the products of radioactive decay that retain since minerals cooled down to certain closure temperatures (Reiners and Brandon, 2006). The thermally sensitive onset of the radioactive clock is used by (U-Th)/He, fission track, and Ar/Ar dating techniques (Farley, 2002; Ehlers and Farley, 2003; Reiners and Brandon, 2006). Cooling ages can be transformed into exhumation rates, when the thermal gradient of the studied area is known (e.g., Braun et al., 2012).

The exhumation rates allow constraints on erosion rates under steady-state conditions of the paleo-topography (Mancktelow and Grasemann, 1997). However, the effects of varying thermal gradients or paleo-topography on exhumation and respective erosion rates are more difficult to assess (Valla et al., 2011). Attempts to resolve variations in erosion and paleo-topography include, for example, combined vertical and horizontal sampling or numerical models of crustal heat transport (e.g., Valla et al., 2011; Braun et al., 2012).

The time scales related to crustal exhumation imply that the estimates of erosion integrate over varying tectonic and climatic conditions (Godard et al., 2014). Spatial and temporal variations in exhumation may induce changes in the geothermal gradient that

do not necessarily correspond to recent conditions or their derivatives (e.g., Valla et al., 2011; Ehlers and Farley, 2003). Also the response mechanisms of erosion to climate are largely averaged as even the major climatic fluctuations during the Quaternary operated at shorter time scales. Effects from cyclic precipitation (e.g., annual, seasonal) or glaciations during the Quaternary are masked behind the long-term adjustment of erosion to exhumation, while the erosional response to climate operates at shorter time scales. Thus, thermochronology is primarily used to reveal long-term trends associated to the evolution of mountain belts (Reiners and Brandon, 2006).

- **Cosmogenic nuclide (CN)-based techniques** for basin wide erosion rates serve as a reference for the "natural background" of millennial-scale conditions (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001; von Blanckenburg, 2005). The principle interactions of cosmic ray flux with the Earth's surface remain as described for CN exposure dating (bedrock, depth profiles), only that now erosion is included.

Assuming constant erosion over a certain period of time induces a proportionality between CN concentration in river sediments and exposure time in source areas (Brown et al., 1995; Bierman and Steig, 1996; Granger et al., 1996; Kirchner et al., 2001). The longer material stays in the zone of cosmic ray interaction with the Earth's surface, the higher gets the CN concentration. Erosion at the surface brings constantly new material into the zone relevant for CN production. The depth of this zone is described by the mean attenuation length of the different cosmic ray particles and is mainly dependent on the density of the material (e.g. Granger et al., 1996). For silicate bedrock, the mean attenuation depth (z^*) of cosmic rays is typically ~ 60 cm (e.g., Lal, 1991; Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). Assuming that all the eroded material in a basin finds finally its way into the rivers, where the material can be sampled and analyzed for its CN concentration (Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). Calculating erosion rates from the CN concentration C in the river sediments then requires only to know the productions rates in the basin:

$$\varepsilon = \left(\frac{P}{C} - \lambda \right) \times z^* \quad (1.5)$$

, where λ refers to the decay constant of the cosmogenic nuclide in use. Representative values for P need correction for shielding S . Uncertainties relate especially to the variable altitudes within basins that are relevant for scaling the reference production rates to the site of interest (e.g., Brown et al., 1995; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). Determining P and S for each basin cell of digital elevation models (DEM, cf. Fig. 1.8) reveals the effects of hypsometric variations (Codilean, 2006; Norton and Vanacker, 2009). Representative values for P and S account for the hypsometric variations by statistic analyses of their respective frequency distributions.

The CN concentration measured in the modern river sediments is inversely proportional to erosion under certain assumptions (comprehensive summaries by e.g., von Blanckenburg 2005; Dunai 2010). Most important are steady state conditions of the system, meaning that the CN input by production in bedrock surfaces of the basin equals the CN concentration of fluvial sediments being transported out of basins (Bierman and Steig,

Figure 1.8: Topographic effects on the production of cosmogenic nuclides.

1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). Steady state is a largely scale-dependent concept. For CN-based erosion rates, steady state is reached when conditions stay constant over the time required to erode the attenuation depth z^* (Lal, 1991) as this represents the averaging time (T_{ave}) of the acquired CN inventory of the eroded material (e.g., Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). For example, erosion rates of 0.1–1.0 mm/yr imply an averaging time of 6×10^3 yr to 6×10^2 yr, and consequently deliver information at millennial scale.

Another issue is the precondition expressed by ‘*Let nature do the averaging*’. This refers to the assumption, that the material delivered from the different surfaces within the basin are well mixed in the sampled river sediments to represent the average conditions of the basin (e.g., Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). This requires one further consideration. The transport time of the sediments from eroding surfaces to the basin outlet (sampling site) should be short compared to T_{ave} (e.g., Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). Effects of CN acquisition during transport may be relevant when along stream samples show increasing values although basin properties do not change significantly.

Bias in the basin-wide averaging of sediments arises when certain basin portions deliver significant quantities of material to the river channels that did not experience the inferred basin-wide production rate. Of main concern are glaciated areas and mass wasting processes such as landslides (e.g. von Blanckenburg, 2005; Heimsath and McGlynn, 2008; Yanites et al., 2009; Dunai, 2010). Both deliver large quantities of sediment with negligible CN concentrations from shielded positions. While for landslides, the low concentrations may reflect the actual fast surface erosion of a certain area within the basin (e.g., Brown et al., 1995), sampling positions need careful selection to avoid the effects from single landforms but to reveal the average conditions of the basin. In large basins, effects on erosion will be averaged due to the stochastic nature of landslides (von Blanckenburg, 2005; Yanites et al., 2009; Dunai, 2010). The effects from glaciers are problematic as they contribute material at rates independent from production rates expected from DEM analyses. Ice enhance the attenuation of the cosmic particle flux before reaching the rock surface (e.g., Cerling and Craig, 1994). Additional bias arises from variations on the extent of glaciers within T_{ave} , a period that is significantly longer than available climate data and short for paleo-reconstructions.

Keeping the preconditions and scale-dependencies in mind, the CN-based erosion rates

fill the gap between the time scales of thermochronology and fluvial sediment load measurements (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001). The millennial scale rates allow to estimate the natural 'background' erosion without recent perturbations such as land use (e.g., Granger et al., 1996). The pattern of erosion provides valuable data on the factors controlling the efficiency of sediment transport out of basins. Comparing basin-wide erosion rates to fluvial incision provides insights into the adjustment of hillslope processes to local base level lowering, and consequently evidence the state of landscape evolution.

- **Sediment loads in rivers** represent the flux of eroded material in a basin. The sediment flux scales with short-term erosion rates for entire basins, when the hillslope sediment supply connects directly to the river channels without significant storage times, and when other processes of sediment transport out of the basin is insignificant (Summerfield and Hulton, 1994; Dadson et al., 2003). Then, the sediment volume per time unit can be translated into surface lowering of the upstream area using the bedrock densities found in the basin.

In the rivers, the sediment can be transported as bedload, suspended load and dissolved load. Estimates of the total sediment discharge require the assessment of each component, but representative values are often difficult to assess. Their contribution varies considerably between regional settings (Summerfield and Hulton, 1994). Suspended sediment and bedload comprise about $(70 \pm 28) \%$ and $(30 \pm 28) \%$, respectively (Dadson et al., 2003). Especially bedload is difficult to measure, but comprises a large proportion of high mountain sediment flux (e.g. Pratt-Sitaula et al., 2007), and also the suspended load varies within the river cross section. The local hydraulic conditions of the riverbed and effects from upstream areas induce along stream variations, but fluctuations occur also under steady conditions (Turowski, 2010). Both affect the representativity of in-situ measured fluxes from hydro-stations.

With increasing grain sizes of the sediment load, fluxes become less continuous and rather exhibit episodic transport events when the fluvial capacity and sediment supply are sufficient (e.g. Singh et al., 2007; Turowski, 2010; Andermann et al., 2012). The high variability of sediment fluxes demand for high temporal resolution and continuity of measurements (e.g., Morehead et al., 2003; Dadson et al., 2003). Available records from station networks typically cover several decades and provide important high-resolution data for the analyses of relations between discharge generation, and precipitation or temperature, and their consequences for sediment supply to river channels.

The decadal records allow important constraints on the response times of erosion to triggering events (e.g., storms, seismicity; Dadson et al. 2003), but may be short for capturing the full range of effects from magnitude-frequency distributions of sediment fluxes. Particularly landslides comprise large sediment translocations with significant contribution to hillslope lowering (e.g. Burbank et al., 1996). The infrequent nature of large mass wasting processes implies difficulties to extrapolate the measures of erosion to longer time scales (Hovius et al., 1997; Kirchner et al., 2001), at which additional response mechanisms control erosion (e.g., Burbank et al., 2003). Despite the difficulties to assess representative values, the magnitude and patterns of continuous measurements from station networks provide important data on short-term mechanisms of erosion, and enable ground-control for hydrological models (e.g., Andermann and Gloguen, 2009)

1.4 Research objectives in the Pamir

1.4.1 Preconditions and research needs in the Pamir

What is the motivation to study the surface processes in Pamir? The answer to that lies in the specific setting of the Pamir, while the magnitudes and control-response mechanisms of the Quaternary landscape evolution are largely unknown. The specific configuration of ongoing, intra-continental deformation, and the transitional position between two atmospheric circulation systems promotes the Pamir for studies of surface response processes, and allows to test the relations between control factors found in other actively deforming, high mountains.

The debate on the factors controlling mountain evolution within the India-Asia collision zone focusses on the southern escarpment of the Himalayas (e.g., Lavé and Avouac, 2001; Burbank et al., 2003; Vance et al., 2003; Bookhagen et al., 2005; Garzanti et al., 2007; Gabet et al., 2008; Godard et al., 2010; Burbank et al., 2012; Lupker et al., 2012; Godard et al., 2014; Scherler et al., 2014). The complex feedbacks are driven by the steep altitude rise, heavy monsoonal rainfall and tectonic uplift. The inferred dominance of tectonics or precipitation on erosion seems scale dependent in space and time, especially related to the extreme seasonal variability of precipitation and long-term persistence of tectonic uplift across a crustal ramp.

The different configuration of the Pamir provides the ideal setting to contribute to the debate on control factors. Tectonic studies of the Pamir focus on the long-term evolution and its links to the Tibetan Plateau, while constrains on the tectonic evolution younger than 2 Myr rely on few data (e.g., Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Strecker et al., 1995; Schwab et al., 2004; Cowgill, 2010; McGraw et al., 2010; Schmidt et al., 2011; Bershaw et al., 2012; Stübner et al., 2013). Nevertheless, seismicity, tomography and geodetic data evidence active deformation concentrated at the Pamir margins (e.g., Fan et al., 1994; Reigber et al., 2001; Koulakov and Sobolev, 2006; Mohadjer et al., 2010; Ischuk et al., 2013; Schneider et al., 2013; Sippl et al., 2013), and extension at the plateau. Also the climatic conditions represent very complex conditions within the transition from Westerly-dominated conditions towards monsoon-influence in the south. Additionally, glacial records indicate significant paleo-climatic variations (Zech et al., 2005; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012).

How those specific preconditions affect the response mechanisms of surface processes is unknown. The drainage architecture evidences major perturbances or re-organizations, but yet, no data on erosion and fluvial incision is available. The main tectonic structures may have dictated flow orientations but also the cyclic changes of climate may play an important role. The overall dry conditions make the Pamir sensitive to especially those climatic variations that control discharge. Furthermore, the dominating Westerlies allow to study the role of winter precipitation that may induce different feedbacks as inferred in the monsoon-dominated Himalayas.

1.4.2 Thesis scope and format

This cumulative thesis comprises five research papers of which three are published in peer-reviewed international journals, one is accepted and one is in the final preparation stage. All are first author contributions with substantial support from co-authors. The work was carried out within the DFG funded Tien Shan-Pamir Geodynamic Program (TIPAGE), and the collaborative work with the universities of Zurich, Bern, Stockholm and Cologne, and with the R Luminescence developer team.

The selected research papers combine reviews of tectonic and climatic aspects with morphometric analyses and geochronological techniques in order to determine the variability of surface processes. The patterns and magnitudes of surface processes are the keys for evaluating the factors that control the mountain evolution in the Pamir. The four main chapters address the following principle research issues:

- Relations between tectonics, climate and morphometry in Pamir (Chapter 2)
- Adequate techniques for luminescence dating of sediments from high mountain areas (Chapter 3)
- Controls on spatial and temporal variations of fluvial incision rates along the Panj river (Chapter 4)
- Controls on the variability of erosion in the major sub-basins of the Pamir river network (Chapter 5)

Individual chapters present the main research questions, methods applied and discuss the key findings of each research issue. The final chapter (Chapter 6) gives a synopsis of the main findings and outlines further questions that may be addressed in future studies.

Relations between tectonics, climate and morphometry in Pamir

Chapter 2 gives a review on the tectonic and climatic setting of the Pamir. This includes details to understand the assemblage of major tectonic units and describes the zones of neo-tectonic activity. Remote sensing data illustrates the distribution of moisture supply from the two prevalent atmospheric circulation systems, and consequently, the availability of water as an agent for geomorphological work. Additionally, a review on the glacial geochronology in Pamir is included to elucidate the surface response to paleo-glaciations.

The patterns of tectonic and climatic factors provide potential predictors for the variability of surface processes. Their effects on surface processes are evaluated by several morphometric indices at different scales. The drainage architecture provides an overview of local perturbances or long-term persistence of flow orientation at the regional scale. The topographic swath profiles describe the altitude variations by transects across the Pamir Plateau towards the different plateau margins. Local measures of morphometry provide profiles along and across the trunk river in order to determine the relative variations of fluvial incision.

The derived pattern of fluvial incision is then analyzed based on the longitudinal profile of the Panj. The actual river profile is compared to modeled graded river profiles and to the patterns of tectonic and climatic factors in order to reveal the evolution of the Panj river network and the major controlling factors behind.

Adequate techniques for luminescence dating of sediments from high mountain areas

Two main aspects require attention when dating sediments from high mountain areas by luminescence techniques. The material used for luminescence dating can involve challenges related to low sensitivity of luminescence signals or low precision in the dose-response behavior. Transport-related effects can induce differential signal reset and sediment mixing. This implies that material from high mountain areas needs to be tested for reliable signal properties. This often demands for extensive measurements to ensure adequate instrumental set up and data treatment.

Chapter 3 addresses both, the analytical and material-related challenges with two sub-chapters. The analytical challenges comprise the measurement of statistical meaningful numbers of sub-samples and adjustment of measurement conditions to ensure reliable luminescence signals. The amount of acquired data and their statistical analyses demands for flexible and transparent data processing routines. An example for a typical routine from data import to age modeling using the **R** package 'Luminescence' is elaborated in Chapter 3.2.

The material-related challenges highlight the need of investigating the luminescence properties of the sampled material. Selecting multiple grain or single grain techniques for quartz, K-feldspar and plagioclase measurements induce certain advantages or drawbacks. Their potentials and limitations are tested in Chapter 3.3 using material from rock glaciers. Such material represents among the most challenging sediments regarding signal sensitivity, signal reset, sediment mixing and dosimetric inhomogenities. The investigations focus on the mineral-specific luminescence properties, dose distribution statistics and age modeling, including tests of the influence of overdispersion on age model results.

Controls on spatial and temporal variations of fluvial incision rates along the Panj river

Fluvial incision comprises an important proxy for landscape evolution as it defines the local base level lowering within basins and triggers the response of adjacent hillslopes. Chapter 4 presents the first quantitative estimates of fluvial incision along the Panj. The incision rates are based on optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating of fluvial terraces and kinematic global positioning system (GPS) measurements of terrace heights.

With respect to the specific luminescence challenges studied in Chapter 3, sediment dating focussed especially on reliable OSL data acquisition and processing. Robust terrace dating involves OSL signal analyses for adequate measurement conditions, aliquots size and dose-response behavior. The degree of bleaching and sediment mixing is examined by dose distribution statistics and age modeling.

Terraces selected for analyses represent the fluvial incision along the Panj where it collects the discharge from major tributaries at the western margin of the Pamir. Here, the trunk stream is ideally suited to record changes in incision across the main tectonic structures. The variability of fluvial incision is discussed for temporal controls related to (paleo-)climatic changes and spatial controls using the geomorphometric indication of the river profile, valley shape ratios and Hack index.

Controls on the variability of erosion in the major sub-basins of the Pamir river network

Basin-wide erosion rates provide further information on the pattern of landscape evolution. They reveal the average sediment transport out of upstream areas and the hillslope response

to fluvial incision. Chapter 5 presents the first millennial, basin-wide erosion rates using cosmogenic nuclide (CN) techniques. Measurements of the ^{10}Be concentration in the target mineral quartz involve accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS) at the DREAMS (DREsden AMS, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf, Akhmadaliev et al., 2013) facility.

Sampled basins in Pamir represent the Panj basin at several locations along the trunk stream as well as the major tributaries. Sampling localities resolve variations in erosion at the Pamir Plateau, the southern and the western Pamir margins. For better differentiation between basin units, an area-weighted and a slope-weighted approach for the approximation of sub-basin erosion rates are introduced.

The factors that control the magnitude of erosion are discussed based on the degree of determination between erosion and basin properties such as altitude variations, slopes, precipitation and permanent snow and ice cover. Correlation analyses focus on linear regression and also include multiple linear regression to study the inter-dependence of factors as some factors possibly control erosion only under certain preconditions. The connectivity of sediment supply from hillslopes and fluvial sediment transport out of basins is discussed by comparing the CN-based erosion rates to the OSL-based incision rates presented in the previous Chapter 4.

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2 Tectonics, climate and topography in Pamir

2.1 Regional background

In the Pamir, the collinearity of mountain ranges and the river network suggests a major control from the India-Asia collision since the Cenozoic. Rivers that drain the Pamir Plateau show a predominant, east-west orientation. In contrast, the south-north orientated trunk stream, the Panj river, cuts across the major tectonic units of the Pamir at the western Pamir margin. At the same time, the river course comprises the transient conditions between a monsoon-influenced climate at the southern margin and a Westerlies-dominated climate towards the north-west. A comprehensive overview on the tectonics and climate in the Pamir is given for a sound regional characteristic of the spatial and temporal variations of the control factors. Chapter 2.2 concerns particularly those control factors that potentially affect the Late Quaternary surface processes. This includes:

- Characterizing the main tectonic units and neotectonic activity of the Pamir
- Characterizing the climatic conditions and paleo-climatic variations
- Analyses of topographic patterns and the longitudinal profile of the Panj river

The review of the tectonic units focusses on the Cenozoic domes that characterize the Pamir Plateau and the predominant orientation of mountain ranges. Evidences of neotectonic activity refer to recent studies on seismicity and on location and style of active deformation. Remote sensing data illustrates climatic gradients (precipitation, snow) imposed from the Westerlies and monsoon approaching the Pamir margins. A review of the glacial chronology is included for evaluation of impacts from past-climate changes on surface processes. The surface expression of both control factors is discussed with respect to the morphometry of the orogen (large-scale topographic swath profiles) and of the river network (longitudinal river profile, valley shapes).

- **Paper I (Chapter 2.2)**

Fuchs, M.C., Gloaguen, R., Pohl, E. (2013): Tectonic and climatic forcing on the Panj river system during the Quaternary. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 102 (7), 1985-2003. doi: 10.1007/s00531-013-0916-2

2.2 Paper I: Tectonic and climatic forcing on the Panj river system during the Quaternary

Tectonic and climatic forcing on the Panj river system during the Quaternary

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Surface processes involve complex feedback effects between tectonic and climatic influences in the high mountains of Pamir. The ongoing India-Asia collision provokes the development of east-west-trending mountain ranges that impose structural control on flow directions of the Pamir rivers. The evolving relief is further controlled by strong moisture gradients. The decreasing precipitations from the southern and western margins of the Pamir Plateau to its center, in their turn, control the emplacement of glaciers. Chronologies of glacial records from the Pamir Plateau attest for strong climatic variability during the Quaternary. Corresponding remnants of glacial advances suggest glacial morphodynamic restricted to >4,000 m a.s.l. since marine isotope stage (MIS) 4. The Panj, the trunk river of Pamir, deflects from the predominant westward drainage, connecting its main tributaries at the western margin of the drainage basin. The geometry of the river network and the pattern of incision characterize the Panj as a composite river. River reaches of indicated low incision coincide with west-trending valleys, parallel to domes and their bounding faults. Valley shape ratios reflect increased incision in north-trending sections, but do not match with changes in the catchment geometry or erodibility of rock types. Modelled riverbed profiles distinguish three Panj reaches. The upstream increase in convexity suggests successive river captures in response to local base-level changes. The northward-deflected river reaches link the local base levels, which coincide with the southern boundaries of the Shakh dara and Yazgulom Dome and Darvaz Range. We argue that tectonics plays a large role controlling the drainage system of the Panj and hence surface processes in the Pamir mountains.

Keywords:

Pamir, Panj river network, Tectonic geomorphology, Glacial chronology, Fluvial incision, River profiles

1. Introduction

The Pamir mountains provide an outstanding natural laboratory to study the role of the forces that drive mountain shaping. The Pamir constitutes the westernmost part of the India-Asia collision zone, one of Earth's largest and most rapidly deforming intra-continental orogens (e.g. Le Pichon et al., 1992; Reigber et al., 2001; Mohadjer et al., 2010). Surface processes in such active orogens involve erosional and depositional mechanisms and their complex feedbacks, controlled by the interplay between tectonic and climatic forcing (e.g. Hack, 1957).

In the Pamir, the northward drift of the Indian plate (Reigber et al., 2001; Mohadjer et al., 2010) imposes relief along east-west-trending mountain ranges. The generated anisotropic relief guides the powerful Panj river system, which drains the Pamir. While most of the Pamir rivers align to the predominant east-west orientation of mountain ranges, the major trunk river, the Panj itself, deflects several times toward the north, thus cutting through the

major Cenozoic structures of the Pamir. The predominantly westward drainage and its major river deflections enable to determine changes in the role of factors controlling the organization of the river network. The fluvial incision along the Panj river course, especially across the main tectonic units of Pamir, constitutes a proxy of local river response. It records variations in forcing on local base levels in response to potential structural control from Late Cenozoic tectonics. The corresponding pattern of river incision in turn sets the pace for related surface processes such as hillslope response and hence relief evolution. The ability of the river system to incise and transport the material supplied to the river channels out of the orogen is also governed by the fluvial discharge (e.g. Leland et al., 1998; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Brookfield, 2008) and therefore by climatic factors, especially precipitation (rain, snow). In the Pamir, the moisture supply is driven by the interaction of the midlatitude Westerlies, the Indian summer monsoon (ISM), and the Siberian High with the relief (e.g. Benn and Owen, 1998; Röhringer et al., 2012). Glacial features on the Pamir Plateau and in the west-trending valleys of the major Pamir rivers recorded considerable climatic variations during the Quaternary. Glacial landform dating, especially cosmogenic exposure dating

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of moraines at the Pamir Plateau, suggests the maximum Late Pleistocene glaciation during the marine isotope stage (MIS) 5 or earlier (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The timing and successively reduced extent of glacial advances indicate cycles asynchronous to those of the Northern Hemisphere. However, the Late Quaternary shifts in atmospheric circulations and their complex effects on the glacial history of the Pamir are yet not well understood (e.g. Röhringer et al., 2012).

In this paper, we evaluate the role of tectonic and climatic factors controlling the organization of the Panj river system during the Late Quaternary. Recording the effects of both tectonic and climatic forcing on local base level and fluvial discharge, the Panj river system constitutes an ideal proxy to understand the surface processes in Pamir. To characterize the structural control on the relief evolution, we first present the tectonic framework of the Pamir, with a focus on the timing and rates of neotectonic deformation and dome exhumation. We then describe the feedback effects between the evolving relief and the prevailing atmospheric circulations using remote sensing data. We include a review of the glacial chronologies to evaluate the extent and timing of glacial advances, which have affected the Pamir during the Late Quaternary. Based on the geomorphological characteristics of the Panj drainage system, we finally discuss the respective roles of tectonics and climate in controlling the surface response processes in Pamir.

2. Tectonic background

2.1. Tectonic setting and structural units of Pamir

The Pamir mountains form the northwestern continuation of the Tibetan Plateau at the northwestern end of the Indian–Asian collision zone (e.g. Schwab et al., 2004; Robinson et al., 2004). They are confined by the Hindu Kush to the south and the Tien Shan to the north, the Tajik Depression and the Tarim Basin limit the Pamir to the west and east, respectively (Fig. 1A, B). The first-order Pamir structure is characterized by Paleozoic to Mesozoic sutures, magmatic belts, and crustal blocks.

The tectonic units of Pamir are assumed to consist of along-strike equivalents of the Tibetan Plateau that accreted to the Eurasian plate (Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Schwab et al., 2004; Cowgill, 2010; Bershaw et al., 2012). Classically, the Pamir is divided into three distinct tectonic terranes: the Northern, Central, and Southern Pamir (Fig. 2; Burtman and Molnar (1993)). The Northern Pamir consists of a Paleozoic–Early Mesozoic suture, arc and accretionary wedge, similar to the Kunlun and the Xil-Songpan-Ganzi system of northern Tibet. The southward following Tanyamas suture (TS in Fig. 2) is part of the Tibetan Jinsha suture. The Central Pamir comprises Paleozoic–Jurassic platform rocks with Middle–Late Triassic granitoid intrusions, which indicate a possible correlation to the Quiangtang block. The striking similarities to

Tibet are also expressed by the east-west-trending anticlinal structure of the Central Pamir. Granitoids attributed to the Rushan–Pshart suture (RPS in Fig. 2) are Jurassic (Schwab et al., 2004). The Southern Pamir consists of Proterozoic to Mesozoic gneisses and metasedimentary rocks with Cretaceous–Neogene granitoid intrusions, equivalent to the Lhasa block in Tibet (Vlasov et al., 1991; Schwab et al., 2004).

Structural domes expose crystalline basement rocks that are mantled by lower-grade to non-metamorphic cover rocks; these domes cover up to 30% of the surface exposure of the Pamir (Vlasov et al., 1991; Brunel et al., 1994; Robinson et al., 2004; Schwab et al., 2004; Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2012).

The Kurgovat dome exposes high-grade rocks metamorphosed in the Triassic (Schmidt et al., 2011). In contrast, the domes in the Central (Yazgulom, Sarez, Muskol and Shatput Domes) and Southern Pamir (Shakh dara–Alichur Dome) exhumed high-grade, middle to lower crustal metamorphic rocks of Cenozoic age (Fig. 2; Schmidt et al. (2011); Stübner et al. (2012)).

An Eocene–Oligocene burial and Miocene exhumation history applies for the Central Pamir Yazgulom, Sarez, Muskol and Shatput Domes (Fig. 2). Robinson et al. (2004) attribute their continuation in the eastern Pamir to the Muztagh Ata and Kongur Shan Domes. Cooling ages along the Kongur Shan fault imply exhumation rates of 4.2 mm/yr for the last 7 Myr (Robinson et al., 2010). The largest of the Pamir gneiss domes is the 350–90 km Shakh dara–Alichur composite gneiss dome in the Southern Pamir. Its structural geometry, kinematics and timing of exhumation involve >35–21 Myr crustal thickening, 21–2 Myr north-south extensional doming, and footwall exhumation (Stübner et al., 2012). Cooling ages date the peak exhumation of the Shakh dara and Yazgulom Domes (cf. Fig. 2) to around ~15 Myr (Stübner et al., 2012). However, the detailed exhumation mechanisms and history of the Central and Southern Pamir domes still need to be refined.

2.2. The crustal deformation in Pamir

The dominant east-west orientation of mountain ranges (cf. Figs. 1, 2) is largely controlled by the crustal shortening due to the Cenozoic India–Asia convergence (Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Bershaw et al., 2012) and still ongoing northward propagation of the Indian plate (Reigber et al., 2001; Mohadjer et al., 2010) in line with local block rotation (Waldhoer et al., 2001). In contrast to models invoked for the neighboring Tibetan Plateau, crustal flow does not seem to be involved in the evolution of Pamir (Gloaguen and Ratschbacher, 2011). The India–Asia convergence resulted in thrust and strike-slip faulting, which follows the trend described by the Pamir salient (Bershaw et al., 2012). The active frontal ranges bend nearly 180° from northern Afghanistan to western China. The Pamir includes two intermediate-depth intra-continental subduction zones resolvable by seismicity and

Figure 1: Tectonic setting of the Pamir within the intra-continental collision zone between India and Asia. **A** Location at the western end of the Himalaya–Tibetan orogen, **B** Distribution of seismic activity (Sippl et al., 2012) and location of the Swath profiles P1-4 (gray lines).

tomography (southern Pamir and Hindu Kush slabs; e.g., Koulakov and Sobolev (2006)).

The active deformation at the frontal part of the orocline is characterized by the south-dipping Main Pamir Thrust (MPT). The MPT is interpreted to be the surface expression of the seismically active southward subduction (cf. Fig. 1B), which has accommodated ~ 300 km of shortening during the Cenozoic (Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Fan et al., 1994). The thrusting along the MPT is indicated to begin during the Late Oligocene and accommodates today 50 % of the India–Asia convergence (Coutand et al., 2002; Bershaw et al., 2012). Shortening rates derived from GPS measurements reach about 20 mm/yr or more across the MPT (Reigber et al., 2001; Mohadjer et al., 2010). Additional shortening of ~ 300 km may have occurred along Pamir internal thrusts (Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Waldhoer et al., 2001). The timing of this shortening might include pre-Cenozoic periods (Robinson et al., 2007).

The lateral margins of the northward overthrusting

along the MPT represent strike-slip faults that suggest transpression at the Darvaz Fault Zone (DFZ) in the west and transtension at the Karakoram Fault Zone (KFZ) in the east (e.g. Fan et al., 1994; Robinson et al., 2007). The Late Quaternary lateral motion is ~ 12 mm/yr across the DFZ (Trifonov, 1978). The active strike-slip motion along faults parallel to the KFZ in southeastern Pamir suggests < 1 mm/yr

(e.g. Strecker et al., 1995). Cowgill (2010) determined an average dextral strike-slip rate of 11–15 mm/yr at the eastern margin of Pamir over the Late Cenozoic. Chevalier et al. (2012) suggest constant along-strike-slip rates of > 5 –11 mm/yr at the KFZ for the last 200 kyr, while Sobel et al. (2011) suggest slow dextral strike-slip rates of 1.7–5.2 mm/yr or less between the Eastern Pamir and the Tarim Basin over the past 5–3 Myr. To the south, the boundary of the Pamir is complex and our field observations indicate a major east-west, low-angle normal fault bounding the Shakh dara Dome to the south, referred to as Southern Pamir Shear Zone (SPSZ, cf. Figs. 1, 2).

Figure 2: Main tectonic structures that characterize the Northern, Central, and Southern Pamir (N Northern, C Central, S Southern, DFZ Darvaz Fault Zone, MPT Main Pamir Thrust, KS Kunlun Suture, TS Tanymas suture, RPS Rushan-Psart-Suture, GSZ Gunt Shear Zone, SPSZ Southern Pamir Shear Zone, KD Kurgovat Dome, YD Yazgulom Dome, SAD Shakh dara-Alichur Dome, SD Sarez Dome, MD Muskol Dome, SPD Shatput Dome), and the Panj drainage network.

The elevated Pamir Plateau (Ducea et al. (2003), cf. Figs. 1, 2, 3) is crosscut by N–S striking normal faults, extending from the Karakul Lake to the Wakhan of Afghanistan (cf. Fig. 1B). Kinematic models of the active extension in the Pamir discuss topographic collapse (Brunel et al., 1994), radial overthrusting (Strecker et al., 1995), and links to the right-slip KFZ (Ratschbacher et al., 1994). Along the eastern boundary of the Pamir, the crustal extension is accommodated along the Kongur Shan extensional system (e.g. Fan et al., 1994; Robinson et al., 2007). Robinson et al. (2007) link the overall pattern of decreasing magnitude of east-west extension from ~ 35 – 30 km in the north (Kongur Shan) to ~ 20 km (Muztagh Ata) and < 3 km (along the Tashkorgan fault) in the south to the radial overthrusting of the Pamir salient along the MPT. The east-west extension at the Kongur Shan normal fault likely prevailed since 7–8 Myr (Robinson et al., 2004, 2010). Apart from those extensional structures, active internal deformation is limited. A series of north-west-striking right-slip faults in the southeastern Pamir determined slip rates of < 1 mm/yr (Strecker et al., 1995; Robinson et al., 2007).

Active seismicity (Fig. 1B; Sippl et al. (2012)) and our own structural studies indicate that tectonic activity is

now concentrated along the orogen margins and along the Karakul rift zone, whereas other internal structures, such as the dome margins, seem to be less active. The seismic network geometry does not allow for resolving earthquakes in Afghanistan, and therefore, it is still unclear whether some structures are currently seismogenic in Badakhshan (Schurr et al., 2011; Sippl et al., 2012). Faults associated with the DFZ such as the Central Badakhshan fault have prominent morphological characteristics and seem to merge with peripheral dome structures. Nonetheless, seismic activity, albeit weak, attests the existence of active deformation along the Gunt and the Vanj valleys along the northern boundaries of the Shakh dara and Yazgulom Dome (Fig. 2).

3. Climate

3.1. Climatic setting

The climate of the Pamirs is characterized by the transition between two atmospheric circulation systems (Fig. 3A). Most precipitation is provided by the Westerlies in the winter and spring seasons and by the ISM in the summer and autumn seasons. The interplay with the

Figure 3: The pattern of moisture supply (TRMM product 3B42 V7) to Pamir controlled by the prevalent atmospheric circulations of the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon and their interplay with relief. **A** Distribution of the mean (1998–2012) annual precipitation, including the assumed influence from predominant atmospheric circulations of the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon. **B** Mean (1998–2012) winter/spring precipitation (given as a sum of January, February, March, and April). **C** Mean (1998–2012) summer precipitation (given as a sum of June, July, August, and September)

orographic rise directs the Westerlies north- and southwards of the Pamir and causes concentrated precipitation at the margins of the orogen. Towards the eastern plateau, precipitation decreases (cf. Fig. 3B, compare to Fig. 5, profile P3). Precipitation from the ISM decreases from the southeast toward the central Pamir and toward the Tibetan Plateau (Fig. 3C). High mountain ranges, such as the Karakoram and Hindu Kush, effectively shield the Pamir from the ISM (Fig. 3, compare to Fig. 5, profile P4).

In order to outline the seasonal and the orographic effects on the local climate, we use precipitation distribution and permanent ice or snow cover as proxies (cf. Figs. 3, 4, 5). We use the precipitation data from the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) product 3B42 V7 (Huffman et al., 1997, 2007). This data set combines infrared (IR) and microwave information from TRMM instruments to adjust merged IR precipitation data of several weather satellites and includes rain gauge measurements where feasible. The pattern of average annual, average winter/spring (Jan–Feb–Mar–Apr), and average summer/autumn (Jun–Jul–Aug–Sep) accumulated precipitation is derived from the TRMM data product in $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ spatial resolution. TRMM3B42 data have been reported to be in agreement with in situ data for example in the Himalayas (e.g. Roe, 2005; Bookhagen and Burbank, 2010; Andermann et al., 2011). The detection of snowfall can be subject to high bias and is in the focus of current data improvement (Prigent, 2010). Even though TRMM is designed for detecting rainfall, it has been shown that mi-

crowave imagers are capable of detecting snowfall (Skofronick-Jackson et al., 2004). Besides, TRMM3B42 is a data set resulting from the joint post-processing of remote sensing data and gauge stations (Huffman et al., 1997, 2007). Additionally, our own validation with in situ gauges confirms that TRMM3B42 data are adequate to assess bulk precipitation in the Pamir (Pohl and Gloaguen, 2012). The fact that there are data records of TRMM3B42 in winter gives further evidence of snowfall detection. This is of special interest for the western Pamir, which receives most of the precipitation as snow in winter and spring.

The time span of TRMM acquisition (launched in 1997) does not represent a climatic record of at least 30 years, but in contrast to weather re-analysis data, e.g., the ECMWF ERA Interim (Dee et al., 2011), TRMM3B42 has a superior spatial resolution and thus improves the recognition of regional features. We assume that the 14-year time span is representative of the climatic conditions in the Pamir. The TRMM-derived precipitation data suggest up to threefold, Westerlies-induced precipitation gradient from western to eastern Pamir (Figs. 3B, 5, swath profiles P2 and P3) and up to fivefold, ISM-induced gradient from southeastern Hindu Kush ($\sim 1,600$ mm/yr) toward the eastern Pamir (< 300 mm/yr) (Figs. 3C, 5, swath profile P4). Overall, the west-east and south-north gradients in precipitation reflect a semiarid western and an arid central-eastern Pamir (cf. Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006); Barry (2008)).

The distribution of permanent ice and snow cover is af-

Figure 4: The timing and extent of glacial advances in Pamir. Tien Shan and Karakoram since the last glacial cycle. **A** Location of study sites concerning Quaternary glacial advances in relation to the distribution of permanent snow and ice cover (black, based on MCD12Q1). The comparison to altitude contour lines illustrates the superimposition of moisture gradients on the extent of glaciers (altitudes given in m a.s.l.). **B** Overview about the glacial chronology for Pamir, Tien Shan, and Hindu Kush inferred from numerical dating of glacial deposits

ected by the temperature gradient at rising altitudes and by the moisture supply. Consequently, the low precipitation at the eastern Pamir Plateau restricts permanent ice and snow cover to much higher altitudes compared to that in western Pamir (cf. Fig. 4A, B). The extent of individual glaciers is sensitive to the regional and local air temperature and precipitation (Carrasco et al., 2005). It hence enables to discriminate between different regional climatic settings, refine conclusions drawn on precipitation distribution alone, and to reconstruct paleoclimatic conditions based on glacial remnants.

The steady-state condition of a glacier in equilibrium with the climate (net balance = 0) results in glacier areas of accumulation and ablation. The line dividing these areas is the equilibrium line altitude (ELA) (Nesje, 1992). There are many different approaches for the calculation of the ELA, e.g., median elevation of glaciers (MEG), toe-to-headwall altitude ratio (THAR), ratio of the accumulation area to total area (AAR), or temperature- and precipitation-related approaches (for an overview, see Nesje (1992); Carrasco et al. (2005)). Nesje (1992) points out that glacier morphology and relief have substantial influences on the ELA calculation, in particular if the ablation area is at a different slope than the accumulation area. We use the ratio of the accumulation area to the total area (AAR). It allows us to pinpoint regional differences of modern glaciers extents and, additionally, to provide a basis for comparison with paleo-ELA estimated from glacial remnants. Several studies proposed a ratio of 0.6 ± 0.05 for steady-state conditions for cirque/valley glaciers (Nesje, 1992). The advantage of the AAR method lies in its ap-

plicability to remote sensing data because glaciated area and elevation data are easily accessible. We use MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer) Land Cover Type data MCD12Q1 version 051 (Strahler et al., 1999) to extract the glaciated areas according to the annual predominant land cover type classification of the IGBP (International Geosphere Biosphere Programme). We superimpose the corresponding class for snow and ice on elevation data to a SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) digital elevation model (DEM) (Jarvis et al., 2008). Using the AAR of 0.6 ± 0.05 (60 % of glacier area above and 40 % below the ELA), we extracted the elevation information for the 40th percentile. As we cannot assess steady-state conditions, we also accounted for negative and positive mass balances with ratios of 0.5 and 0.8 (50 and 20th percentile), respectively (Nesje, 1992). The average ELA for the Tien Shan, western and eastern Pamir, Hindu Kush, and the Karakoram Range is given in Table 1. The contour lines in Fig. 4 highlight the differences between the ELA of different regions, even closely located. In general, ELA for regions at the outer margins of the orogen shows lower values than those for the eastern Pamir and the Karakoram Range. Permanent ice and snow extent are strongly correlated with precipitation distribution (Figs. 3A, 4), suggesting precipitation as the limiting factor for glacier extent in Pamir.

3.2. Quaternary glacial chronology

3.2.1. Geochronological framework

Stratigraphic correlations of moraine generation provided a first framework for the glacial chronology in Cen-

Table 1: ELA approximation for the eastern and western Pamir and adjacent regions.

Region	50th [m a.s.l.]	40th [m a.s.l.]	20th [m a.s.l.]
Tien Shan [70-80E, 40-45N]	4,277	4,206	4,040
Hindu Kush [70-74E, 34-36N]	4,664	4,579	4,379
Western Pamir [66-73E, 37-40N]	4,854	4,750	4,473
Eastern Pamir [73-78E, 37-40N]	5,100	5,037	4,881
Kharakoram Range [74-80E, 34-37N]	5,323	5,184	4,841

The 50th, 40th and 20th percentile of extracted elevation data superimposed by MCD12Q1 permanent snow and ice cover. Percentiles represent negative, steady-state, and positive mass balances according to AARs of 0.5, 0.6 and 0.8, respectively.

tral Asia (summary in Table 2; Zabiroy (1955); Dodonov (2002)). But a robust reconstruction of the paleoclimate in Pamir, which allows the interpretation of links to shifts in the atmospheric circulation patterns and the comparison with adjacent regions or even global trends, relies on numerical dating. Especially, ^{10}Be surface dating of moraine boulders has proven to yield quantitative measures for deciphering the regional context of those glacial records (cf. Fig. 4). We present here the glacial chronology in Pamir based on the available published records. However, the glacial remnants in Pamir indicate a high spatial variability and constraints about the glacial chronology rely on few study sites on the Pamir Plateau (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012), where today the climate is relatively dry (cf. Figs. 3, 4). Unfortunately, age constraints of glacial remnants from west-trending valleys at the Pamir margins are not available yet. Hence, possible paleogradients of glacial extends toward the west are not resolved. We include the adjacent areas of the Tien Shan to the north and the western Tibet to the south, to shed further light onto the varying prevalence of the Westerlies on the ISM. It allows us to evaluate the influence of shifting atmospheric circulations and the corresponding timing and extent of glacial process regimes during the Late Quaternary.

3.2.2. Oldest glacial advances (Early MIS 4 and older)

According to the oldest dated glaciation in the Pamir, an early local glacial maximum during MIS 4 or older has been proposed (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). This early, most extensive glaciation is stratigraphically associated with the Early Pleistocene East-Pamir complex (cf. Table 2; Dodonov (2002)) or might represent remnants of a much-debated Late Pleistocene ice sheet covering the entire eastern Pamir (e.g. Kuhle, 1997, 2011). Exposure dating of the oldest moraines from Lake Yashilkul (Fig. 4, no. 9–11), from the Southern Alichur Range (Fig. 4, no. 12), and from the Ailuitek Pass (Fig. 4, no. 8) determines two age clusters at 93–136 kyr (MIS 5) and 60–86 kyr (MIS 4/Late MIS 5) for the

Table 2: Stratigraphic correlation of glacial advances in Pamir (Zabiroy, 1955; Dodonov, 2002).

Moraine generation	Description	Thickness [m]
Q1 (Early Pleistocene, 1 - 1.5 Ma)	West	Tupchak/Kokbai complex ~1,000
	East	East-Pamir complex ~500 - 800
Q2 (Middle Pleistocene, 120 - 300 ka)	West	Bartang complex ~300 - 400
	East	Murgab complex ~200 - 300
Q3 (Late Pleistocene, 30 - 44 ka)	West	Badakhshan complex <200
	East	Alichur complex
Q4 (Holocene)	Complex of all younger moraines	

Pamir Plateau (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The dated latero-frontal moraine that represents the most extensive moraine generation at Yashilkul is assumed to have crossed the Yashilkul valley reaching the opposite valley slope (Zech et al., 2005a; Röhringer et al., 2012). Although the continuation of this latero-frontal moraine is hidden below the water surface of the present-day Yashilkul, sediments on the northern shoreline might reflect this glacial advance to have reached the floors of inner-plateau valleys in Pamir. The finer-grained moraine matrix corresponding to the dated boulders at the Southern Alichur Range is assumed as washed away (Abramowski et al., 2006). Two comparable age clusters can also be recognized in the eastern Pamir. Boulder exposure ages and electron spin resonance (ESR) ages associate the oldest, most extensive moraines in the Tashkurgan valley (Fig. 4, no. 15; Owen et al. (2012)) and in the Muztagh Ata and Kongur Shan (Fig. 4, no. 13 and 14; Seong et al. (2009a); Wang et al. (2011)) to MIS 5/MIS 6 and MIS 4/MIS 5.

Exposure ages from the oldest moraine generation further north in the Tien Shan agree to the indicated timing of glacial advances in the Pamir. The remnants of the most extensive glaciations correspond to advances during MIS 6 at At-Bashy (Fig. 4, no. 4; Zech (2012)), to Early MIS 5 and again during MIS 5–4 in the north and east Tien Shan (Koppes et al., 2008), and to pre-MIS 4 in the Turkestan Range (Fig. 4, no. 6; Abramowski et al. (2006)).

However, the timing of the oldest glacial advances on the Pamir Plateau does not indicate a clear link to those south of Pamir. In the Chitral valley (Fig. 4, no. 16; Owen et al. (2002b)), Hindu Kush, no comparable glacial sediments were found and dated. Owen et al. (2002a) recognized two Late Pleistocene glaciations in the Hunza valley (Fig. 4, no. 17), but could only narrow the age to >60 kyr. Two much older glacial advances before 700 kyr and during MIS 6 or earlier were distinguished in the central Karako-

ram (Fig. 4, no. 18; Seong et al. (2007)).

3.2.3. The last glacial cycle (MIS 4 and 2)

Prominent deposits of the last glacial cycle on the Pamir Plateau were dated to MIS 4 and MIS 2, and potentially to MIS 3, and suggest the local LGM during MIS 4 rather than during the global LGM during MIS 2 (Fig. 4A, B; Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006)). Successively less extensive glacial advances over the course of the Late Pleistocene reflect the sensitivity to the increasing aridity in High Central Asia (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Herzschuh, 2006; Koppes et al., 2008; Narama et al., 2009). This trend is also recorded in maxima of loess accumulation between 25 and 20 kyr in southern Tajikistan (Frechen and Dodonov, 1998). Causes of this increasing aridity are associated with the growing strength of the Siberian Anticyclone and a southward shift of the westerly jet stream (cf. Velichko et al. (1997); Hubberten et al. (2004); Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006)). During the global LGM, both coincide with the collapse of the ISM (Phillips et al., 2000; Kamp et al., 2004; Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006).

In Pamir, the second major advance is characterized by sets of latero-frontal moraines that accompany hummocky moraines. Such hummocky moraines are described from various locations throughout the Pamir and are associated with the Middle Pleistocene Bartang/Murgab complex (Dodonov, 2002), but numerical age constraints are challenging. At Lake Yashilkul, the two lateral moraines represent a Late MIS 4/Early MIS 3 and a MIS 3 stages. The outer one reveals exposure ages from 77 to 57 kyr, while the inner lateral moraine dates to ~40 kyr (Fig. 4, no. 9–11; Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006); Röhringer et al. (2012)). The lateral moraines are difficult to correlate between study sites and do not allow for an identification of separate (re-)advances, also because their terminal parts are (glacio-)fluvially eroded (Röhringer et al., 2012). However, the indicated MIS 4 for the outer lateral moraine (Fig. 4, no. 10) agrees to exposure ages between 57 and 75 kyr of a latero-frontal moraine dated at the Southern Alichur Range (Fig. 4, no. 12; Abramowski et al. (2006)).

Exposure ages from the hummocky moraine itself, which reach the lake shoreline at lake Yashilkul, scatter between 65 and 12 kyr (Fig. 4, no. 9; Zech et al. (2005a)). Zech et al. (2005a,b) related the moraine generation to a cold period in western High Asia between 45 kyr and 52 kyr (Thompson et al., 1997) and hence argue the oldest ages to most likely represent the glacial advance during MIS 3. They refer the high scatter of younger ages to long-lasting ice decay and corresponding surface instability. However, they distinguish two subsequent glacial advances from the scattered ages, one at 30–27 kyr (MIS 3) and the other one at 24–22 kyr (MIS 2). A corresponding age cluster between 28 and 20 kyr from the southern Alichur Range (Fig. 4, no. 12) is associated with the Alichur complex (Dodonov, 2002). The timing may be linked to a phase of intensified

monsoon between 29 and 24 kyr (Bookhagen et al., 2005; Herzschuh, 2006). The timing of MIS 2 glacial advances at ~24–22 kyr and 20–18 kyr suggests slightly earlier or synchronous occurrence to the global LGM (~20 kyr). Several age clusters indicate phases of accelerated moraine degradation or several recessional glacial stages at 16–15 and ~12 kyr (Fig. 4, no. 9–11; Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006); Röhringer et al. (2012)). The glacial cycles in the Kongur Shan and Muztagh Ata, eastern Pamir, reflect basically the same pattern. The most prominent advance occurred during 87–66 kyr (MIS 4, local LGM) and the deposition of the hummocky moraines during 49–36 kyr (MIS 3). Younger exposure ages scatter between 27 and 13 kyr (MIS 2; Seong et al. (2009a); Wang et al. (2011)). Possible re-advances or recessional stages are indicated at ~16 kyr and 13–12 kyr (Seong et al., 2009a). No evidence for glacial advances at MIS 3, but for MIS 4 and MIS 2 is found to the south in the Tashkurgan valley (Owen et al., 2012).

To the north in the Tien Shan, surface exposure dating from the Alay-Turkestan Range (Abramowski et al. (2006); Fig. 4; no. 6 and 7), the At-Bashy (Zech (2012); Fig. 4; no. 4), and OSL dating from the Teskey Ala-Too and At-Bashy Ranges (Narama et al. (2009); Fig. 4; no. 3 and 4), correspond to a local LGM in Tien Shan during the Late MIS 4 or Early MIS 3. Koppes et al. (2008) distinguish a shift toward MIS 3 in the south and east Tien Shan (Fig. 4; no. 1 and 2). The less prominent glaciation and subsequent degradation during MIS 2 are linked to clusters of exposure ages around 22, 20–16, and 12–10 kyr (e.g. Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Narama et al., 2007).

South of Pamir, Owen et al. (2002b,a) found no evidence of a MIS 4 glaciation in the Hindu Kush and Karakoram mountains (Fig. 4, no. 16–18). The most extensive glaciation during 55–43 kyr, probably lasting until 27 kyr, represents the monsoon characteristic, local LGM during MIS 3 (Benn and Owen, 1998; Owen et al., 2002b,a). Several less prominent advances during 26–15 kyr (MIS 2) and earlier (Owen et al., 2002b,a; Seong et al., 2007) agree to the general trend of restricted MIS 2 glaciation in many areas of the Himalaya (Phillips et al., 2000; Richards et al., 2000a,b). In contrast, Kuhle (2011) infers an extensive ice sheet covering the Tibetan Plateau during the global LGM. Regional correlations and, in particular, the possibility of a Late Pleistocene plateau glaciation are still debated (for review, see, e.g., Derbyshire et al. (1991); Grosswald et al. (1994); Kuhle (2011)).

3.2.4. The Holocene (post-MIS 2)

The Early Holocene moraine generation at the Pamir Plateau might reflect phases of increasing moisture supply (cf. Abramowski et al. (2006); Fig. 4, no. 9–12), caused by phases of intensified ISM (for an overview phases of intensified ISM, see Bookhagen et al. (2005); Herzschuh (2006)). Ambiguously, they might also be linked to the temperature decrease during the post-Younger Dryas event at

~10.5 kyr (compare to Alay Range further north; Fig. 4, no. 7; Abramowski et al. (2006)). Evidence of younger glacial advances with potential links to the Westerlies-driven moisture increase during the Mid-Holocene (Herzschuh, 2006) are not resolved. Only the well-defined glacial advances in the eastern Pamir, at Muztagh Ata (Fig. 4, no. 13), record quasi-periodic climate oscillations throughout the Holocene (Seong et al., 2009a). Wang et al. (2011) distinguished two glacial stages at 1.5–0.4 kyr and during the Little Ice Age, which they attribute to Northern Hemisphere climate oscillations. However, Herzschuh (2006) proposes that Westerly-dominated regions have received reduced moisture since the Late Holocene.

In contrast, Koppes et al. (2008) describe limited glacial advances from the Tien Shan (Fig. 4, no. 1–2) associated with Mid- and Late Holocene. No Holocene moraines are dated in the Terskey Ala-Too and At-Bashy Ranges by Narama et al. (2007, 2009); Fig. 4, no. 3) and Zech (2012); Fig. 4, no. 5). In regions south of Pamir, Owen et al. (2002a) and Seong et al. (2007) assume the Holocene, characterized by less prominent glaciations to respond to Northern Hemisphere cooling cycles. Owen et al. (2002b,a) and Seong et al. (2007) describe a post-Younger Dryas-related glacial advance at ~10.8 kyr (Hunza valley, Fig. 4, no. 17) and Mid- or Late Holocene, and/or the Little Ice Age advances (Chitral valley and central Karakoram, Fig. 4, no. 16 and 18).

The sensitivity of the Pamir region to climatic changes has important implications for the glacial dynamic and hence for the reconstruction of paleoclimatic conditions ((Zech et al., 2005a,b). Its position within the transition zone between the Westerlies and the ISM suggests that shifts of the two atmospheric circulation systems can result in considerable changes in moisture supply to the region. Therefore, linking the Quaternary glacial chronology of the Pamir (overview in Fig. 4) to Northern Hemisphere cooling cycles or monsoon-driven (moisture) cycles is challenging. Existing ^{10}Be -based investigations of Zech et al. (2005a,b), Abramowski et al. (2006), and Röhringer et al. (2012) point toward glacial advances that are only partly contemporaneous with climatic cold phases in the Northern Hemisphere. Moraines associated with the characteristic, Westerlies-driven, last glacial maximum (LGM) during marine isotope stage (MIS) 2 are ubiquitously present, but they reflect significantly smaller extents compared to earlier Late Pleistocene advances. The maximum of Late Pleistocene glaciation in Pamir occurred most probably during MIS 4 or even before (cf. Zech et al. (2005a); Abramowski et al. (2006); Röhringer et al. (2012)). Furthermore, several exposure ages suggest glacial advances contemporaneous with the local LGM at MIS 3, typical for the ISM-driven Tibetan Plateau (Phillips et al., 2000; Kamp et al., 2004; Owen et al., 2008). This suggests that the glacial advances in Pamir are not only sensitive to the cold phases resulting from insolation minima but also to moisture advection from the prevailing atmospheric circulation (cf. Röhringer et al. (2012)). The records of mul-

tiple Late Pleistocene glaciation cycles outline the influence of glacial imprints due to erosion and the corresponding sediment flux on the Quaternary landscape evolution. Hence, past changes in atmospheric circulation patterns potentially contributed to the evolution of the drainage network by driving river discharge and sediment budgets.

4. Geomorphological characteristics

The surface processes respond to the described tectonic and climatic conditions. Both, the evolving relief and corresponding drainage network, record variations of surface processes. They indicate spatial and temporal changes in the respective roles of controlling factors that basically comprise both, precipitation and base level (e.g. Leland et al., 1998; Hancock and Anderson, 2002; Bull, 2007). While relief characteristics and drainage network indicate mainly regional trends, in particular proxies of fluvial incision, highlighted areas are affected by local changes along the course of a river. It is then possible to evaluate the potential culprits such as precipitation, catchment geometry, rock types, and tectonic structures (cf. chapters 2 and 3). We characterize the interplay between relief and precipitation of the Westerlies and the ISM along four swath profiles across the Pamir Plateau toward its margin (Fig. 5). We further focus on the pattern of fluvial incision along the Panj to resolve spatial variations and to detect the areas of increased riverbed adjustment that illustrates deviations from a graded river. As proxies for the fluvial incision, we combine variations in valley shape ratios along with indication from valley swath profiles (Figs. 6, 7) and that of the longitudinal profile of Panj (Fig. 8).

4.1. The relief

We extracted four swath profiles from a DEM of 30 m resolution to quantify variations in the topographic relief across the Pamir (location cf. Fig. 1B). The swath profiles represent the range of altitudes within 20 km broad swath running perpendicular to the defined, central profile line. For each consecutive profile segment, they show the mean altitude (gray line) as well as its maximum and minimum (gray shaded area). We superimposed TRMM annual precipitation data extracted along the same profile (Fig. 5).

The four swath profiles illustrate the variations in relief between the Pamir Plateau and its margins. The Pamir Plateau displays low variations relative to the mean altitude of ~4,500 m a.s.l. (cf. Fig. 5, swath profiles P1, P2, and P3). The minimum altitudes throughout the Pamir Plateau show a persistent level at ~4,000 m a.s.l. and witnesses a very flat isobase. The large areas of low frequent changes in local base levels indicate wide, flat intra-plateau valleys. River incision is not reflected below that elevation (cf. Fig. 5, swath profile P4). The indicated limited ability of rivers to transport material toward the plateau margins and out of the Pamir Plateau coincides with the

Figure 5: Swath profiles showing the mean altitude (*solid line*) and topographic variation (*gray shaded area*), extracted from a DEM (30 m x 30 m) within a distance of 10 km from both sides of the central profile line (P1–4, locations see Fig.1B) and the annual precipitation based on TRMM data (25 m x 25 km)

low amount of precipitation penetrating into the Pamir Plateau (cf. Figs. 3, 5). The second and third profiles (P2 and P3 in Fig. 5) illustrate the decreasing mean altitudes at the western plateau margin. High variations, especially at minimum altitudes, coincide with the gradient of Westerlies-induced precipitation. Deeply incised valleys outline the boundaries between mountain ranges and reflect river down-cutting far below 4,000 m a.s.l., resulting in high variations of the local base level (cf. Fig. 7, photographs D, E, and F). The intensities of monsoonal

precipitation attenuate before reaching the Pamir. The moisture gradient concurs with lower mean altitudes in the Karakoram Range along with high fluctuating altitudes (mean, minimum, and maximum) and deeply incised valleys (see Fig. 5, swath profile P4).

4.2. The pattern of fluvial incision

The pattern of fluvial incision along the Panj provides a valuable proxy to characterize areas of distinct surface response and more important, to outline the areas, that

respond to variations in tectonic and/or climatic forcing. The Panj constitutes the major trunk river, which connects the westward-orientated river network at the western margin of the drainage basin. Hence, the Panj river incision traces the variations along the west-trending main drainage orientation within its strongly asymmetric drainage basin. Its northward-deflected river sections with deeply incised valleys record the effects of the consecutive following structural units and confluences with major tributaries.

We describe the relative intensities of fluvial incision along Panj by its valley geometry perpendicular to the river course (Figs. 6, 7). Changes in the valley morphology indicate trends in valley slope response to fluvial incision and outline the areas of different control factors (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Singh and Awasthi, 2010). To characterize the valley morphology, we extracted elevation data along more than 160 Panj valley cross-sections from a DEM of 30-m resolution and 6 swath profiles (cf. Fig. 7). Calculated valley shape ratios (VSR) represent the ratio of the valley width divided by the mean heights of left and right drainage divides (Burbank and Anderson, 2001). Low VSR values suggest prolonged base-level changes and pronounced fluvial incision, whereas high VSR values indicate that the landscape is less affected by recent increase in discharge and/or relative base-level lowering (Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Bull, 2007). The trends in VSR document subsequent river segments that are characterized by valley sections with high VSR followed by sections of strongly decreasing VSR and separated by an abrupt increase in VSR (Fuchs et al., 2012). The wide valleys sections correspond in general to east-west-trending valleys and confluences of major tributaries. However, the evidence of abrupt valley widening also coincides with tectonic structures such as the SPSZ or the Gunt Shear Zone (GSZ; cf. Fig. 6). The valley swath profiles and photographs A and C in Fig. 7 represent the wide valley at the Pamir Plateau and parallel to the SPSZ. The lowest VSR correspond to zones, where the Panj deflects northward and cuts the Shakh dara, Yazgulom, and Kurgovat Domes (Figs. 6, 7).

4.3. Profile modelling

The longitudinal profile of a river being in dynamic equilibrium has a smooth concave-up form. The bedrock erosion rate of a channel is a function of the stream power incision law (Hack, 1973). The slope S of a channel is closely related to the drainage area (Hack, 1973) and the longitudinal profile length from river source (Hack, 1957):

$$S = k_1 A_1^{-\theta} \quad \text{or} \quad S = k_2 D_2^{-\theta}$$

where k and θ are constants, and D is the distance from the river source. The constants can be extracted from a logarithmic plot of slope versus distance or drainage area. The intercept and the slope of the linear regression determine k and θ . This scaling relationship is useful for reconstructing river profiles. Uplift and/or base-level

changes modify the original concave shape of the profile. The resulting knickpoint separates the initial profile into two concave parts. In the case of an uplifted area, the higher portion of the river will be steeper while the lower portion will keep its original shape. If the river is affected by a base-level fall, the two segments will have a similar steepness. Using the slope-distance relationship (i.e., calculating constants for one of the two segments of the river profile), we can reconstruct the theoretical river profile (i.e., without knickpoint) prior to the uplift or base-level fall. In addition, the difference in elevation between the theoretical initial profile and the segment that experienced the uplift or the base-level fall provides an estimate on the amount of vertical displacement.

Here, we construct theoretical profiles that fit the concave portions of the Panj best. As they follow the power-law function relying slope to distance along the river course, these river segments are considered in equilibrium (i.e., uplift is balanced by incision in a configuration where transport capacity exceeds sediment flux). Practically, we perform a least-squares linear regression of the adequate portions in a log-log representation of slope versus distance to source. We then reconstruct the length profile using the extracted parameters (slope and intercept of the regression). The code has been developed in the R environment.

The extracted longitudinal profile presented in Fig. 8 highlights the composite, non-equilibrated character of the Panj. The slope-distance analysis indicates four major zones in which the Panj fits modelled equilibrated curves, i.e., in the Tajik Depression, in the Darvaz Range, between the rivers Shiva and Gunt, and from the northward deflection of Panj to Wakhan river (Fig. 8). The modelled Panj river length profile fitted from the river course in the Tajik Depression (lowermost profile on Fig. 8, further called "base-level Tajik Depression [BLTD]") clearly indicates that most of the Panj river is incompatible with a base level in the Tajik Depression. It implies that the upstream portions of the Panj did not reach an equilibrated stage since being connected to Tajik Depression drainage.

By fitting the equilibrated portion in the Darvaz Range, the modelled length profile is ca. 400 m above BLTD and the upstream portion fits the actual Panj profile in the Shiva region. It could indicate that, although convex on a large part and thus in strong disequilibrium, this portion represents an original drainage basin. The convex portion deviated about 300 m from the equilibrated profile and is roughly located in the area of the Yazgulom Dome.

The length profile extracted by fitting the Shiva-Gunt section is 1,500 m above BLTD and the modelled upstream reach fits the actual Panj riverbed in the Langar, where the Pamir and the Wakhan rivers merge. We propose that the section between the rivers Shiva and Wakhan represents a drainage unit, that is, in disequilibrium from the Gunt to the north deflection of Panj. The convex portion is about 300–400 m about the equilibrated profile and fits with the extent of the Shakh dara Dome.

Figure 6: The characteristics of the Panj river network that drains the Pamir. Indications about the spatial and temporal variations of fluvial incision are illustrated by valley shape ratios along the Panj and timing of glacial advances at the Pamir plateau. The indicated locations of the valley profiles AF refer to the topographic profiles presented in Fig. 7 (abbreviations given in captions of Figs. 2, 8)

The last segment is represented by the Ishkashim-Langar section, which lies more than 2,200m above BLTD. The Pamir river (the uppermost reach of the Panj profile) does not fit at all with the modelled profile and we therefore assume that this portion represents a very recent capture of the Pamir river by the Wakhan-Panj system. The convex portion is about 100 m above the equilibrated profile. Low riverbed gradients reflect that the Pamir river barely incises the orogen upstream of the convex portion. Fluvial erosion did not constraint hillslope processes in this part of Pamir (cf. Fig. 7, profile A).

The comparison to river orientation and tectonic structures links the major convex zones to the Shakhdara and Yazgulom Domes with very low channel slopes at the southern dome boundary and strong increases at the northern boundary. The downstream, stepwise increases in catchment are in general not reflected in the longitudinal profile or correlate in magnitude with changes in riverbed slopes. The profile modelling clearly indicates that the Panj is formed by the juxtaposition of river segments with different base levels that are incompatible with the fluvial response of a single drainage system to a base level located in the Tajik Depression. An absolute timing of the different captures is impossible to infer from the profiles but the intensities of the deflections to the modelled equilibrated profiles are compatible with more recent reorganizations upstream.

5. Discussion

The described geomorphometric characteristics of relief and drainage network outline complex temporal and spatial

variability in tectonic and climatic forcing on shaping the Pamir. The crustal shortening from the ongoing India-Asia collision forces the drainage network to align to the induced relief of east-west-trending mountain ranges. Structural discontinuities, inherited from the successive accretion of terranes, comprise potential sources of differential tectonic forcing on local base levels, which control river incision and the reorganization of the drainage network, e.g., river deflections and capture (Hancock and Anderson, 2002; Bull, 2007).

The deeply incised Panj river sections connect the main tributaries, the Gunt and Shakhdara, Bartang, Yazgulom, and Vanj rivers that drain the Pamir to the west and parallel to tectonic structures. The Panj deflects from this super-imposed orientation northwards, cutting the southern and central Pamir domes, their bounding faults (e.g., SPSZ and GSZ), and other major Cenozoic structures, and then doubles back to the southwest before entering the Tajik Depression (Fig. 6). The northward deflections are parallel to known structures such as the Central Badakhshan fault and major lineaments parallel to the DFZ and observable on satellite data. The local differences in incision outline the response of the Panj to consecutive local base levels by the consistent pattern of fluvial incision illustrated by valley morphologies along with VSR

Figure 7: The valley profiles AF display the characteristic valley morphologies of the different river sections along Panj river. To avoid artefacts of profile extraction along a single line, we used swath profiles of 15 km width to describe the typical valley morphometry by the mean altitude (*solid line*) and deviation.

Figure 8: The longitudinal profile of Panj displays distinct, non-equilibrated river sections that are compared to the catchment, river orientation, and main tectonic structures (SPSZ Southern Pamir Shear Zone, GSZ Gunt Shear Zone, RPS Rushan-Psart-Suture, TS Tanymas Suture, KS Kunlun suture, DFZ Darvaz Fault Zone). The indicated locations of the valley profiles AF refer to the topographic profiles presented in Fig. 7.)

and profile modelling. The morphometric proxies distinguish basically two characteristic types of river sections, west-trending sections of low incision and north-trending sections of strongly increasing river incision.

The east-west-orientated southern part of Panj reflects two different units. The upper reach constitutes an extremely wide valley at $\sim 4,000$ m a.s.l., corresponding to the intra-plateau valleys with characteristic low slopes and river incision not cutting into bedrock (Fig. 7, valley profile A). The downstream continuation resembles a less wide valley at $\sim 3,000$ m a.s.l., but of roughly comparable low incision that exhibits a very straight river course along the SPSZ and parallel to the southern boundary of the Shakh dara Dome (Fig. 7, valley profile C). Similar valley morphologies are indicated for the southern boundary of the Yazgulom Dome. Minor, local valley widening is associated to confluences with other major tributaries such as the Gunt ($\sim 2,000$ m a.s.l.) and Vanj ($\sim 1,500$ m a.s.l.) rivers. The valley cross-sections and locally preserved glacial sediments document the influence of Quaternary glaciations, but as outlined above, such glacial inheritance is difficult to associate to glacial cycles of the Pamir Plateau without numerical dating.

In contrast, northward-orientated river reaches represent the Panj crosscutting the Shakh dara and Yazgulom Domes and corresponding faults. The indicated strongly increasing fluvial incision (cf. Figs. 6, 8) suggests the river to respond to local base-level changes (cf. Fig. 7).

Indicated reaches coincide with the Panj connecting the main tributaries at the western margin of the asymmetric drainage basin (Figs. 6, 7, photographs and valley profiles D, E, and F). The nearly perpendicular river deflections together with the apparent pattern of fluvial incision characterize the Panj as a composite river that responds to locally differential forcing (cf. Fig. 6). In particular, the modelled, equilibrated river segments fitted to the actual Panj profile indicate local base levels at ~ 400 , $\sim 1,500$, and $\sim 2,200$ m above the BLTD (Fig. 8). However, the three main reaches of the actual Panj river profile illustrate clear deviations from the modelled, theoretical profiles. The main convex zones indicate deviations above the theoretically equilibrated river to increase upstream from ~ 300 to nearly $1,000$ m (Fig. 8). The convex zones agree with the indication of increased fluvial incision and with the Panj cutting the Kurgovat, Yazgulom, and Shakh dara Domes. We attribute the indicated trend of consecutively increasing deviations of the actual Panj profile from equilibrated models to subsequent river captures in response to locally differential base-level control.

We can rule out erodibility variations caused by different rock types. First, most the Pamir is constituted by stacked units of different composition but relatively uniform erosivity of bedrock. It is challenging to single out units, which might be more easily eroded along the main rivers. Secondly, the major anomalies in the organization of the river network (Fig. 6) and in the river profiles

(Fig. 8) do not match with changes in rock types. Furthermore, the major confluences with Panj tributaries are not reflected by anomalies on the longitudinal profile. Erosivity and catchment geometry are not plausible for explaining the composite character of the Panj river.

The prevailing atmospheric circulations of the Westerlies and the ISM superimpose gradients of moisture supply on the Pamir relief (cf. Figs. 3, 5). Increased precipitation occurs during winter at the northwestern margin and therefore runoff is mainly controlled by temperature. To the south, the Karakoram and Hindu Kush mountains shield the Pamir from ISM-induced summer precipitation. Consequently, the central Pamir receives very little precipitation. The distribution of permanent ice and snow indicates moisture control by a rising ELA from $\sim 4,000$ m a.s.l. at the Pamir margins to $\sim 4,800$ m a.s.l. at the central plateau.

The gradients in precipitation correspond to specific relief morphologies (Fig. 5). The Pamir Plateau is characterized by low valley incision and smooth changes in local base level in contrast to its margins with deep incised valleys and high altitude variations (Fig. 5). We argue that the plateau has been shaped by glacial processes during wet periods and that, since the local LGM (during MIS 4 or earlier), increasing aridity limits surface processes. Corresponding fluvial capacities suggest only minor connectivity of sediment transport to the plateau margins. At the plateau margins, the currently highly incised valleys point toward fluvial processes that dominate the landscape evolution and over-print glacial landforms. However, control of the geometry of the river network (e.g., stepwise catchment increases due to confluences with tributaries) on the locally differential incision along the Panj is not indicated.

Past shifts in the atmospheric circulation triggered substantial climatic changes. Reconstructions suggest a maximum depression of paleo-ELA between ~ 370 and ~ 260 during the Pleistocene (cf. von Wissmann (1960), Abramowski et al. (2006)). Local evidences indicate that the most extensive glaciations to have reached the floors of plateau valleys during MIS4/5 or earlier (Röhringer et al., 2012). A deeper paleo-ELA with a maximum depression of ~ 950 m have been suggested (Abramowski et al., 2006) but the timing and glacial extents are not resolved in the major Pamir rivers (cf. Fig. 4, no. 8–12; Fig. 6). As the ELA is mostly controlled by precipitation, the regionalization of local events is difficult. The disputed theory of a Late Pleistocene plateau glaciation in Central Asia assumes that a regionally uniform ELA depression of $\sim 1,000$ m (Grosswald et al., 1994; Kuhle, 1997, 2011) seems unlikely in Pamir. The two maxima in altitude frequencies at 3,600–4,100 m and 4,400–4,800 m a.s.l. are associated with the glacial erosion of two major Late Pleistocene glaciations at Muztagh Ata and Kongur Shan (Seong et al., 2009b). The lower maximum corresponds to the indicated local base level of the Pamir Plateau.

However, the few existing studies are concentrated on the Pamir Plateau and cannot fully resolve the glacial dy-

namics during the Quaternary and the possible gradients toward the margins. Large moraine remnants in the west-trending valleys are not dated yet and we are unable to set these glacial markers into context to moraine stages at the Pamir Plateau, potential rooting zones or the recent glaciation. Assuming an ELA depression analog to the Pamir Plateau, where the most extensive glaciations during/pre-MIS 4 reached the inner-plateau valley floors ($\sim 4,000$ m a.s.l.) and hence, glacial remnants in west-trending, lower altitude valleys ($< 3,500$ m a.s.l.) are older, may be erroneous. Due to the present, dry climate at the plateau, glaciers rise to higher altitudes compared to the margins (cf. Fig. 4A). But, the paleogradients of moisture supply and the links of glaciers that formerly occupied the west-trending valleys to potential rooting zones are largely unknown. One might argue that the west-trending valleys basically originate at the plateau suggesting links to plateau-internal rooting zones and corresponding glacial extents. However, potential paleogradients toward the margins need to be considered and require further investigations. Referring to the limited extent of glacial advances in neighbor regions (e.g., Hindu Kush and Tien Shan) and at the plateau, we suspect that glacial cycles did not cause or had only minor influences on perturbations of the Panj river dynamics at least since MIS 2 below $\sim 3,500$ m a.s.l. Also, the regional consistent indication of an increasing aridity in Central Asia, since MIS 4 suggests glacial processes restricted to higher altitudes and hence, caused an overall decreasing role of glaciers on surface processes especially at the Pamir margins. The sediments from the Quaternary glaciations are still present at the plateau in the form of moraine remnants and huge valley fills. Both, the geometry of the Panj network and the pattern of fluvial incision, cannot be explained by the last glaciations, which were mostly confined to the Pamir Plateau.

Brookfield (2008) highlights the interaction of tectonic processes, climate changes, and local random effects, e.g., of landslides, on the development of major river systems draining Central Asia. The neotectonic deformation, especially documented by the records of recent seismology, is concentrated at the Pamir margins (cf. chapter 2.2. and Fig. 1B, Schurr et al. (2011); Sipl et al. (2012)). The corresponding earthquakes trigger landslides of various magnitudes and comprise an important forcing on mass movements in the region. The major earthquakes in Pamir and northeastern Afghanistan resulted in massive valley damming landslides, causing the related rivers to form among the biggest lakes of the region, lake Sarez, Yashilkul, and Shiva (Shroder et al., 2011). The Panj valley itself shows no signs of such extreme events causing long-term valley blocking. The local sediment supply is governed by gravitational mass movements from adjacent hillslopes, such as rockfall and debris, and by fan sedimentation. The outlined river sections of steep slopes, especially in the northward-deflected part, and the seasonal highly concentrated melt-water allow the Panj to incise and erode the supplied sediments rapidly. There-

fore, we consider the effect of local mass movements on local base levels for river incision to represent only short-term ($<10^3$ years) perturbations.

Brookfield (2008) presents an alternative hypothesis that interprets the northward Panj sections as the original, predominant drainage orientation corresponding to other major rivers draining Central Asia. Several arguments point against the hypothesis of an antecedent river, but speak for successive river captures across the main structural units of Pamir. First of all, the asymmetric drainage basin with the Panj close to the western divide and predominantly westward flowing rivers are not characteristic for an established long-term, north-draining river network. Secondly, the Panj experiences multiple river deflections from the westward but also from the northward drainage, corresponding to southern dome boundaries and tectonic structures parallel to the DFZ. That suggests the pattern of fluvial incision observed in the longitudinal profile and VSR not solely explained by an antecedent, north-trending river responding to differential tectonic uplift. Lowest incision in west-trending reaches corresponds to low forcing on river response parallel to the Pamir domes and mountain ranges. The northward-deflected river reaches, which indicate much higher incision, link the modelled base levels across the tectonic structures but do not connect to a straight northward river course. Thirdly, the deviations of the actual river profile from the modelled equilibrated profiles suggest upstream decreasing profile adjustment in response to local base levels. We interpret the increasing convexity by decreasing time intervals since capture, resulting from successive upstream river captures. Although possible, the control of differential rock uplift on local base levels is not resolved in our data.

It is too early to definitely statute whether these captures occur along active structures or are following inherited discontinuities. Nonetheless, several geomorphological evidences are supporting the fact that the rivers are controlled by active structures. The river profiles of most Panj tributaries are disequilibrated, showing convex profiles when they cross the domes. The main tributaries of the Panj (Vanj, Yazgulom, Bartang, Gunt) are located at dome boundaries and are extremely linear. The drainage system of the Panj is highly asymmetrical, with the northward flowing Panj itself being almost located at the western drainage. The tributaries of the Panj are parallel to the main trunk at the southern boundary of the Shakh-dara Dome. The north-south linear structures guiding the Panj may be associated with active faults parallel to the DFZ and the Central Badakhshan fault, accommodating the northward motion of the Pamir indenter.

6. Conclusion

It makes no doubt that the shaping of Pamir is controlled by the complex interplay of tectonic and climatic forces, whereas the inhering fundamental question remains: what are their respective roles in the evolution of the Panj

river network? Ongoing intra-continental collision of the Indian and Eurasian plate results in east-west-trending mountain ranges, bending along major slip fault zones. The river network illustrates the structural control by the main westward draining rivers in Pamir, which coincide with the Shakh-dara and the Yazgulom Dome and related bounding faults. The northward-deflected sections of the Panj connect the main tributaries at the western margin of the drainage basin.

The interplay of the Westerlies and ISM superimposes gradients of moisture supply from the Pamir Plateau to its margins. Low amounts of precipitation limit recent ice and snow cover to high altitudes ([4,800 m a.s.l.], and the ability of rivers to incise and erode the sediment supplied to the wide plateau valleys. Low variations from the mean altitude of $\sim 4,500$ m a.s.l. and consistent local base levels at $\sim 4,000$ m a.s.l. on the Pamir Plateau reflect wide valleys and restricted fluvial incision. Glacial chronologies suggest an important influence of the glacial processes on the plateau relief. The maximum Quaternary glaciation during MIS 4 or earlier reached the inner-plateau valley floors. Successively reduced glacial extents agree to chronologies from eastern Pamir, Tien Shan, and Hindu Kush that correspond to an increasing aridity in Central Asia. Hence, glacial morphodynamics may be limited to the Pamir Plateau since MIS 4. The post-glacial fluvial dynamics on the plateau did not suffice yet to transport sediments to the margins. Glaciations that reached lower altitudes are indicated by moraine remnants within the west-trending, wide valley sections of the Panj river network by moraine remnants. The timing and potential rooting zones of glacial advances at the plateau are not constrained.

Toward the plateau margins, the gradients of increasing precipitation superimpose the regional pattern of decreasing altitudes and higher relief variations that differentiate the glacial-controlled plateau from its fluvial-driven margins. We argue that the climatic gradients are not plausible contributors for the control of the orientation of the river course and of the pattern of reaches with increasing fluvial incision along the Panj. The local base-level changes that drive the river incision do not match with variations in bedrock erodibility and do not correspond in magnitude to the increases in catchment from tributary confluences.

We propose that the Panj is a composite river of reaches that respond to distinct local base levels. Profile modelling of theoretical, equilibrated profiles fitted three main river reaches with base levels at ~ 400 , $\sim 1,500$, and $\sim 2,200$ m above the BLTD. The modelled base levels of theoretically equilibrated river sections correspond to the Darvaz Range, the section between the rivers Shiva and Bartang at the southern boundary and the river reach parallel to the SPSZ at the southern boundary of the Shakh-dara Dome. The sections of the actual Panj river that are not locally equilibrated agree with zones of increased fluvial incision characterized by high VSR, where the Panj cuts

the Pamir domes. While the river section related to the modelled base level at the Darvaz Range deviated ~ 300 m above the equilibrated profile, the upstream reaches related to the Shiva-Bartang base level and to the one south of the Shakh dara Dome deviate up to ~ 400 m a.s.l. and $\sim 1,000$ m a.s.l.. We associate the increasingly convex zones and local base levels to successive river captures in response to active tectonics causing locally different base-level control across the major tectonic structures in Pamir. It remains unclear whether the Cenozoic domes forming the bulk of the Pamir are still active or probably reactivated by recent deformation along DFZ parallel faults.

Acknowledgments

We thank the DFG for funding our research associated with the TIPAGE project (Gl361/4-1) and we also want to thank the Academy of Science of Tajikistan for supporting our fieldworks. We used GMT (Wessel, P. and W. H. F. Smith, New, improved version of the Generic Mapping Tools released, EOS Trans. AGU, 79, 579, 1998) QGIS (<http://qgis.org/>) and the R environment (<http://www.r-project.org/>) for most of the geomorphological processings and the resulting figures.

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2.3 Factors controlling the Panj river network

The geomorphometric analyses of the Panj river network highlight a first order control from structural features. Whether active or not, the main tectonic structures of faults, sutures and domes induce the predominantly east-west orientation of mountain ranges that guide the rivers. Wide intra-plateau valleys define a relatively constant local base level at ~ 3600 m a.s.l., Declining altitudes of high variations confine the plateau at its margins. Deep incised valleys display the drop of local base levels in response to the regional base level in the Tajik depression. The higher altitude differences at the Pamir margins coincide with pronounced moisture supply from the Westerlies, but also from the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM, TRMM3B42 data, Huffman et al. 1997, 2007). Particularly the distribution of permanent snow and ice (MODIS, Strahler et al., 1999) illustrate orographic precipitation at the western and southern margins. But the increase of precipitation with altitude becomes de-coupled in the rain shadow towards the eastern plateau where permanent ice and snow is restricted to the highest mountain peaks.

Remnants of glacial moraines attest for periods of more extensive glaciations. The most extensive glacial advances dated to ~ 100 kyr reached the inner-plateau valley floors (Zech et al., 2005; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). Less extensive younger glaciations suggest that glacial processes dominated the topographic evolution of the plateau during certain periods in the past, but ceased in importance since MIS 4. The water storage in form of ice further triggers higher discharge during deglaciation periods. Effects on the fluvial dynamic and sediment transport are also likely at the Pamir margins, but glacial sediments still remain at the plateau. The wide, inner-plateau valleys are filled with sediments and fluvial activity is not yet fully established. Both suggest a reduced connectivity of sediment transport across the plateau margins.

River reaches draining the Pamir Plateau follow the pre-dominant westward flow orientation parallel to dome boundaries. Their relatively graded profiles indicate local base levels at the western Pamir margin, and suggest long-term persistence of valley locations. The Panj connects the westward reaches by northward oriented river segments cutting across the Shakh dara and Yazgulom Domes.

The longitudinal profile of the Panj illustrates the composite character of the trunk river by major convex zones that separate graded reaches. The major deviations in the river profile are not explained by changes in rock resistivity or changes in catchment size, and also climatic factors are not plausible for such localized changes in riverbed slope and valley steepness. Instead, the convex zones in the river profile coincide with the location of Pamir domes and are explained by river captures. The upstream increasing convexity compared to modeled graded profiles suggests successive river captures. The role of tectonic-driven relative base level lowering on triggering the river captures remains unknown as the activity of dome bounding faults is debated.

Chapter 2: References

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3 Luminescence dating analyses in high mountains

3.1 Methodological challenges

Luminescence dating methods have great potential to resolve the timing of sedimentation which motivated geoscientists to investigate their applicability to an increasing range of depositional settings. Furthermore, the temporal decoding of sedimentation has important implications on how fast surface processes act and how they evolve over time. The high interest in such geochronological data increased the data quantity to be processed as well as the need to evaluate luminescence signals of sediments from a wide range of settings.

In high mountains, luminescence techniques encounter specific challenges related to the sediment and the transport process. Short transport distances from young source rocks affect the luminescence sensitivity of the chosen mineral. High fluvial discharge and steep slopes result in fast transport processes related to differential bleaching. Post-depositional sediment mixing may arise particularly in permafrost environments, for example, due to cryoturbation, creep processes or sub-surface drainage. There are two main requirements for accurate and precise luminescence dating analyses:

1. Large quantities of data need to be processed to evaluate luminescence signal properties
2. Luminescence techniques need to address effects arising from low signal intensities, differential bleaching and post-depositional sediment mixing

Data processing in luminescence dating

Investigations of luminescence signal properties and limits for dating led to the development of new measurement equipment and protocols. The increasing quantity and variety of luminescence data demands for transparent and flexible data processing routines. Luminescence data are commonly analyzed using software such as the *ANALYST* (Duller, 2007) as an appropriate analytical tool for standard measurement routines. However, further statistical analyses and individual requests on graphical output usually implies combining different software with open source solutions, programming scripts, or other means of calculation. This adds time consuming conversion of data between various formats to already extensive analytical steps. Additionally, experimental measurements and new protocols demand for a more flexible handling of measurement data and consecutive analytical steps.

This growing demand was the motivation to introduce the **R.Luminescence** package (Kreutzer et al., 2012; Dietze et al., 2013) for the open source programming environment **R** for statistical computing (R Core Team). The **R** environment allows a flexible and transparent data handling from data input to age modeling. Functions provided by the **R.Luminescence** package may be combined with other **R** generic functions or packages provided through the CRAN website

(<http://cran.r-project.org/>), all within one computational language. The access to the source code of all analytical steps allows to adjust and develop new routines due to the measurement design, analytical procedures and desired output.

The progressive integration of new functions and the feedback of package users greatly enriched the **R.Luminescence** package and led to a series of version updates distributed via the CRAN mirror (<http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Luminescence/index.html>). Additionally, the **R.Luminescence** developer team provides support to the user community by various tutorials and a user forum available at the package homepage (<http://www.r-luminescence.de/>). However, as users may not be familiar with the **R** programming environment, the developer team was asked for examples of **R** code that illustrate the use of functions provided by the package. This encouraged the **R.Luminescence** developer team to present a data processing routine including three **R** code templates that may be used and adopted according to the needs of package users. The presented data processing routines (chapter 3.2) outline the basic procedures used for luminescence analyses in studies bundled in this thesis (see chapter 3.3 and 4.2).

- **Paper II (chapter 3.2)**

Fuchs, M.C., Kreutzer, S., Burow, C., Dietze, M., Fischer, M., Schmidt, C., Fuchs, M. (accepted): Data processing in luminescence dating analysis: an exemplary workflow using the R package 'Luminescence'. *Quaternary International*, doi: 10.1016/j.quaint.2014.06.034.

- **Supplementary material (Appendix A)**

R templates illustrating the use of the **R.Luminescence** package
List including all functions available with the **R.Luminescence** package
Supplementary data sets

Sediment-related luminescence characteristics

The material transport processes encountered in high mountains demand for luminescence techniques adequate for differentially bleached and/or mixed sediments. This regards the selection of the mineral and aliquot size for measurement as well as the statistical age modeling. Using quartz for luminescence measurements has the advantage of a higher sensitivity to optical bleaching compared to feldspars (e.g., Wallinga, 2002). But quartz from high mountain material tends to show low luminescence sensitivity (e.g., Preusser et al., 2006) which is assumed to relate to few transport-sedimentation-cycles and young source rock of sediments (e.g., Pietsch et al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012). The resulting weak signals challenge the reduction of aliquot size recommended to address differential bleaching and sediment mixing (e.g., Duller, 2008). Feldspars show generally brighter signals, but a less stable storage can cause an anomalous fading of the signal (Wintle, 1973; Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). Furthermore, feldspars derive their signal additionally from internal ^{40}K , of variable often not individually measured concentration (e.g., Huntley and Baril, 1997; Barre and Lamothe, 2010).

The material from rock glaciers is used in Paper III (chapter 3.3) as an example of the potential of luminescence techniques for age investigations in high mountains. Such permafrost-related sediments represent extreme conditions regarding the basic assumptions for the application of luminescence techniques. Sediment grains are prone to insufficient bleaching, sediment

mixing and microdosimetric variations not at least due to highly variable ice content (e.g., Bateman, 2008; Fuchs and Owen, 2008).

The reliability of luminescence signals is tested for OSL measurements of quartz and IRSL measurement of K-feldspar and plagioclase applied to multiple grain and single grain aliquots. Statistical data analyses addresses potential effects of differential bleaching and sediment mixing on dose distributions from different sources of grain input and grain transport within the creeping permafrost of rock glaciers. The expected complex dose distributions require age estimation based on adequate statistical models. Therefore, the most commonly applied age models - the minimum age model (MAM, Galbraith et al. 1999) and the finite mixture model (FMM, Galbraith and Green 1990) - are tested. Their performance is further investigated regarding the influence of overdispersion, the essential input parameter of both age models.

- **Paper III (Chapter 3.3)**

Fuchs, M.C., Böhlert, R., Krbetschek, M., Preusser, F., Egli, M. (2013): Exploring the potential of luminescence methods for dating Alpine rock glaciers. *Quaternary Geochronology* 18, 17–33, doi: 10.1016/j.quageo.2013.07.001.

- **Supplementary material (Appendix B)**

Plots and tables showing the influence of overdispersion between 0.05 and 0.5 on age model results

Table of measurement protocols

Supplementary material available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2013.07.001>.

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3.2 Paper II: Data processing in luminescence dating analysis: an exemplary workflow using the R package 'Luminescence'

Data processing in luminescence dating analysis: an exemplary workflow using the **R** package ‘Luminescence’

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Abstract

The first version of the **R** package ‘Luminescence’ was released and published in 2012. Since then, the package has been continuously improved - by implementing further measurement protocols, adding age models, and extending functions. In geoscientific applications, luminescence dating requires a series of data processing procedures. A comprehensive and replicate analysis of luminescence data using the **R** package ‘Luminescence’, therefore, suggests combining selected functions. With this contribution, we provide a practical example of a workflow from reading measurement data to age modelling. The exemplary data processing routine is applied to an OSL data set of a fluvial sediment sample from the Pamir Mountains.

Keywords: CRAN, data processing, OSL, Pamir, R templates

1. Introduction

The **R** package ‘Luminescence’ (Kreutzer et al., 2012) provides a bundle of functions for the analysis of luminescence signals and related data. The feedback from package users encouraged the developer team to revise, upgrade and add functions, and to release supportive material such as a practical guide for its use (Dietze et al., 2013) and various tutorials, available at the **R** Luminescence website (<http://www.r-luminescence.de>). The current package (version 0.3.3) equips the user with a flexible tool for various data processing steps, such as reading measurement data, fitting growth curves, calculating equivalent doses, inferring dose distribution statistics and applying age models. The open source code guarantees full access to all calculations. One may adapt functions according to individual requirements, taking advantage of the **R** programming environment (R Core Team, 2014) and any packages available through the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN, <http://cran.r-project.org/>).

In luminescence dating, a convenient workflow demands a series of data processing steps to be reproduced for several samples. This suggests the use of **R** code templates that define how data are passed through selected functions and how the output is processed. Nevertheless, the application of luminescence methods to a broad range of

sediments affects various methodological aspects. Consequently, the selection of adequate analytical steps requires adjustment and may be far beyond routine procedures.

Here, we can neither discuss the full range of data processing needs nor provide a standard decision procedure for luminescence data analysis. We rather introduce one example of how the **R** package ‘Luminescence’ can be used. For illustration, we apply selected functions to an optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) data set of fluvial sediments from the Panj river network in Pamir. We focus on a typical workflow from loading the measurement data into the **R** environment to statistical age modelling without any age interpretation. The described workflow (Fig. 1) introduces one of many possible routines to encourage the wider geosciences community to use, adapt or combine the available functions and to contribute to the **R** package development.

R code snippets are typed in monospaced letters throughout the manuscript. For data processing, the **R** user interface RStudio (<http://www.rstudio.com>) is used. The described workflow may require adaptation for previous (<0.3.3) package versions. Details on sample data processing are given in three **R** code templates (supplementary data).

2. Sample material and OSL measurement

A practical example to illustrate one possible workflow for OSL dating analyses is a data set derived from a fluvial sediment sample (TA110817N9-10) from the Panj

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Figure 1: Flow chart of exemplary data processing in luminescence dating analysis. Exemplary variable and data names are chosen for straightforward comprehension of the content. The flow chart comprises three major steps (light grey boxes): data input and analyses of measured signal, dose distribution analyses, age modelling. Arrows indicate the flow of variables as modified by R-functions (within/between light grey boxes) or data input and output options (in/out of light grey boxes). R code snippets are typed in monospaced letters

River, situated in the Pamir mountains. The regional geology, climate and the geomorphometry of the drainage system is described in Fuchs et al. (2013). The site is part of a complex terrace system along the Murgab River at the eastern Pamir Plateau (N 38.155 012°, E 73.968 168°, 3,599 m a.s.l.). The sampled sediment consists of well-sorted, layered sand 23 m below the terrace surface. The measurements to determine the equivalent dose (D_e) for OSL dating were conducted on the coarse-grained quartz fraction (90–160 μm), using a single aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol after Murray and Wintle (2000). Based on multiple grain SAR measurements, 20 medium size (4 mm) aliquots were measured. The SAR cycles were first applied to measure the natural signal, followed by six regeneration cycles (R1 to R6), including one to measure the recuperation (R5) and one to measure the recycling ratio (R6). Finally, an infrared stimulation cycle was performed using the same dose as for R1. Alongside the 20 aliquots measured for D_e determination, four additional aliquots (position 21–24) were measured to record signals from a dose recovery test (Murray and Wintle, 2003). All measurements were conducted using a standard Risø DA-20 TL/OSL reader ($^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source ~ 5.6 Gy/min, CW-OSL, blue LEDs at 470 nm and 90% optical power, 7.5 mm U340 Hoya filter, Bøtter-Jensen et al., 2000; Thomsen et al., 2006), which stores the measurement data in the .BIN file (version 03) format.

3. Data processing steps

The **R** package ‘Luminescence’ offers various functions to process the measurement data, such as any equivalent dose data stored in a .BIN or .BINX file (see supplementary data for a complete list of available functions). The recommended workflow includes three main analytical steps: (1) reading and analysing the measurement data, (2) analysing and plotting the dose distribution data, and (3) applying the age models. Figure 1 illustrates the workflow, including how the data can be handled with selected analytical functions, how variables can be used, and which plots can be generated.

3.1. Read and analyse measurement data

In order to analyse the OSL signal properties of the Pamir sample, the measurement data was first loaded into **R**. The presented example data is stored in a .BIN file. Other file formats such as .BINX are also fully supported. The data was imported by `readBIN2R()` and stored in a variable, here called `BINfile` (Fig. 1). The details on the measured sequence are available through `metadata` by selecting the desired rows and columns of the slot. Luminescence signal data is available through the `DATA` slot of the `BINfile` variable.

```
> BINfile <- readBIN2R(<your data>)
> BINfile@METADATA[1:30, c(2, 7, 8, 9, 22, 31, 45)]
> BINfile@DATA
```

For this data set, aliquot positions 1 to 20 were chosen to investigate the OSL signal properties, while positions 21 to 24 were bleached and dosed before applying the SAR protocol. The function `plot_Risoe.BINfileData()` plots OSL curve data for each stimulation run of the SAR protocol for all selected positions. The output can be returned to the screen or saved to the working directory using **R** internal functions such as `pdf()`.

```
> BINfile@METADATA$POSITION
> aliquot.position <- 1:20
> plot_Risoe.BINfileData(BINfileData = BINfile,
  position = aliquot.position,
  sorter = "POSITION",
  ltype = "OSL")
```

Background and sensitivity corrected initial signals of each OSL curve were calculated and grouped according to position by `Analyse_SAR.OSLdata()`. The integrals for the initial signal and for the background were set to 1–5 (1 s) and 200–250 (10 s), respectively. Given values represent examples and may be modified due to the individual requirements of analysed data. A variable named `SAR` was introduced that contains the results of integral calculations for each regeneration cycle (R1–R6) in the component `$LnLxTnTx` (Fig. 1). Additionally, the function returns recycling ratio estimates (R6 / R2), recuperation values (R5 / natural signal) in `$RejectionCriteria`, and SAR parameters.

```
> SAR <- Analyse_SAR.OSLdata(input.data = BINfile,
  signal.integral = <min> : <max>,
  background.integral = <min> : <max>,
  position = aliquot.position)
> SAR$LnLxTnTx
> SAR$RejectionCriteria
> SAR$SAR
```

The dose response curve and the D_e of the natural signal were determined by fitting exponential curves to the SAR signals (L_x/T_x values) of each aliquot. This was performed by the function `plot_GrowthCurve()`, which requires a data frame of three columns containing regeneration doses, corrected OSL signals, and signal errors. Therefore, the respective data of the selected aliquot position `i` was passed from `SAR$LnLxTnTx` to a new data frame, here named `LxTx.data`.

```
> select.aliquot <- i
> LxTx.data <- as.data.frame(cbind(SAR[[1]]
  [[select.aliquot]][c(2, 12, 13, 6)]))
```

The variable `LxTx.data` was then used to run the `plot_GrowthCurve()` function. The `output.plot` parameter enables printing of results, for example as a .pdf file. Results from the `plot_GrowthCurve()` function were returned as an “S4 object”, here named `growthcurve` (Fig. 1). Estimated D_e and curve fitting parameters were addressed

through the data slot using the function `get_RLum.Results()` and selecting, for example, the data object "De". Results may be stored in an empty `data.frame()` of a certain number of columns and filled with missing values (NA).

```
> pdf()
> growthcurve <- plot_GrowthCurve(sample = LxTx.data,
  output.plot = TRUE)
> dev.off()
> get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")
> De.data <- data.frame(De = NA, De.error = NA)
> De <- get_RLum.Results(growth.curve,
  data.object = "De")
> De.data[,1] <- De[1]
> De.data[,2] <- De[2]
```

A two column data frame of equivalent doses and related errors is required for further dose distribution statistics and age models of the **R** package 'Luminescence'. An effective way to analyse all selected aliquot positions from measured signal to D_e estimate is provided by the loop `for()` as illustrated in Fig. 1. The loop repeats signal extraction from individual SAR cycle measurements including growth curve estimation for the aliquot positions 1 to 20, and passes all D_e and respective error to a data frame termed *De.data* (for a detailed example see also the **R** template 1 in the supplementary material).

The reliability of the D_e calculation can be assessed using, for example, the recycling ratio and recuperation values returned by `Analyse_SAR.OSLdata()`. Respective data was stored in the slot `Rejection.Criteria` of the variable *SAR*. Recycling ratio and recuperation of 10% and 5%, respectively, were included to illustrate D_e selection for the Pamir sample. Template 1 (supplementary material) includes an example of how to implement rejection criteria and change thresholds as needed. The data in the variable *SAR* or *growthcurve* may be adopted to derive further rejection criteria (e.g., signal to background ratio, D_e error) depending on the user's research focus or requirements.

The *De.data* values of the Pamir sample were given in seconds as irradiation times were given in seconds. To convert the data to the unit Gray (Gy) the package provides the function `Second2Gray()`. It requires the D_e data and the dose rate of the β -source along with its error. In case the dose rate of the β -source at the date of measurement is unknown, the **R** template 1 (supplementary material) shows an example of the calculation based on the last β -source calibration and the date of measurement. The variable *De.data* can be saved as a `.txt` file for further usage.

```
> De.data <- Second2Gray(De.data, c(
  <dose.rate>, <dose.rate.error>))
> write.table(De.data, file = "<name>.txt")
```

3.2. Analyse and plot dose distribution data

The fluvial origin of the Pamir sample demands for statistical analysis of replicated equivalent dose measurements to determine the degree of bleaching and the most likely paleodose (e.g., Galbraith et al., 1999; Bailey and Arnold, 2006; Duller, 2008). Basically, the **R** package 'Luminescence' offers three functions for dose distribution visualisation: `plot_KDE()`, `plot_RadialPlot()` and `plot_Histogram()`. Any two-column data can be used as input data: the *De.data* from previous analyses or any other data frame loaded into the **R** environment. The input data may require several preparation steps (see **R** template 2 in the supplementary material). This includes selecting the correct data columns with the equivalent doses and errors, removing missing values for aliquot positions which yielded no equivalent dose, and sorting values in ascending order. Although not essential for the plot functions, it is convenient to sort the data for later use with age models (see below and **R** template 3 in the supplementary material). Finally, the variable *De.data* is converted to a data frame.

```
> De.data <- read.table("<name>.txt")
> De.data <- De.data[,1:2]
> De.data <- na.omit(De.data)
> De.data <- De.data[order(De.data[,1],
  decreasing = FALSE),]
> De.data <- as.data.frame(De.data)
```

The dose distribution of the Pamir sample was plotted by `plot_KDE()`. The function illustrates the variability of D_e by kernel density estimates (KDE). Basic statistic measures were added to the plot by the parameters `centrality` for vertical lines indicating the position of central measures within the distribution, and `stats` for numerical output of descriptive statistics (Fig. 1). The plot output is again saved as a separate `.pdf` file (see **R** template 2 in the supplementary material).

```
> pdf()
> plot_KDE(De.data,
  centrality = c("kdemax", "median"),
  stats = c("n", "mean", "seabs", "sdrel",
  "skewness"))
> dev.off()
```

The Pamir example data showed a positively skewed distribution (skewness of 1.13) with the mean higher than the median and the maximum density of D_e values. The high standard deviation of $\sim 47\%$ supports the indication of differential bleaching (e.g., Bailey and Arnold, 2006; Arnold et al., 2007). Consequently, the paleodose calculation is based on further age modelling to extract the well-bleached portion of all D_e .

3.3 Paper III: Exploring the potential of luminescence methods for dating Alpine rock glaciers

Exploring the potential of luminescence methods for dating Alpine rock glaciers

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Rock glaciers contain valuable information about the spatial and temporal distribution of permafrost. The wide distribution of these landforms in high mountains promotes them as useful archives for the deciphering of the environmental conditions during their formation and evolution. However, age constraints are needed to unravel the palaeoclimatic context of rock glaciers, but numerical dating is difficult. Here, we present a case study assessing the potential of luminescence techniques (OSL, IRSL) to date the inner sand-rich layer of active rock glaciers. We focus on the signal properties and the resetting of the signal prior to deposition by investigating single grains. While most quartz shows low signal intensities and problematic luminescence characteristics, K-feldspar exhibits much brighter and well-performing signals. Most signals from plagioclases do not show suitable properties. Luminescence signals far below saturation indicate distinct but differential bleaching. The finite mixture model was used to determine the prominent populations in the equivalent dose distributions. The luminescence ages represent travel times of grains since incorporation into the rock glacier and hence, minimum ages of rock glacier formation. Luminescence ages between 3 kyr and 8 kyr for three rock glaciers from the Upper Engadine and Albula region (Swiss Alps) agree well with independent age estimates from relative and semi-quantitative approaches. Therefore, luminescence seems to have the potential of revealing age constraints about processes related to the formation of rock glaciers, but further investigations are required for solving some of the problems remaining and reducing the dating uncertainties.

Keywords: Rock glacier, Luminescence dating, OSL, IRSL, Single grains, Alps

1. Introduction

In order to set modern climate-related observations into long-term perspectives, environmental proxies recorded in various natural archives are needed to reconstruct past climate and landscape evolution. In mountain areas, highly climate sensitive glacial and periglacial processes are the main agents modulating the Earth's surface. These regions are also of special interest because within short horizontal distances they host climatic regimes similar to those of widely separated latitudinal belts (Beniston et al., 1997; Beniston, 2005). The resulting sensitivity to changes in environmental conditions constitutes mountain areas to be among the key regions for observing, reconstructing, and finally predicting climate change and its impact on surface processes.

Extensive areas of high mountain regions are governed by permafrost conditions with rock glaciers marking the lower boundary of its distribution (Haeberli et al., 2011).

Rock glaciers comprise perennially frozen and ice-rich debris on non-glaciated mountain slopes that creep steadily under the influence of gravity (e.g. Haeberli et al., 2006). Active rock glaciers of the Alps (i.e. containing ice and actively deforming) are assumed to have formed and evolved during the Holocene (Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Relict forms at lower altitudes have lost their ice content and do not creep anymore. As they initially must have formed under permafrost conditions, they have a considerable potential for constraining past climatic conditions (Ballantyne et al., 2009). However, the deciphering of rock glaciers as geo-archives requires a temporal assignment by means of numerical dating.

Haeberli et al. (2003) suggest a concept of combined relative and (semi)quantitative techniques for rock glacier dating. Photogrammetric measurements of surface flow fields, weathering rinds, Schmidt-hammer rebound, and lichenometry indicate increasing surface ages towards the front. Extrapolation of present day velocities may indicate surface ages of 5 - 6 ka (Kääb et al., 1998) or 3 - 5 ka (Frauenfelder et al., 2005), but with uncertainties related to possible changes in palaeo-velocities or even phases of flow inactivity. Although the relative and semi-quantitative approaches confirm the concept of rock glaciers

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developing at millennial time scales, spatial variations in flow velocities indicate various site-specific effects (e.g., local slopes, ground temperature, rock types). This emphasizes that the interpretation of relative age constraints and their comparison between study sites requires calibration based on numerical dating. Radiocarbon dating of the only organic remnants encountered during drilling at the Murtl rock glacier yielded a ^{14}C age of (2.3 ± 0.1) ka BP (Haeberli et al., 2003). From the rock glaciers Murtl, Muragl and La Veduta (Upper Engadine, Switzerland) preliminary results indicate problematic luminescence properties due to low signal intensities in quartz (90 - 200 μm fraction). Although no detailed datasets are presented, Haeberli et al. (2003) state that all datable samples give ages between about 4 ka and 8 ka. Böhlert et al. (2011b,c) suggest two different permafrost activity phases since the Lateglacial: one phase after the ice retreat following the Younger Dryas and the other in the Holocene. Based on cosmogenic nuclide dating and weathering rinds in the French Alps, Cosart et al. (2010) distinguished three main generations of rock glaciers since the Lateglacial: the first one around 11 ka or 12 ka, the second around 2 ka or 3 ka, and the last one in more recent times.

Over the last decades, advances in optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) techniques broadened the field of applications in sediment dating (e.g., Lian and Roberts, 2006; Bateman, 2008; Fuchs and Owen, 2008). The main advantages are that these methods directly date the material's last light exposure associated to the timing of deposition, and that they use almost ubiquitously present quartz (OSL) and feldspar (IRSL) for dating. Concerning the dating of rock glaciers, luminescence techniques are not reliant on organic material necessary for radiocarbon dating, and are independent of stable surfaces as required for cosmogenic nuclide dating. However, the OSL properties of quartz, the mineral chosen in most applications, are often problematic in mountainous areas (e.g., ?). This is apparently related to the fact that OSL signals suitable for dating result from sensitisation during repeated sediment transport/deposition cycles (Pietsch et al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012), but with the exact physical processes in the crystal lattice being poorly understood (cf. Preusser et al. 2009). This problem is not known to apply for feldspars, but the signal of this mineral can be less stable, and such fading of the signal can cause underestimation of the determined age (Wintle, 1973). Furthermore, the IRSL signal from feldspar is expected to bleach more slowly than the OSL from quartz (e.g., Wallinga, 2002b).

In the context of glacial and periglacial environments and their related transport processes, it has to be considered that insufficient light exposure may not completely bleach the pre-existing luminescence signals (e.g., Fuchs and Owen, 2008). Such incomplete bleaching causes residuals that form part of the measured signal and, if not detected and excluded, lead to an overestimation of the palaeodose and, accordingly, of the calculated age. How-

ever, it has been shown that poorly bleached sediments are usually composed of grains with different bleaching levels (Duller, 1994). It is possible to detect differential bleaching when measuring the signal of small aliquots or single grains, where it is expressed by the spread of replicate measurements (e.g., Wallinga, 2002a; Duller, 2008). Statistical approaches are then applied to extract the true burial dose (e.g. Galbraith et al., 1999; Bailey and Arnold, 2006). To ensure a correct extraction of the well-bleached signal portion, such approaches have to account for sample specific parameters that have an effect on the expected spread of data without differential bleaching (e.g., instrumental error, material-inherent variability, microdosimetry).

In this study, we investigate the potential of both, quartz OSL and feldspar IRSL (K-feldspar, plagioclase) focussing on single grain measurements to date three active rock glaciers in the Piz Julier area and in the Val Tschitta, Swiss Alps (Fig. 1). For the Gianda Grischa and the Suvretta rock glacier age estimates are available from streamline interpolations and relative dating measurements (Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Due to the relatively simple geometry and the availability of relative age estimates, the Salteras rock glacier was chosen as an additional site. Firstly, we describe rock glacier sedimentary dynamics and discuss the relevance of processes involved in grain input and transport within rock glaciers for the interpretation of luminescence ages. Secondly, we present the luminescence signals of quartz OSL and feldspar IRSL measurements and statistically analyze the dose distributions for prominent populations. Finally, we discuss the derived grain travel times in the context of the process related assumptions and accordingly the potential of luminescence techniques to constrain the age of rock glacier formation.

2. Methodological aspects of rock glacier dating

2.1. Formation and dynamic of rock glaciers

According to Barsch (1996) three main aspects define active rock glaciers: the form of a lobate or tongue-shaped body, the perennially frozen unconsolidated material supersaturated with interstitial ice and ice lenses, and the process of down-slope creep as a consequence of deforming ice contained in them (cohesive flow). Berthling (2011) emphasizes the cumulative deformation by long-term creep of ice/debris mixtures under permafrost conditions. All rock glaciers studied in this work formed in crystalline areas and can be described as 'bouldery rock glaciers' with mean boulder diameters of 15 - 20 cm (Böhlert, 2010), following the classification scheme of Matsuoka et al. (2005). They are furthermore classified as valley floor/tongue shaped rock glaciers according to Humlum (1982) and Hamilton and Walley (1995).

Rock glaciers form when the ice content of perennially frozen debris or talus on slopes exceeds saturation, and the body of debris and ice starts deforming slowly

Figure 1: Regional setting of the study area.

(creeps) under gravitational stress (Haeberli et al., 2006). Such creeping, ice-rich rock glacier bodies develop at slopes where a concave area favors the accumulation of material from adjacent steep bedrock walls (Fig. 2). The processes leading to material and ice accumulation are numerous, and complex interactions with glaciers are possible (Haeberli et al., 2006), sometimes making a clear identification of the landform challenging (Böhlert, 2010; Berthling, 2011). For instance, the source material can be provided by ice-cored moraines ('moraine-derived' rock glaciers) or by debris flows and solifluction. Separation processes result in the typical sorting of grain sizes, represented by boulder enrichment in the top and bottom layer whereas the fine-grained material concentrates in the inner part. The upper, normally boulder-enriched part represents a highly heterogeneous layer that is strongly influenced by the thickness and temporal distribution of the snow cover (Haeberli et al., 2006). Characteristic active layer thicknesses range from a few centimeters to a few meters (Humlum, 1998). In the fine-grained (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) and often ice supersaturated material of the inner parts energy fluxes are mainly conduction-controlled. The creep of rock glaciers can be described by 'caterpillar-like' flow behaviour (Fig. 2): boulders at the surface fall down at

the over-steepened front and are subsequently overridden by ice-supersaturated, fine-grained material.

2.2. Sediment dynamics and relevance for luminescence dating

According to the model of rock glacier dynamics described above, the material available for dating derives either from the upper boulder-rich layer, principally suitable for cosmogenic nuclide dating, or from the inner fine-grained layer that has the potential to be dated by luminescence methods. The 'caterpillar-like' flow results in an age inversion of the boulder enriched layers: at the surface, the age of the blocky material increases towards the front, while for the overridden base-layer the opposite applies (Haeberli 1985; Fig. 2). Beside inaccessibility of the oldest boulders in the base layer, additional problems for numerical dating (i.e. cosmogenic nuclides) are related to the unstable exposure of boulder surfaces and possible inheritance of cosmogenic nuclides from previous exposure. The layer of fine-grained material at the front of active rock glaciers represents buried particles of the long-term creeping, perennially frozen talus (Haeberli et al. 2003, Fig. 3). Dating this inner, fine-grained layer will give the time when grains were incorporated into the rock glacier.

Figure 2: Idealised sequence of rock glacier development (after Haeberli et al. 1998).

As a consequence, luminescence ages of such layers will represent travel times, i.e. the time since the signal was reset during deposition on the rock glacier surface followed by shielding and signal growth as long as grains are transported within the rock glacier body.

In this context, two main processes need to be considered regarding their effects on the luminescence signal: (1) grain pathways into the rock glacier with corresponding characteristic bleaching history, and (2) grain transport within the rock glacier body affecting sediment mixing and signal growth. It is important to note that luminescence ages, due to the input paths of fine-grained material described above, will likely only represent the minimum age of the rock glacier. Only in the case of dominant material input and sufficient bleaching at the rock glacier's rooting zone, undisturbed signal growth during grain transport towards the front, and under the assumption that no fine-grained material is eroded at the front, the travel time might indicate the age of rock glacier formation.

Possible process-related effects on the luminescence signal are summarized in Table 1. The accurate determination of the travel time fundamentally relies on the level of signal resetting prior to grain incorporation, related to how the fine-grained material was supplied to and incorporated into the rock glacier. Different input pathways lead to distinct populations of grains with characteristic bleaching histories and potentially representing different times of incorporation. In principal, material available for rock glacier aggregation may be derived from headwall erosion of bedrock that surrounds the rooting zone, from aeolian sediment supply, from basal uptake or from internal

grain size reduction. The short transport distances from surrounding headwalls might cause incomplete bleaching, while prolonged surface retention times of grains due to, for example, perennial snowfields or avalanche residues as well as aeolian input will likely deliver well-bleached grains. Potential sources of incompletely bleached grains are basal uptake of material and internal, permafrost-related grain size reduction resulting from the shear stress of creeping, ice super-saturated sediment.

After incorporation into the rock glacier, luminescence signals are expected to reveal an age-distance relation with increasing signal towards the front of the rock glacier (Fig. 3), but sediment mixing might disturb this simple relation. Causes for vertical and lateral sediment mixing might be related to gravitational creeping permafrost and corresponding uncertainties in grain trajectories. Possible mechanisms of vertical sediment mixing involve melt-water that may transfer grains from the surface of the rock glacier into deeper parts. The input of material along crevasses (extension/compression zones) similarly promotes the vertical and lateral mixing of surface-derived grains with older sediment layers.

Apart from uncertainties due to the grain pathways, processes related to the gravitational creep of ice super-saturated material might cause variations in the efficiency of the dose rate and with regard to the shielding against cosmic radiation. Potential micro-dosimetric variations mainly relate to uncertainties in the water/ice content and especially in its distribution. Ice super-saturation, segregated ice or ice lenses can cause inhomogeneity in the distribution of radionuclides in the fine-grained matrix and

Figure 3: This example shows a talus-derived rock glacier below a rock wall. The top layer with coarse block approximates the active layer. The blue arrows represent idealised trajectories of single grains subsequently removed at the front for luminescence dating. The measured age theoretically is the time the grain needed to travel this distance within the rock glacier body, protected from daylight. A = rooting zone (grain incorporation); B = rock glacier lobe (grain transport); C = rock glacier front (sampling). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

may affect the actual dose rate of each individual grain.

Considering the possibility of both, different input-related bleaching histories and transport-related sediment mixing, we expect to measure luminescence signals that reveal different grain populations within the same sample. The determination of the travel time of grains from the mixed grain populations requires the correct detection and exclusion of signals from subsequently incorporated younger grains (age underestimation) and grains incompletely bleached prior to burial (age overestimation). The accurate and precise determination of the well-bleached grain population relies on reliable luminescence properties (e.g., dose-response relation, signal sensitivity and reproducibility) and at least some grains completely zeroed before incorporation into the rock glacier. Because the material loss at the rock glacier front is difficult to evaluate, the travel times based on the well-bleached grain population represent minimum ages of the rock glacier formation. To reduce the relative contribution of the external dose rates and related uncertainties to the total dose rate, we aim at comparing the results for three minerals with differing internal dose rates (quartz, K-feldspar, and plagioclase; cf. Barre and Lamothe 2010).

3. Study sites

The study sites are located in the eastern part of Switzerland (Upper Engadine). Greenish ‘Albula Granite’ comprised of quartz, plagioclase (in places altered to epidote), K-feldspar, biotite and rarely hornblende is the dominant rock type in the area (cf. Bearth et al. 1987). The reconstructed Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) ice surface geometry shows that the area was situated near the ‘Engadine

Table 1: Potential processes related to rock glaciers and their effects on the luminescence signals.

Process	Effect
<i>Deposition and incorporation:</i>	
Aeolian input onto rock glacier surface	Supply of well-bleached grains
Input from short distance transport (e.g. from mass movements)	Insufficient light exposure (incomplete bleaching)
Grain retention on rock glacier surface (e.g. due to snow cover)	Prolonged light exposure, well-bleached grains
Internal source of fine material (grain size reduction by permafrost)	No or insufficient light exposure (partial bleaching)
Basal material uptake (incorporation of older sediments)	No or insufficient light exposure (Incomplete bleaching)
<i>Transport:</i>	
Horizontal sediment mixing (e.g., by meltwater)	Mixing with younger grains
Vertical sediment mixing (e.g., crevasses)	Mixing with grains, e.g., derived from aeolian material supplied to the rock glacier surface
Trajectories of individual grains (grain transport at constant depth?)	Uncertainties related to shielding against light exposure as well as cosmic dose rate
Permafrost variability	Uncertainties in dose rate efficiency and paleo-water/ice content

ice dome’. Trimline and other erosional features indicate that during the LGM the Albulapass formed a northward transfluence with ice flowing from the Engadine into the Rhine river system (Florineth, 1998; Florineth and Schlichter, 2000; Bini et al., 2009). As a result of the highly unstable climate during the Lateglacial (c. 19 - 11.5 kyr) and the early Holocene, a variety of climate-related landforms developed in mountain areas of the Alps. A geomorphic map of the region describes the landforms and the different glacier stages after the LGM (Maisch, 1981). The glacier stages were numerically dated measuring in-situ produced ^{10}Be in boulders on moraines, polished bedrocks, and roches moutonnes (Ivy-Ochs et al., 1996; Böhlert et al., 2011b,c). Distinct glacier stages could be attributed to the Daun (Oldest Dryas) phase (14.9 - 1.8 kyr) and several Egesen phases (Younger Dryas). At high-elevation sites near the LGM trimline, ^{10}Be exposure ages of glacially modified bedrock are between 11.2 kyr and 13.5 kyr (Böhlert et al., 2011b). This suggests the persistence of long-lasting small local ice caps after the breakdown of the LGM ice domes or, alternatively, a reformation of ice perhaps during the Younger Dryas. Exposure ages from a glacially polished rock barrier showed that this area was ice-free at the end of the Younger Dryas ((9.0 ± 0.7) kyr and (11.9 ± 0.9) kyr; Böhlert et al. 2011b). In general, two different altitudinal levels of rock glaciers are recognized. A first generation (inactive rock glaciers) reaches altitudes down to 2000 - 2300 m a.s.l. A second generation (active rock glaciers) is usually above 2400 - 2700 m a.s.l. (depending on exposure). Surface exposure

Figure 4: The rock glaciers sampled for luminescence dating are shown. Sampling locations are represented by red dots. Samples are ideally taken between the coarse blocks on the surface and the eroded and accumulated material at the lower part of the slope. This zone at the rock glacier Gianda Grischa is especially clearly visible as a white band. Digging below big boulders provides a better slope stability and increases the possible penetration depth (lower right, rock glacier Suvretta). Neighbouring and associated (potentially) inactive and relict creeping forms are indicated by white lines. The dashed line on the rock glacier Gianda Grischa approximates the zone where an older part is overrun by a more active lobe. At this site, three main parts can be distinguished: (A) active rock glacier, (B) older, possibly relict part, (C) inactive rock glacier (based on Frauenfelder et al. 2008). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

dating (SED) of a roches moutonnes using ^{10}Be , ^{14}C dating of a peat bog, palynological investigations as well as glaciomorphologic mapping (Maisch, 1981) delimited the maximum age of the Lateglacial permafrost activity that apparently started shortly after the Younger Dryas (about 11.6 kyr; Böhlert et al. 2011a). Soil analyses support these time constraints for the second activity phase that hypothetically started sometime around 6 kyr ago and continues today (Böhlert et al., 2011a).

Three active rock glaciers were investigated (Fig. 1). Age constraints from relative and semi-quantitative methods, summarized in Frauenfelder et al. (2005), enable to set the here-measured luminescence ages into context. Age estimations mainly based on streamline interpolations were the reason for the choice of the Gianda Grischa and the Suvretta rock glacier. A comparably simple geometry in combination with a dataset from relative dating approaches

was the reason for the choice of the Salteras rock glacier as an additional site. The sampling sites on each rock glacier are shown in Figure 4.

3.1. Suvretta

The Suvretta rock glacier is characterised by a more than 1 km long, relatively thin monomorphic body creeping out of the cirque below the Piz Albana, in closest vicinity to Piz Julier (Fig. 1 and Fig. 4a). It covers an altitudinal range of about 500 m, with a starting zone at around 2800 m and a front position at 2300 m. The rock glacier front is undercut by the mountain stream coming down the Suvretta valley (Vonder Mühl, 1993). The thickness of the permafrost body ranges from almost 100 m in the upper part to around 20 m near the front, as determined by geoelectric techniques. Active layer thickness does usually not exceed 2 m (Vonder Mühl, 1993). The

length profile is S-shaped: The slightly dipping root zone changes at 2600 m to a steep zone of extending flow in the middle part, flattening again towards the valley bottom with a zone of compressing flow in the tongue area. The area around the rock glacier was most probably not influenced by extensive ice during the end of the Lateglacial and the Holocene (Suter, 1981; Ohlendorf, 1998). The corresponding sheet from the Siegfried map (sheet St. Moritz, 1875) does not indicate that the cirque was occupied by ice masses during the Little Ice Age (LIA). However, the presence of (perennial) ice or snow patches cannot be ruled out.

Photogrammetric techniques determined horizontal surface displacement rates of up to 2 m a^{-1} and a surface age at the front of approximately 3 kyr (Kääb et al., 1997, 1998; Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Reconstructed streamlines represent the trajectories of individual particles on the surface. Considering that the overall advance rate of the rock glacier can be much smaller, the calculated ages have to be interpreted as minimum ages. The maximum age (travel time) can be 2 - 5 times higher (Kääb, 2005). Both Schmidt-hammer rebound values 'r' (Castelli, 2000) and weathering rind thicknesses (Laustela et al., 2003) show a clear trend following the length profile and, in combination with the estimated ages from photogrammetry, allows for calibration. The oldest parts near the tongue yielded weathering rind thicknesses between 2.5 mm and 3 mm and r-values ranging around 35, respectively (Frauenfelder et al., 2005). The values are typical for rock glaciers having a maximum surface age of several thousand years that suggest Holocene rock glacier formation (Böhlert et al., 2011a).

3.2. Gianda Grischia

The double-tongued Gianda Grischia rock glacier (Fig. 1 and Fig. 4b) on the western slopes of Piz Julier is, from a geometrical point of view, the most complex one. Multiple generations of lobes with different activity stages are distinguishable. Several situations show younger active parts overrunning older inactive or even relict parts. This is especially pronounced at the orographic left tongue. In order to reduce complexity, we chose the right tongue for sampling. The southern margin of the middle part of the rock glacier is steeply sloping down towards SW, in Figure 4b identifiable as a bright area clearly contrasting the more gently sloping surface of the rock glacier.

To the north of this active polymorphic rock glacier an inactive exemplar can be separated. Its location in a flat niche was occupied by a small glacier during the LIA, while the cirque of the active rock glacier was ice-free at this time (Coaz 1850; Siegfried map, sheet St. Moritz, 1875). According to Suter (1981), well-pronounced Egesen-equivalent moraines near Julierpass indicate a glaciation during the Younger Dryas. Two-dimensional electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) surveys showed unusual high active layer thicknesses up to 4 - 5 m. Typical values in this region are

3 - 3.5 m on rock glaciers and 4 - 5 m in rock walls. Photogrammetry yields lower surface displacement rates compared to the rock glacier Suvretta, with an average velocity of $0.4 - 0.5 \text{ m a}^{-1}$ and maximum values around 0.8 m a^{-1} . The minimum estimated surface age is 4 - 5 kyr (Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Schmidt-hammer measurements show no clear trend. This may be a result of boulders being rearranged under the influence of gravity in the steep part of the rock glacier, causing a reset of the 'clock' (Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Weathering rinds, however, show a development with increasing thicknesses towards the front, at least on the orographic left side (Laustela, 2003). Maximum values (median, mode) are in the range of 1.5 mm to 2 mm. This trend is not as clear on the orographic right side, but the measured values are in the same range, indicating a similar age structure on both sides. Related to the age estimation, rind growth rates are about half as high as in the case of the rock glacier Suvretta, although made up of the same source material (Frauenfelder et al., 2005).

3.3. Salteras

The Salteras rock glacier, originating from the NE-oriented cirque to the east of Piz Salteras, shows a rather simple geometry without zones of pronounced compressing or extending flow. The long profile is slightly convex with an increasing slope angle towards the tongue, which is about to creep over a steep grassy slope. The front is thereby divided into two individual lobes. In front of the talus apron, several vegetation covered lobe-shaped forms are visible (Fig. 4c). These might be interpreted as remnants (ridges in a compressing zone or front?) of a collapsed relict form, indicating that the rock glacier Salteras has experienced several activity phases. Lacking lichen coverage and weakly consolidated coarse blocks covering the surface suggest an active stage of the rock glacier.

Neither Schmidt-hammer r-values nor modal values of weathering rind thicknesses - both measured in the middle and the lower part of the rock glacier (Laustela, 2003) - show a clear trend representing an increasing exposure time to weathering processes towards the front. The high r-values (45 - 50) agree with the very thin and often completely absent weathering rinds. Using the median, there is a trend indeed; still, the values are very small (<1 mm). This picture of surprisingly fresh and unweathered surface material might be explained by the influence of glacier ice that might have removed the more weathered rocks at the surface. Although the Siegfried map (sheet Savognin, 1887) shows no ice in this position, moraines found in the upper part support the conclusion that at least the upper parts of the rock glacier have been covered by surface ice during the LIA (Maisch, 1981).

4. Methods

4.1. Sampling

Rock glaciers were sampled at the talus apron at the front (Fig. 4). To avoid the influence of superficially eroded and reworked material, we chose sampling spots in the upper third of the slope, clearly higher than the visible debris accumulation zones in the lower parts, but below the coarse blocks at the surface. The approximately 40° steep slopes showed a low stability. Digging was carried out whenever possible underneath isolated boulders that protected the sandy matrix to a certain degree from collapsing immediately. Keeping a minimum distance of 40 cm from the boulder itself, approximately 50 -100 cm of the surface material was removed until fresh sediment was reached. During sampling, an opaque cover served for shielding the sediment from daylight. Horizontal sediment cores were recovered in opaque plastic cylinders and properly sealed for transportation and storage. The surrounding sediment was sampled for gamma-spectrometric analyses of the sediments radionuclide content.

4.2. Determination of dose rate

The radionuclide content of the sediment was determined based on the specific activities of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and of ^{40}K and daughters by means of low level HPGe gamma-spectrometry. Radioactive disequilibria in the ^{238}U -series were evaluated by comparing the specific activities of subsequent radionuclides with focus on ^{222}Rn daughters to identify Rn-loss. The cosmic dose rate was estimated according to latitude, longitude, mean altitude (accounting for the altitude change during grain transport from the source to talus apron) and thickness of the debris coverage above sampling positions. The dose rate efficiency was corrected based on the mineral and sediment density, grain-size, etched layer, and by the assumed palaeowater content. The palaeowater content refers to the measured in situ content compared to saturation values. While the in situ values are attributed to conditions near the front during sampling season, the sample's water saturation provides a reference for previously higher water/ice contents required for the creep process of the rock glacier. Potential uncertainties arise from inhomogeneity in the sediment matrix and distribution of ice (e.g., ice lenses), although the creep process might average out corresponding dose rate variations between grains. To account for the expected high palaeowater content up to super-saturation (associated to actively creeping rock glaciers), the used palaeowater values was set to about two third of the saturation values. To cover possible variations in water content, high errors were included that range from in situ and exceed saturation values.

The parameters contributing to the total external dose rates of the three rock glaciers are given in Table 2. No significant disequilibria are indicated for ^{238}U due to the specific activities of the Rn daughters ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi . A lower activity of ^{210}Pb compared to the rest of the decay

chain was observed for samples GiG1 and 2, but the effect on age calculation is less than 1%. For the determination of the mineral-internal dose rate of K-feldspars, a potassium content of $(12.5 \pm 0.5)\%$ was assumed (Huntley and Baril, 1997) and for plagioclase $(2.0 \pm 0.8)\%$ (cf. Barre and Lamothe 2010). Investigations on samples from the Swiss lowland reveal very little variation in the internal K-content of K-feldspars (D. Gaar, pers. com.) Based on the measured specific activity of the sediment, the estimated cosmic component and correction parameters the overall environmental dose rate (and luminescence age) was calculated with the ADELE software (Kulig, 2005). The age and uncertainty calculation follows the principles described by Aitken (1985).

4.3. Sample preparation

In the laboratory, the samples were treated under attenuated red light. The two outermost centimeters of the sediment cores were removed on each side as these parts could have experienced light exposition during sampling. This material was used to determine the water content (in situ and saturation) of the sample. The material from the inner part of the cylinders was used for the separation of the quartz and the feldspar grains. Sieving isolated the 100 - 200 μm grain size fractions for multiple-grain aliquot and 200 - 300 μm for single grain measurements. The treatment with 10% HCl and 30% H_2O_2 removed carbonates and organic matter, respectively. To assure the separation of quartz, K-feldspar and plagioclase, we introduced a feldspar flotation before density separation. The feldspar flotation was carried out in a solution of 0.2% HF with pH 2.4 - 2.7 to activate feldspar adherence to bubbles that were induced by pumping air through a frit and the foam agent dodecylamine. Both, the enriched quartz and the feldspar froth, were washed in 5% HCl and then separated due to density with sodium polytungstate (quartz: 2.62 - 2.67 g cm^{-3} ; K-feldspar: <2.58 g cm^{-3} ; plagioclase: 2.58 - 2.62 g cm^{-3}). The quartz fraction was then etched using 40% HF for 60 min and the feldspar fraction using 10% HF for 40 min to remove ~10 mm of the outer, alpha-ray affected rim of the grains. The following cleaning with 37% HCl (quartz) and 10% HCl (feldspars) washed out the fluorite precipitates. Final sieving isolated the fractions 90 μm to 160 μm for multiple-grain aliquots and 200 - 250 μm for single grain analyses. The multiple-grain aliquots were prepared by fixing homogenized subsamples of the separated material on aluminum discs within a diameter of 4 mm using silicon oil. Such an aliquot will contain about 200 - 400 grains, of which a small amount will be luminescent (cf. Heer et al. 2012). For single grain measurements, discs with 100 holes arranged in a grid were used, each dimensioned to accommodate a single grain of the size 200 - 250 μm (Bøtter-Jensen et al., 2000).

4.4. OSL measurements of quartz

OSL multiple-grain aliquots measurements were carried out using a RisøTL/OSL reader DA 20 equipped with

Table 2: Data for dose rate estimation (SAL = Salteras; SUV = Suvretta; GiG = Gianda Grischa; D_{cos} = cosmic dose rate; I = in situ S = saturation; U = used for calculations).

Sample	Radionuclides			D_{cos} [mGy kyr ⁻¹]	Water content			External Dose rate [Gy kyr ⁻¹]
	²³⁸ U [Bq kyr ⁻¹]	²³² Th [Bq kyr ⁻¹]	⁴⁰ K [Bq kyr ⁻¹]		I [%]	S [%]	U [%]	
SAL1	28.5 ± 0.7	29.2 ± 1.4	911.1 ± 3.7	144	4.6	15.7	12 ± 8	3.5
SUV1	69.8 ± 1.4	45.6 ± 2.0	761.3 ± 2.9	190	2.5	9.0	10 ± 8	4.1
SUV2	74.7 ± 1.6	45.6 ± 2.1	774.5 ± 3.2	190	4.5	15.9	12 ± 8	4.2
SUV3	77.0 ± 6.0	45.5 ± 2.0	770.0 ± 50.0	171	4.4	16.6	12 ± 8	4.3
SUV4	77.0 ± 5.0	46.5 ± 2.0	750.0 ± 50.0	171	4.6	44.4	25 ± 20	3.8
GiG1+2	52.0 ± 4.0	36.5 ± 2.0	705.0 ± 40.0	250	3.4	18.0	12 ± 9	3.6

a Sr-90 beta irradiator (5.6 Gy min⁻¹). OSL emission was stimulated with blue LEDs (470 nm) for 50 s at 125 °C and detected through a U 340 Hoya optical filter. 20 aliquots of samples SAL1 and SUV2 were measured following the single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol (Murray and Wintle, 2000) for quartz. Subsequent to the natural signal, the aliquot-specific dose-luminescence relation was determined based on six regeneration cycles including monitoring of recuperation, recycling ratio, and sensitivity change. Preheat before each OSL stimulation was set to 260 °C and cutheat to 220 °C for 10 s (for details on measurement parameters, see Supplementary Material D). For sample SAL1, four additional dose recovery tests (Murray and Wintle, 2003) were applied to assess the reproducibility of OSL signals in reference to a known laboratory dose. This coefficient of variation (v_{DR}) determines the sample-specific variability of OSL signals inherited from the sample's material and the applied measurement conditions.

Additionally, single grain measurements were performed for samples SAL1, SUV1-4 and GiG1-2 to avoid the averaging effect of luminescence signals from multiple grain aliquots (e.g., Duller, 2008). Single grain measurements improve the distinction between different populations in the dose distribution and allow for assessing the degree of bleaching. Using a RisøTL/OSL Reader DA 15, luminescence emission was stimulated by a green laser (532 nm, ~50 W cm⁻²) for 2 s at 125 °C and detected through a Hoya U 340 filter. For each sample 2 - 4 discs were measured. For technical reasons, it was not possible to fill the discs (100 grains) completely. Grain counting under the microscope after the measurement confirmed the degree of filling per disc to be 70 % to 90 %. Equivalence doses were determined following the SAR protocol and parameters described above (for details see Supplementary Material D). Dose recovery tests were carried out only for SAL1.

4.5. IRSL measurements of feldspars

IRSL single grain measurements were carried out for K-feldspars (samples SAL1, SUV2-4, GiG1-2). Additionally, plagioclase was measured for SAL1 and SUV4 to test their applicability for dating with respect to the lowered potassium content and corresponding contribution to the internal dose (cf. Barre and Lamothe 2010). The RisøTL/OSL

DA 20 reader was equipped with an IR single grain stimulation unit and we used stimulation with an IR laser (830 nm, 150 mW) for 5 s at 30 °C.

Suitable conditions for luminescence emission and detection were evaluated for sample SAL1 by carrying out thermal transfer tests for different preheat temperatures (220, 240, 260 and 280 °C for 10 s) and by applying different detection filters (280, 410, 560 nm). The measurement procedure followed the SAR protocol of Murray and Wintle (2000), but by replacing measurement of the natural signal by measurement of a laboratory bleached (zero dose) sample. Thermal transfer is expressed by the equivalent dose determined by the SAR measurement (three aliquots for each pre-heat level). This procedure was repeated for each filter, which corresponds to the three typical IRSL emission wavebands of feldspars with different properties (Krbetschek et al., 1997). According to the results from the thermal transfer tests (Fig. 5), preheat temperature and optical detection filter were set to 280 °C and 410 nm, respectively. Although the signals determined through the 410 nm optical filter are similar to slightly lower for the preheat temperature of 220 °C, corresponding errors suggest less appropriate measurement conditions for both, 10 % as well as 90 % LED power. Generally higher thermal transfer and much higher errors in equivalent dose estimation were detected through the 280 nm and especially through the 560 nm optical filter. Dose recovery tests according to Murray and Wintle (2003) were performed for SAL1 (K-feldspar, plagioclase).

Anomalous fading is often considered to ubiquitously cause systematic underestimation of IRSL ages (e.g., Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). However, it has been shown that IRSL emission centred at 410 nm (used in our study) is less affected by fading than UV emissions (Krbetschek et al., 1997). In particular for the Alps several studies have shown that IRSL ages agree well with independent age control (Preusser et al., 2001, 2003; Preusser and Schlüchter, 2004). Storage tests used for correcting the signal loss have recently shown to yield IRSL ages that are overestimating independent age control (Gaar and Preusser, 2012; Lowick et al., 2012). Furthermore, it has been shown that the fading rate is probably temperature dependent (Thomsen et al., 2008) and Krause et al. (1997) did not observe fading in their samples from Antarctica. Considering all

the above, we refrained from carrying out time-consuming storage tests, especially since it would have been very challenging to simulate the permafrost environment of our samples.

4.6. Analyses of luminescence data

The adequacy of detected luminescence signals for further analyses was evaluated based on their signal intensities above background (shine down curves) and dose-signal relation (growth curves) using the software ANA-LYST 3.24 (Duller, 2007). The distribution of equivalent doses for each sample is then analyzed using the R software and the R package Luminescence (Kreutzer et al., 2012) in order to assess the degree of differential bleaching and presence of distinct signal populations.

For well-bleached samples, a normal distribution of equivalent doses is expected, with standard deviations corresponding to uncertainties in individual doses and in dose rates. The palaeodose calculation based on the arithmetic mean or using the central age model (CAM; Galbraith et al. 1999) is sufficient. Non-normal distributions and higher standard deviations indicate differential bleaching and hence, require statistical modelling to determine the palaeodose that represents the true burial time of the well-bleached grains (e.g., Olley et al., 1998; Bailey and Arnold, 2006). The minimum age model (MAM) is designed to determine the palaeodose from skewed dose distributions assuming values from well-bleached grains for the lower portion of the distribution (Galbraith et al., 1999). However, the MAM is very sensitive to the lowermost equivalent doses. In the case of sediment mixing with younger grains the use of the MAM might be problematic. For rock glaciers, the grain input processes with differential bleaching and the potential of transport-related sediment mixing suggests that the dose distributions may be composed of several distinct populations. Accordingly, the finite mixture model (FMM; Galbraith and Green 1990) is preferred to determine the dominant population of the sample.

The overdispersion constitutes the essential input parameter for both, the MAM and the FMM. We have no appropriate material (e.g., well-bleached aeolian sand from the study area) to assess the overdispersion of our samples independently. Arnold et al. (2007) and Arnold and Roberts (2009) report values between 0.1 and 0.4 for fluvial deposits from different geographical regions. Accordingly, we tested the effect of using different overdispersion values (0.05 - 0.50) on the performance of the FMM (details are given in the supplementary material). Due to the overall low variations in FMM results with changes in overdispersion, a value of 0.3 seems to be a reasonable approximation for our samples, which also represents the value found for samples from the Swiss lowlands (Gaar and Preusser, 2012).

5. Results

5.1. Signal properties of quartz OSL

In general, the analyzed material often shows problematic luminescence properties and the low intensities often hardly allow separating the luminescence signal from the background noise. The very few equivalent doses (Tab. 3) of SUV1 (n = 3), SUV2 (n = 1), SUV4 (n = 3), GiG1 (n = 5), and GiG2 (n = 2) that could reliably be determined, provide only limited information about the dose distribution. For such samples, single grain measurements are not adequate enough to allow for the identification of distinct equivalent dose populations and the degree of bleaching. Corresponding dose-response curves from Suvretta and Gindana Grischa show a variable correlation of the OSL signal and applied laboratory dose (Fig. 6; top and middle). Poor recycling ratios and pronounced sensitivity changes and recuperation indicate poor luminescence properties of the measured material. Much brighter signals reveal higher luminescence sensitivities and low errors in equivalent dose estimation for several grains from Suvretta and most grains from Salteras (Fig. 6; bottom). The high uncertainties in recovering applied laboratory doses indicate material-inherent uncertainties that affect the reproducibility of OSL signals. Recovered doses deviate from the applied dose by more than 30 % in both, multiple-grain aliquot (SAL1) and single grain (SAL1) measurements. The latter tends to underestimate the recovery dose (Fig. 7a).

5.2. Signal properties of feldspar IRSL

Luminescence signals of IRSL single grain measurements show generally higher intensities for K-feldspar compared to plagioclase (Fig. 8). More grains reveal initial IRSL signals above the generally elevated background noise of 500 - 1000 counts per 0.01 s. Dose-response curves from the majority of those grains suggest a reliable dose-signal correlation. Recycling ratios close to unity and low recuperation allow for an improved curve fitting. Dose recovery tests for K-feldspar reproduce the applied laboratory dose with a variation (v_{DR}) of 8.1 % for SAL1 (Fig. 7b). In the case of plagioclases (SAL1), the overestimation of the applied laboratory dose resulted also in a high v_{DR} (~85 %). The poor reproducibility complicates the interpretation of equivalent doses. Only few equivalent doses could be determined from measured plagioclase grains (SAL1, SUV4). Low signal intensities and large uncertainties in growth curve fitting indicate mostly poor luminescence properties.

5.3. Analyses of equivalent dose distributions

The generally large scatter of equivalence doses (Figs. 9 - 11) implies a heterogeneous composition of the distributions, caused by insufficient bleaching and/or resulting from factors connected to the sediment dynamics within the rock glaciers. Hence, further statistical treatment is needed to infer palaeodoses representing the true age of

Figure 5: Thermal transfer test for SAL1 K-feldspars comparing three different parameters: preheat temperature (220 °C, 240 °C, 260 °C and 280 °C), optical filters (280 nm, 410 nm, 560 nm) and LED power (90% and 10%).

incorporation. A major problem in our study is the fact that in several cases the luminescence properties described above lead to only few determined values per sample along with high uncertainties (Tab. 3). This complicates or even precludes the analyses of the equivalent dose distributions; such limited datasets do not allow drawing conclusions about the bleaching level. We used the arithmetic mean (as a pragmatic solution) in a descriptive sense but did not calculate luminescence ages for these samples.

Only samples where more than 15 equivalent doses could be determined were used for further statistical analyses (Figs. 9 - 11). Well suited in this context is the Salteras sample (SAL1, Fig. 9) for which a large number of K-feldspar single grain ($n = 74$) and quartz single grain (234) equivalent dose values are available. Additionally, we have a sufficient number of multiple-grain quartz measurements (18) for this sample (Tab. 3). For Suvretta (Fig. 10), only four out of nine different measurements yielded sufficient numbers of equivalent dose values: SUV1 multiple-grain quartz (18), SUV2 single grain K-feldspar (60), SUV3 single grain quartz (58), and SUV4 single grain K-feldspar (35). For Gianda Grisca (Fig. 11), only GiG2 single grain K-feldspar (43) gave rise to a substantial number of analyzable measurements (Tab. 3). For all of these samples, we observe a broad spread of equivalent dose values, in many cases with relative standard deviations above 100%. The CAM yields overall lower values compared to simply using the arithmetic mean and thus, may be less affected by outliers (Tab. 3). However, the CAM values do not represent the main cluster at the lower end of the dose distribution as indicated by the probability density function (PDF) of most samples

(Figs. 9 - 11). The MAM palaeodose calculation tends to underestimate the main data cluster (maximum in PDF). Especially single low values affect MAM calculations, in some cases leading to palaeodose estimation based on only the lowest 1 - 5 values. The FMM enables a robust determination of the dominant population, corresponding to the main data cluster at the lower end of the dose distribution. Using the overdispersion value of 0.3, we determined two to three components in our samples. In all our samples the highest proportion (for most samples >70%) is represented by the lowest component, except for SAL 1 OSL multiple grain analysis with the second as the main component (Tab. 3). In most cases, the main component is accompanied by a secondary component of ~10% to 30%. For a few samples a minor third component of <10% could be distinguished comprising the highest dose values. Only for SAL 1 multiple grain OSL this

minor component comprises the lowest equivalent doses. Two samples (SUV 2 and GiG 2 single grain IRSL, both K-feldspar) differ from that picture by revealing two prominent components, of which the lower one is slightly dominant (>50%) and the secondary (<50%) indicates a distinct population of higher dose values.

5.4. OSL and IRSL ages

Table 3 summarizes the calculated luminescence ages for samples that allowed statistical analyses based on more than 15 values. All ages represent the main dose population determined by the FMM. The well performing luminescence signals of the Salteras rock glacier revealed ages of (6.4 ± 1.2) kyr and (6.4 ± 0.6) kyr for multiple grain

Figure 6: OSL single grain (SG) shine down (left) and dose response curves (right) for samples SAL1 disc1 grain 10, SUV3 disc3 grain 2 and 28.

Figure 7: Results from dose recovery tests for single grains (OSL and IRSL) of the rock glacier Salteras. The quartz grains (left) show a clear trend to underestimate the recovery dose (applied dose: 200 s or 36.4 Gy). In the case of K-Feldspar (right), a good reproducibility of the luminescence signals can be estimated, as indicated by the low coefficient of variation v_{DR} . N = number of grains.

quartz and single grain K-feldspar, respectively. Although the age of (7.7 ± 0.7) kyr for single grain quartz is slightly higher, it confirms the overall consistency of the results from investigated luminescence signals. The less well performing plagioclase single grain signals do not allow for a robust palaeodose and hence, age calculation. However, detectable equivalent doses and corresponding arithmetic mean are similar to the other luminescence measurements.

The consistency of the quartz and K-feldspar ages indicates that anomalous fading is likely not affecting the samples under consideration.

For the rock glacier Suvretta (Tab. 3), we determine consistent ages of (5.2 ± 0.8) kyr (multiple-grain quartz) and (4.8 ± 0.5) kyr (single grain K-feldspar) for the sample SUV2. Unfortunately, the OSL single grain measurements of SUV2 were not successful. All approaches failed

Figure 8: Single grain IRSL shine down curve and dose response curve for K-Feldspar of sample GiG1 and SUV3 and for Plagioclase of sample SAL1.

for close-by SUV1 apart from three OSL single grain results that indicate significantly higher values. The laterally distant samples SUV3 and SUV4 revealed ages of (3.5 ± 0.5) kyr (single grain quartz) and (3.0 ± 0.6) kyr (single grain K-feldspar), respectively. The OSL quartz and IRSL K-feldspar single grain datasets from SUV3 and SUV4 that consisted only of <15 values cover a comparable dose range like the FMM estimates of the robust datasets (>15 values). IRSL plagioclase measurements for SUV4 were not able to provide a sufficient dataset.

The sediments taken from the Gianda Grischa rock glacier yielded the poorest luminescence properties. Only for the single grain K-feldspar of sample GiG2, a substantial number of equivalent dose values are available (43), delivering an age of (3.0 ± 0.4) kyr. Interestingly, the eight single grain K-feldspar values from sample GiG1 agree with the FMM results of GiG2. In contrast, OSL single grain measurements of both samples yielded only few values with significantly higher doses. The poorly constrained quartz signals prevent reliable age estimation.

6. Discussion

The problematic luminescence properties of quartz and feldspars, especially plagioclase, indicate overall low luminescence sensitivities of the sampled rock glacier material, typical for sediments that underwent no or only few sedimentation cycles (cf. Pietsch et al. 2008). While very low signal intensities are especially encountered with the quartz measurements, also feldspar measurements often show high uncertainties in dose response curves and partly poor reproducibility in the dose recovery tests. In

general, the quartz OSL properties of the Salteras sample appear to be far more reliable than those of Suvretta and Gianda Grischa. A similar trend is observed for K-feldspar single grain measurements for Salteras compared to Suvretta and Gianda Grischa. We assume that material intrinsic properties of source rock play an important role for the differences in luminescence behavior of the investigated rock glaciers. Although the rock type is everywhere similar, some minor differences in the mineral assemblage (and mineral structure) might exist (see also Böhlert et al. 2011b,c).

The equivalent doses indicate heterogeneous, in most cases positively skewed distributions that suggest differential bleaching. However, considering the possibility of different grain transport pathways along with sediment mixing, different grain populations may be present. While the MAM tends to underestimate the main signal cluster, palaeodose calculation based on the FMM seems to be more adequate to address both, differential bleaching as well as the possibility of the incorporation of surface-derived grains. For most samples, the main FMM component ($>70\%$) represents the prominent signal cluster at the lower range of values that indicates a distinct population of well-bleached grains. Hence, we assume sufficient light exposure of grains during a dominating input process. Interestingly, we observe several rounded grains under the microscope implying the presence of an aeolian component in the sediment matrix. The secondary FMM component of $\sim 10\%$ to 30% comprises higher equivalent dose values accompanied in some cases by an additional third component of $<10\%$ for highest values (Tab. 3), but the effects of incomplete bleaching cannot be differentiated from the

Figure 9: Equivalent dose distributions of the sample from Salteras using different luminescence methods, top: OSL quartz multiple grain (left) and single grain (right), bottom: IRSL K- feldspar (left) and plagioclase (right). Dose distributions are described by the probability density function (PDF). Statistical analyses include the arithmetic mean (red line), the central age model (CAM, orange line), the minimum age model (MAM, green line) and the finite mixture model (FMM, light blue line). v_{DR} = coefficient of variation, N = number of aliquots/grains, sd = standard deviation.

contribution of sediment mixing. For SUV 2 and GiG 2 single grain IRSL, the prominent secondary FMM component of 40% to 47% may indicate a distinct input/uptake of an older grain population. Single low values may relate to a minor influence of mixing. The FMM distinguishes only for SAL 1 multiple grain OSL a minor component (<10%) from lowest equivalent doses. However, further implications on grain input and transport process for individual dose populations remain unresolved in our dataset.

Dose rate analyses did not reveal any significant disequilibrium in the ^{238}U decay series from direct Rn daughters. More challenging is the estimation of the palaeowater/ice content. The very low in situ contents are associated to the summer conditions during the sampling season and are probably not representative for the entire transfer time. Considering that creeping permafrost requires a high ice content, values close to saturation are more likely representing the average during grain travel. To cope with these overall uncertainties, large uncertainties for water content values have been included in this study. Theoretically,

high ice content and ice lenses may have caused an inhomogeneous distribution of dosimeter minerals (quartz, feldspar) and radionuclides (radiation sources controlling signal growth) in the sediment. However, measuring three minerals of different internal dose rates does not reveal systematic effects according to the reduced influence of external microdosimetric variations of K-feldspars compared to plagioclase and quartz. Overall, samples having a sufficient dataset showed a clearly dominant cluster that suggests normal distribution and only a low variation within the main population of assumed well-bleached grains. It appears that the creeping process of rock glacier material results in a more or less constant displacement of grains within the sediment-ice matrix, leading to an averaging effect on dose rates.

The calculated luminescence ages represent the time since grains were incorporated into the rock glacier and transported towards the talus front. Therefore, they provide minimum age of rock glacier formation. Despite difficult material properties, the ages calculated by different

Figure 10: Equivalent dose distributions of samples from Suvretta comparing OSL (top) and IRSL (bottom) measurement results. Dose distributions are described by the probability density function (PDF). Statistical analyses include the arithmetic mean (red line), the central age model (CAM, orange line), the minimum age model (MAM, green line) and the finite mixture model (FMM, light blue line). N = number of aliquots/grains, sd = standard deviation.

Figure 11: Equivalent dose distributions of samples from Gianda Grischa showing results of IRSL measurements. Dose distributions are described by the probability density function (PDF). Statistical analyses include the arithmetic mean (red line), and for sample GiG 2 additionally the central age model (CAM, orange line), the minimum age model (MAM, green line) and the finite mixture model (FMM, light blue line). N = number of aliquots/grains, sd = standard deviation.

Table 3: Palaeodose estimates and luminescence ages determined for different approaches. MG = multiple-grain aliquots; SG = single grains; kf = K-feldspar; pl = plagioclase; n = number of included aliquots/grains; Mean = arithmetic mean; RSD = relative standard deviation; CAM = Central Age Model; od(CAM) = overdispersion corresponding to CAM; FMM = Finite Mixture Model; Comp 1-3: proportion of each component determined by the FMM; Age = calculated only for samples with $n < 15$ using the component of highest proportion of the FMM.

Sample	Method	N	Mean [Gy]	RSD [%]	CAM [Gy]	od (CAM)	FMM [Gy]	Comp 1 [%]	Comp 2 [%]	Comp 3 [%]	Age [kyr]
<i>Salteras</i>											
SAL1	OSL-MG	18	28.9 ± 4.0	58.3	24.2 ± 3.7	0.56	22.8 ± 3.8	5.7	76.0	18.3	6.4 ± 1.2
	OSL-SG	234	48.4 ± 3.8	119.5	34.3 ± 1.6	0.68	26.9 ± 0.8	84.2	8.1	7.7	7.7 ± 0.7
	IRSL-SG (kf)	74	56.1 ± 11.5	176.5	35.9 ± 3.0	0.68	28.6 ± 1.5	85.3	10.7	4.0	6.4 ± 0.6
	IRSL-SG (pl)	9	40.6 ± 4.4	32.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Suvretta</i>											
SUV1	OSL-SG	3	206.3 ± 65.6	55.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SUV2	OSL-MG	18	36.0 ± 8.7	105.6	29.5 ± 5.5	0.66	21.8 ± 3.0	78.4	21.6	-	5.2 ± 0.8
	OSL-SG	1	29.3 ± 2.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SUV3	IRSL-SG (kf)	60	90.0 ± 10.9	94.3	54.0 ± 7.4	1.03	24.7 ± 1.6	59.5	40.5	-	4.8 ± 0.5
	OSL-SG	58	43.9 ± 7.5	125.8	25.2 ± 3.6	0.94	14.9 ± 1.4	73.9	26.1	-	3.5 ± 0.6
SUV4	IRSL-SG (kf)	9	11.4 ± 6.5	170.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	OSL-SG	3	11.7 ± 3.5	51.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	IRSL-SG (kf)	34	31.8 ± 10.3	188.2	18.3 ± 2.7	0.72	13.9 ± 1.6	79.6	15.7	4.7	3.0 ± 0.6
	IRSL-SG (pl)	1	20.7 ± 4.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Gianda Grischa</i>											
GiG1	OSL-SG	5	145.1 ± 29.8	46.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	IRSL-SG (kf)	8	16.1 ± 3.6	62.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
GiG2	OSL-SG	2	133.8 ± 13.5	14.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	IRSL-SG (kf)	43	113.5 ± 18.5	106.6	49.2 ± 11.2	1.42	13.4 ± 1.2	53.1	46.9	-	3.0 ± 0.4

approaches (Tab. 3) are consistent for individual sampling sites. However, estimates differ between the different rock glaciers. The longest grain travel times have been determined for Salteras. Compared to Suvretta and Gianda Grischa, this could indicate differences in creeping rates. Additionally, the deviation of results from two laterally distant sites at Suvretta implies that it might be even possible to resolve variations in creeping rates for distinct lateral zones of rock glaciers. To confirm creeping rate differences, additional tests are required that address the partly high luminescence variability encountered in dose recovery tests.

All luminescence ages for the currently still active rock glaciers are between 3 kyr and 8 kyr, supported by previous estimates (Haeberli et al., 2003) and in agreement with flow trajectory analyses and photogrammetric approaches that indicate minimum surface ages between 3 kyr and 6 kyr (Kääb et al., 1998; Frauenfelder et al., 2005). This confirms the concept of Holocene rock glaciers developing at millennial time scales as also deduced from weathering rinds, lichenometry and radiocarbon dating (Haeberli et al., 2003). Although derived travel times determine a similar time range as preliminary results of quartz measurements (4 - 8 kyr) for the rock glaciers Murtl, Muragl and La Veduta (Upper Engadine, Switzerland), results cannot be compared in terms of their reliability due to unavailability of measurement details.

However, the OSL based travel times from Salteras, Suvretta and Gianda Grischa indicate differences between the rock glaciers. Recent velocities measured at various sites reveal variations between and within rock glaciers that depend especially on slope, local climate and related

ice content as well as temperature (Haeberli et al., 2003; Frauenfelder et al., 2005). Accordingly, the different travel times may simply reflect site-specific variations in flow velocities. To clearly distinguish rock glacier generations from travel times requires further investigations on the respective roles of different flow velocities and activity phases. Overall, the OSL based travel times need to be regarded as minimum ages and indicate that the investigated high Alpine rock glaciers began to evolve during the Early and/or Middle Holocene.

7. Conclusion

This is the first study systematically exploring the potential of luminescence dating of sediments that are imbedded in rock glaciers. In general, poor luminescence properties of both feldspar and, in particular, of quartz were encountered, with only some measurement approaches resulting in robust datasets. Most reliable results were yielded for Salteras, whereas samples from Suvretta and especially Gianda Grischa are highly problematic. Promising is the fact that most datasets showed a clear signal clustering at the lower end of the dose distribution, suggesting sufficient bleaching during a dominant grain input process, likely through aeolian sediment supply to and/or grain retention at the rock glacier surface. The heterogeneous dose distributions also indicate a contribution of incompletely bleached grains, but only limited effects of sediment mixing.

The luminescence ages are consistent at each individual sampling site, but show variations between rock glaciers and may indicate even differences between different parts

of the same rock glacier lobe (Suvretta). Again, it should be noted that the ages represent the travel times of grains and hence represent only minimum ages of rock glacier formation. Luminescence ages between 3 kyr and 8 kyr fall within the expected time range determined by other relative and semiquantitative approaches, indicating that rock glaciers started their present phase of activity in the Early/ Middle Holocene. While the derived minimum ages do not further narrow down onset of rock glacier formation, they deliver valuable constraints about grain travel times and, hence, dynamics of rock glacier material. However, several questions about variations in luminescence properties and dose rates of sediments with high ice content have not been investigated here in detail, and need to be addressed in future studies.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation grant numbers 20-109565/1 and 20-124380. We gratefully thank Alexandra Hilgers for the support and opportunity of OSL single grain measurements at the luminescence laboratory at the University of Cologne. We also received substantial support from Thomas Rosenberg during the IRSL single grain measurements at the luminescence laboratory of the University of Bern.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data related to this article can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2013.07.001>.

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3.4 Methodological implications

The Chapters 3.2 and 3.3 highlight the need of comprehensive data analyses when applying luminescence methods to sediments from high mountains. The **R.Luminescence** package provides a flexible toolbox of functions to evaluate the reliability of the used mineral, measurement conditions and sediment-related effects (bleaching, sediment mixing). The presented **R** templates of Paper II introduce how the functions of the **R.Luminescence** package may be combined and how function results may be passed to the next analytical step via the definition of variables.

This allows for effective data processing especially when challenging luminescence properties of the analyzed material demand repetitive measurements to assure a convenient measurement set-up or to record the influence of adjusted parameters. Once the analysis routines are defined according to the applied protocol or model parameters, data processing may be easily reproduced as desired. For example, the integration of **R** internal loop functions into the **R** template for age modeling allowed for an automatic analysis of the influence of overdispersion on model results. Using this computational flexibility, it could be demonstrated that changing the input parameter overdispersion between 0.05 and 0.5 had little effects on age models, in particular on FMM results (see Paper III in chapter 3.3, and Appendix II).

The luminescence characteristics of the permafrost material from Alpine rock glaciers reveal the generally lower quartz signals, while feldspars showed sufficient intensities also in single grain analyses. However, comparing luminescence signals from different study sites shows that the mineral-intrinsic variations occur for the same mineral between localities. Especially quartz reveals clear variations between sites. Hence, in the case of bright quartz signals even single grain measurements are possible besides the assumed low sensitization before grain incorporation into the rock glacier body. That promises a reliable application of luminescence methods to quartz taking advantage of the faster signal bleaching. Additionally, no uncertainties arise from anomalous fading that would lead to time consuming correction of fading and also the uncertainties from the ^{40}K -related, internal dose rate do not apply. The comparison of age model results from quartz and feldspar analyses support reliable performance with no systematic trend when comparing multiple and single grain aliquots of quartz. This also suggests that the multiple grain aliquots may be sufficient to reveal the signals of well bleached grains. This supports the finding that only few grains of quartz contribute to the luminescence signal measured for multiple grain aliquots and the effect of averaging signals from individual grains seems of low importance for the studied samples.

4 OSL-based incision rates along the Panj

4.1 Fluvial incision along the Panj river

Fluvial incision in the Pamir is dominated by the Panj, the trunk stream that defines the local base level for most of the Pamir rivers. The Panj contours the southern boundary of the Pamir and cuts the western margin close to the drainage divide, before turning west towards the Tajik depression. Geomorphometric analyses reveal the composite character of the Panj as a result of successive river captures (Paper I, chapter 2.2). The zones of pronounced fluvial incision do not coincide with changes in rock type or catchment size but with the Panj cutting across the Shakh dara and Yazgulom domes and their bounding faults. Wide valleys and graded profile sections indicate low incision parallel to southern dome boundaries.

However, despite this relative indication of structural control on the organization of the Panj river network and hence, fluvial incision, little is known about time scales and absolute rates. The Panj constitutes ideal conditions to study the variability in fluvial incision where it flows at the western Pamir margin and cuts the main tectonic structures of the orogen. Steep, narrow valleys imply the prevalence of fluvial incision, while fluvial terrace remnants document local, short-term sedimentation at higher paleo-river levels. Such references of the paleo-river altitudes are used in Paper IV (chapter 4.2) to determine the fluvial incision rates of the Panj. Spatial and temporal variations are identified based on:

- OSL dating of fluvial terrace sediments
- Analyses of terrace age - height relation
- Discussion of variations in fluvial incision rates with respect to tectonic and climatic factors

The accurate and precise estimation of terrace ages and hence, when the paleo-river was at the respective altitudes, essentially relies on the luminescence properties and the detection of differential bleaching (see chapter 3). In Paper IV, both are addressed by different aliquot sizes, variations in measurement parameters and comprehensive statistical analyses including age modeling based on the minimum age model (MAM, Galbraith et al. 1999) and the finite mixture model (FMM, Galbraith and Green 1990). Terrace sedimentation and incision are then evaluated for their regional and temporal consistency based on the terrace age-height relation. Temporal and spatial variations distinguish the influence of climatically triggered, regionally consistent sedimentation and that of local differences in tectonic forcing.

- **Paper IV (chapter 4.2)**

Fuchs, M.C., Gloaguen, R., Krbetschek, M., Szulc, A. (2014): Rates of river incision across the main tectonic units of the Pamir identified using optically stimulated luminescence dating of fluvial terraces. *Geomorphology* 216, 79-92.
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4.2 Paper IV: Rates of river incision across the main tectonic units of the Pamir identified using optically stimulated luminescence dating of fluvial terraces

Rates of river incision across the main tectonic units of the Pamir identified using optically stimulated luminescence dating of fluvial terraces

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Abstract

Calculated incision rates along the Panj, the main river of the Pamir, are used to investigate any influence by tectonics or climate on the architecture of the river. The depositional ages of Panj river terraces were calculated using optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating of terrace sand. Fluvial incision rates were generated by integrating the terrace depositional ages with accurate kinematic GPS measurements of terrace heights above the modern Panj. We investigated 16 terraces along the Panj at the western Pamir margin and one terrace from the Vakhsh River to the north of the Pamir. The results reveal brief periods of fluvial deposition over the past 26 kyr. The oldest Panj terrace depositional ages coincide with early MIS 2 and MIS 2/1 glaciations on the Pamir Plateau. Younger terrace ages have no apparent link with glacial cycles. Terraces with varying heights above the modern Panj at different localities yielded similar depositional ages. This suggests that local conditions have determined fluvial incision rates. Combining all of the terrace measurements, the average incision rate of the Panj over the last 26 kyr has been ~ 5.6 mm/yr. A high mean incision rate of ~ 7.3 mm/yr was calculated from terraces where the Panj has cut a steep-sided valley through the Shakh dara Dome. Significantly lower incision rates (~ 2 -3 mm/yr) were calculated from terraces where the Panj flows along the southern boundaries of the Shakh dara and Yazgulom domes. At those localities, graded segments of the Panj river profile and increased valley widths are indicative of local base levels. Downstream of the Yazgulom Dome, river incision rates are generally lower (~ 4 -5 mm/yr) than the Panj average. However, there is one exception where higher incision rates (~ 6 mm/yr) were calculated upstream of the Darvaz Fault Zone, a major tectonic feature that forms the western boundary of the Pamir. The Vakhsh river terrace to the north of the Pamir yielded a lower incision rate (~ 3 mm/yr) compared to the Panj average. Variation in incision rates along the Panj does not correspond to changes in rock type or river catchment area. Instead, incision rates appear to have been primarily influenced by river capture across the southern and central metamorphic domes of the Pamir. Wherever the Panj cuts these domes it displays a convex river profile. The combination of localized river profile convexity and changes in incision rates across the Pamir domes indicates that the dome boundaries have been active recently.

Keywords: OSL dating, fluvial terraces, incision rates, Hack Index, valley shape ratios, Pamir

1. Introduction

The Pamir region is an excellent natural laboratory for studying the influence of tectonics and climate on fluvial processes and topographic evolution. Situated at the western end of the India-Asia collision zone, the Pamir have experienced some of the highest deformation rates on the planet (e.g., Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Pegler and Das, 1998; Reigber et al., 2001; Ducea et al., 2003; Wheeler et al., 2005). The topography of the Pamir is dominated by a series of Oligo-Miocene domes (Hubbard et al., 1999; Ducea et al., 2003; Schwab et al., 2004; Amidon and Hynek, 2010). The timing and mechanism of

dome exhumation and the distribution of neotectonic activity are a focus of research in the Pamir (e.g., Schmidt et al., 2011; Schneider et al., 2013; Sippl et al., 2013; Stübner et al., 2013). The Pamir lies in a climatic transition zone between the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM). Feedbacks with topography result in climatic gradients between the margins and the plateau of the Pamir. Glacial moraines on the Pamir Plateau provide evidence for multiple glacial advances during the Late Quaternary (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012).

Drainage in the Pamir generally follows the predominantly east-west trend of the mountain ranges (Fig. 1). However, at the western margin of the Pamir the Panj river turns northwards and cuts across the southern and central Pamir domes and several major Cenozoic faults. The Panj then turns again to resume a southwesterly flow direction.

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Such anomalies in drainage architecture provide keys to unraveling the local controls on landscape evolution (e.g., Leland et al., 1998; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Hancock and Anderson, 2002; Bull, 2007; Brookfield, 2008). The Panj cuts through one of the most tectonically active regions on the planet. The circuitous route of the Panj is advantageous as it allows the measurement of fluvial incision rates for different tectonic units of the Pamir. Relative estimates of fluvial incision such as the river profile and valley morphology suggest successive river capture events across the Pamir domes (Fuchs et al., 2013b). However, fluvial incision rates have not previously been quantified for the Panj and little is known about the spatial and temporal variations of terrace formation within the Pamir.

Incision rates can be calculated based on fluvial terraces by dividing the height of a terrace above the modern river floodplain by the age of the terrace. In erosional settings such as high mountains, fluvial terraces above a modern river record periods of fluvial stability that interrupt prevalent incision (e.g., Vandenberghe et al., 2011). The factors behind changes in the fluvial dynamic associated with sediment deposition, terrace abandonment and subsequent incision may be complex because of the interplay of tectonics and climate (e.g., Pazzaglia et al., 1998; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Formento-Trigilio et al., 2002; Pan et al., 2009). Globally compiled fluvial records indicate that terrace formation is primarily a consequence of tectonic uplift combined with cyclic climate (e.g., Bridgland and Westaway, 2008; Westaway et al., 2009). The cyclic glaciations of the Quaternary have played an important role in triggering sediment generation and water discharge (e.g., Hancock and Anderson, 2002; Formento-Trigilio et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2009). Tectonic uplift causes relative base level lowering that is an important precondition of terrace incision and preservation (e.g., Bridgland and Westaway, 2008; Vandenberghe et al., 2011). Without relative uplift, fluvial sediments rather form stacked or over- and onlapping deposits as observed, for example, in sedimentary basins (Vandenberghe et al., 2011). Differential uplift may further cause small-scale variations in stream power across tectonic units that lead to the formation of localized terraces between areas of relative subsidence (Vandenberghe et al., 2011). However, the interpretation of incision rates in terms of relative bedrock uplift rates or climatic control is debated. It requires careful evaluation of intrinsic effects of the studied fluvial systems such as timescale dependencies or river channel evolution (e.g., Burbank et al., 1996; Leland et al., 1998; Carcaillet et al., 2009; Pan et al., 2009; Vandenberghe et al., 2011; Finnegan et al., 2014).

OSL dating of terrace sediments provides a maximum age of terrace abandonment. OSL dates the last time a sediment has been exposed to light. Assuming the sediment has had no contact with light since initial burial this age has important uses in geomorphologic studies. Advantageous is that OSL dating can be applied to quartz grains, a ubiquitous component of sediment. Compared

to feldspars, the other commonly used mineral in luminescence dating, quartz does not show anomalous fading (Wintle, 1973) and has a faster signal reset (Wallinga, 2002). However, in mountain settings the OSL properties of quartz have been found to be problematic (e.g., Preusser et al., 2006; Fuchs et al., 2013a) due to low sensitization related to few sedimentation cycles (e.g., Pietsch et al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012). In such settings OSL dating of quartz requires additional attention to measurement parameters. Another essential question concerns the degree of signal reset (bleaching) during fluvial transport. Especially in mountainous areas, peak discharge in the melting season and high sediment loads can cause incomplete bleaching of grains. Such sediments require statistical dose distribution analyses to select the appropriate age model (e.g., Galbraith et al., 1999).

Here, we combine optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating of fluvial terraces and kinematic GPS measurements of terrace heights above the present river to quantify local fluvial incision rates along the northward-deflected Panj and its downstream reaches. To address differential bleaching and ensure a correct paleodose determination, we apply statistical age models to the measured data sets (e.g., Bailey and Arnold, 2006; Arnold et al., 2007). OSL-based local incision rates and their variations are set in context by analyzing the longitudinal profile of the Panj and utilizing Hack Indices as long-term morphometric indicators (Hack, 1973; Snyder et al., 2000; Singh and Awasthi, 2010; Stokes et al., 2012). We compare the pattern of fluvial incision rates to valley morphology perpendicular to the modern river, quantified by measuring the valley shape ratio (VSR) (Fuchs et al., 2013b). We discuss the potential forcing from glacial cycles during the Late Quaternary as well as the relevance of changes in rock types and increases in catchment area for explaining the spatial variations of fluvial incision.

2. Study area

2.1. Tectonic setting

Lying at the northwestern end of the India-Asia collision zone (Fig. 1), the Pamir comprises a series of Paleozoic to Mesozoic sutures, magmatic belts and crustal blocks (e.g., Burtman and Molnar, 1993) that formed a steady state elevated plateau since the onset of the Cenozoic (Ducea et al., 2003). The tectonic units are assumed to be along-strike equivalents of the Tibetan Plateau that accreted to the Eurasian plate (e.g., Cowgill, 2010; Bershaw et al., 2012). In particular, the Cretaceous arc-type granitoids in the Central and Southern Pamir have been linked to equivalents in Tibet. However, the details of such correlations are still debated (e.g., Schwab et al., 2004; Robinson, 2009).

The domes cover up to 30% of the Pamir and expose crystalline basement and metamorphic rocks (Vlasov et al., 1991; Brunel et al., 1994; Schwab et al., 2004; Robinson

Figure 1: Regional setting of the Panj river network. Map of the Pamir with drainage network, main geological structures and atmospheric circulation (m. a.s.l.: meters above sea level, KD: Kurgovat Dome, YD: Yazgulom Dome, SD: Sarez Dome, MD: Muskol Dome, SPD: Shatput Dome, SAD: Shakhdara-Alichur Dome, DFZ: Darvaz Fault Zone, MPT: Main Pamir Thrust, KS: Kunlun Suture, TS: Tanymas Suture, RPS: Rushan-Psart Suture, GSZ: Gunt Shear Zone, SPSZ: Southern Pamir Shear Zone, white line: national boundaries, ?: unknown extent of tectonic structure). Modified after Fuchs et al. (2013b)

et al., 2007; Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2013) The Kurgovat Dome of the Northern Pamir consists of high-grade metamorphosed Triassic rocks. The domes in the Central Pamir (Yazgulom, Sarez, Muskol and Shatput domes; Fig. 1) and the Southern Pamir (Shakhdara and Alichur domes) have exhumed high-grade metamorphic rocks of Oligocene-Miocene age (Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2013). The Pamir gneiss domes relate to orogen-wide exhumation between ~ 21 Myr and 13 Myr (Lukens et al., 2012). Dome exhumation in the eastern Pamir has remained constant since ~ 7 Myr (Robinson et al., 2010). Thermochronology indicates that exhumation of the Shakhdara and Yazgulom domes reached a peak at ~ 15 Myr and continued until at least ~ 2 Myr (Stübner et al., 2013).

Neotectonic activity is focused at the active frontal range of the Pamir that bends almost 180° from northern Afghanistan into western China (Bershaw et al., 2012). The indentation of the Pamir into Eurasia has involved two intermediate-depth intra-continental subduction zones that are resolvable by seismicity and tomography (southern Tien Shan-Pamir and Hindu-Kush-Pamir slabs; e.g. Koulakov and Sobolev, 2006; Schneider et al., 2013; Sippl et al., 2013). GPS measurements show northward shortening of ~ 15 mm/yr across the Main Pamir Thrust (MPT)

and ~ 10 mm/yr south of Pamir across the Hindu Kush and Chitral Himalaya (Ischuk et al., 2013). The lateral margins of the orocline accommodate transtension to the east along the Karakoram Fault Zone (KFZ) and transpression to the west along the Darvaz Fault Zone (DFZ, cf. Fig. 1). Late Quaternary lateral motion across the DFZ reaches ~ 12 mm/yr (Trifonov, 1978; Mohadjer et al., 2010). The strike-slip faults in the south-eastern Pamir that root in the KFZ display low lateral displacement rates of < 1 mm/yr (Strecker et al., 1995). The southern boundary is complex but indicates a major east-west, low-angle normal fault that bounds the Shakhdara Dome to the south, referred to as Southern Pamir Shear Zone (SPSZ, cf. Figs. 1, 2, own field observations and Stübner et al. 2013). Away from the Pamir boundaries, seismic records indicate an intra-plateau neotectonic activity that relates to the east-west extension of the Karakul rift system, and scattered seismic activity in the Southern Pamir (e.g., Fan et al., 1994; Strecker et al., 1995; Sippl et al., 2013).

2.2. Present and past climatic conditions

Data from the Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM, 3B42 V7 product) shows that the Westerlies supply most precipitation to the western margins of the Pamir

Figure 2: Location of fluvial terraces along the Panj and Vakhsh rivers that were sampled for OSL dating. Potential control factors include topography (m. a.s.l.: meters above sea level), and major tectonic structures (KD: Kurgovat Dome, YD: Yazgulom Dome, SAD: Shakh dara-Alichur Dome, DFZ: Darvaz Fault Zone, MPT: Main Pamir Thrust, KS: Kunlun Suture, TS: Tanyamas Suture, RPS: Rushan-Psart Suture, GSZ: Gunt Shear Zone, SPSZ: Southern Pamir Shear Zone, white line: national boundaries, ?: unknown extent of tectonic structure) and distribution of permanent snow and ice cover (MODIS MCD12Q1, Strahler et al. 1999, year 2010, Land Cover Classification according to the International Geosphere Biosphere Programme). Additionally, we display the timing of glacial advances inferred from three sites at the Pamir Plateau (blue to greenish boxes in the map, numbers represent ^{10}Be -based moraine ages in thousand years (kyr), *-***: reference annotations of individual glacial chronologies, references are given in the map legend).

during winter and spring. To the south, summer precipitation from the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) rapidly attenuates over the Hindu Kush and Karakoram Range before reaching the Pamir. Both result in considerable precipitation gradients and a westward displacement of permanent ice and snow cover. The central plateau regions receive little rainfall, mainly in the form of snow. Plateau glaciers are small (Fuchs et al., 2013b).

The position of the Pamir at the transition between the Westerlies and the ISM means the region is particularly sensitive to changes in atmospheric circulation patterns (Zech et al., 2005a). Glacial advances particularly during the Late Quaternary likely affected the drainage evolution by changing transported sediment volumes and river discharge and therefore may have triggered the development of river terraces along the Panj. Information regarding the Quaternary glacial chronology of the Pamir is limited to few study sites on the Pamir Plateau (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). A chronology for local glacial landforms at lower altitudes in west-trending valleys has yet to be established.

There is a synchronicity between the Quaternary glaciations and Northern Hemisphere cooling cycles during MIS 4 and MIS 2 (Fig. 2), indicating the dominance of the Westerlies (Abramowski et al., 2006; Owen et al., 2008). Pro-

gressively less extensive advances suggest links to an increasing aridity throughout the Late Quaternary in Central Asia due to a strengthened Siberian High (Abramowski et al., 2006).

However, the most extensive glacial advances on the Pamir Plateau occurred during MIS 4 or earlier during MIS 5-6. Cosmogenic nuclide dating of the moraine yielded two age clusters of 136-93 kyr and 86-60 kyr (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The oldest glacial moraine from the Lake Yashilkul, the Southern Alichur Range and the Ailuitek Pass indicates the presence of paleo-glaciers down to the intra-plateau valley floors at ~ 3600 m a.s.l.. Hummocky moraines accompanied by two lateral moraine ridges indicate a glacial advance during MIS 3, which is synchronous with an increased influence of the ISM (Zech et al., 2005a; Röhringer et al., 2012) as reported from the Hindu Kush, Karakoram Range and Tibet (e.g., Owen et al., 2002b,a, 2008, 2012). Additional scattered younger ages are interpreted as prolonged ice degradation and/or glacial recession (Zech et al., 2005b). Two less extensive glacial advances between 37-30 kyr (MIS 3/2) and 24-22 kyr (MIS 2) pre-date the LGM (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). Minor glacial advances have been identified at ~ 16 kyr and ~ 12 kyr during an overall period of glacial

Figure 3: Valley morphology of the Panj. A: Uppermost Panj reach (Pamir River) in wide valley with extensive sediment fills, B: Deep canyon incised into bedrock at the margins of the Pamir Plateau, C: Wide valley with low riverbed slopes, braided river perturbed by lateral fan sedimentation, D-F: Steep valleys with debris and alluvial fan deposits that are cut and removed by the Panj. Fluvial sediments are locally restricted to a few localities and indicate only short-term periods of deposition.

retreat (Röhringer et al., 2012).

2.3. The Panj river network

The Panj river originates at the south-eastern Pamir Plateau (Fig. 3A). Flowing along the southern and western Pamir margins, it drains most of the Pamir towards the west into the Tajik depression. The Panj drainage basin is strongly asymmetric with predominantly westward draining rivers (Fig. 2). Tributaries join the Panj at the western Pamir margin, close to the drainage divide. The northward-deflected reach of the Panj parallels the south-bending DFZ and cuts across the Shakh dara and Yazgulom domes. Valley morphometries (Fig. 3A-F) and the longitudinal profile indicate that the Panj is a composite, non-equilibrated river (Fuchs et al., 2013b). Steep valleys (Fig. 3B, D-F) and prominent convex zones along the river profile suggest three successive river capture events (Fuchs et al., 2013b). The non-equilibrated, convex zones connect reaches where the Panj develops a more concave profile with wider valleys (Fig. 3C). The more graded Panj reaches suggest local base levels at the southern dome boundaries of westward-oriented valleys. In this context, the term local base level refers to the base level that the fitted profiles respond to (details on profile analyses of the Panj are given in Fuchs et al. 2013b).

3. Methodology

3.1. Investigated fluvial terraces

The fluvial terraces investigated in this study are located along the northward-deflected Panj and its downstream reaches (Figs. 2, 3 D-F). These were sampled for OSL dating to determine variations in fluvial incision rates across the main tectonic units of the Pamir. In this part of the Panj, the terraces comprise relatively rare, discontinuous fluvial deposits. Their formation is not regionally consistent, as indicated by the lack of continuous valley fills and paired terraces. The narrow and steep valleys of the northward-deflected reach of the Panj with limited sedimentation indicate the predominance of fluvial incision. Layers of coarse fluvial sand are in most cases ~ 1 m thick, reaching 2-4 m at a few localities (TA31N, TA31O, TA02C, TA11A and B). The north-trending reach of the Panj incises bedrock and deposited sediment forms isolated beaches (Fig. 4B, C).

Sixteen fluvial terraces from different localities along the Panj were sampled (Fig. 2). Additionally, one terrace from the Vakhsh River was sampled to test for any difference in incision rate north of the Main Pamir Thrust. Selected terraces were layered, well-sorted and composed of quartz-rich sands. These outcrop as lenses several meters in length. Only terraces that clearly originated from the trunk river were sampled. Sample positions were located using multi-frequency post-processing kinematic GNSS (PPK) techniques. Apart from exact longitude and lat-

Table 1: Location and description of sampled terraces (m a.s.l.: meters above sea level, m a.r.l.: meters above local river level). Bold letters in sample names indicate notations used in the text.

Location	Sample	Position			Terrace heights		Sediment description
		Latitude [°N]	Longitude [°E]	Altitude [m a.s.l.]	[m a.r.l.]		
Ishkashim	TA090826A	36.813	71.555	2425	13.0	13.0	Layered medium sand
Ishkashim	TA090826C	36.792	71.568	2454	24.9	24.9	Lens of medium sand
Ishkashim	TA090825A	36.739	71.610	2850	191.0	191.0	Layer of silt to fine sand
Ishkashim	TA090825B	36.737	71.610	2746	68.0	68.0	Lens of medium sand
Sanjut	TA100906A	36.903	71.526	2613	151.0	151.0	Layer of medium sand
Andarop, south	TA090827H	37.216	71.461	2259	20.7	20.7	Lens of fine to medium sand
Andarop, south	TA090828B	37.219	71.460	2236	6.3	6.3	Layer of medium sand
Andarop, south	TA090828D	37.219	71.462	2246	15.3	15.3	Layer of fine to medium sand
Andarop	TA090827E	37.235	71.485	2264	10.0	10.0	Layered silt to medium sand
Khorog, south	TA090830C	37.348	71.492	2152	29.3	29.3	Layered fine to medium sand
Khorog	TA090831A	37.181	71.530	2108	72.0	72.0	Cross-bedded fine to medium sand
Rushan, south	TA110831N	37.676	71.533	2059	10.7	10.7	Layer of medium sand
Rushan, south	TA110831O	37.676	71.533	2102	4.1	4.1	Layer of coarse sand
Vanj, confluence	TA090902C	38.291	71.340	1589	84.6	84.6	Cross-bedded fine to medium sand
Khalaikhum, west	TA090908A	38.124	70.493	1061	57.8	57.8	Layer of fine to medium sand
north-western Panj	TA090923B	37.181	71.530	2108	72.0	72.0	Cross-bedded medium to coarse sand
Vakhsh river	TA090911A	38.859	69.963	1115	21.2	21.2	Layered medium sand
Vakhsh river	TA090911B	38.859	69.963	1115	21.2	21.2	Cross-bedded medium sand

itude positioning, GNSS PPK ensures precise altitude determination with an uncertainty of < 5 cm (Table 1). The altitudes of the terrace surface, the sample site, and the modern river level were measured in order to calculate accurate terrace and sample heights above the river.

3.2. OSL-based terrace dating

3.2.1. OSL sampling

For each terrace we sampled the uppermost sand layer or lens to determine maximum ages of terrace abandonment and hence the earliest terrace incision age. Sample location within the uppermost fluvial layer kept a minimum distance of 50 cm below the terrace surface. Layer boundaries and areas of clear sediment inhomogeneities were avoided. OSL samples were taken after removing ~50 cm of surface material to exclude the daylight-exposed part of the outcrop (Fig. 4A). Horizontal sediment cores were recovered in light-occluding cylinders and sealed for transport and storage. Sediment surrounding the hole made by the cylinder was sampled for gamma-spectrometric analysis of radionuclide content in order to determine the dose rate.

3.2.2. Sample preparation

Under subdued red light, an approximately 2 cm-thick layer was removed from both ends of each sediment core. That material was used to measure the sediment's water content during the sampling season (in situ) and its maximum capacity (saturation). From the inner part of the sediment core, the coarse quartz fraction was separated by sieving (100-200 μm), removal of carbonates (HCl 10%) and organic material (H_2O_2 30%), feldspar flotation (HF 0.2%, H_2SO_4 , dodecylamine, HCl 5%), density separation

(sodium polytungstate 2.62 g/cm³ and 2.67 g/cm³), etching (HF 40%, HCl 37%), and further sieving (90-160 μm). Homogeneous subsamples (aliquots) were prepared by fixing a monolayer of the extracted quartz grains on aluminum cups with silicon oil. Two aliquot sizes with diameters of 4 mm and 2 mm were used to address the effect of averaging the signals of multiple grain aliquots (Duller, 2008). However, 4 mm aliquots contain about 200-400 grains, of which only a few will be luminescent (e.g., Heer et al., 2012). The selection of aliquots suitable for quartz OSL measurements was based on negligible Infrared Stimulated Optical Luminescence (IRSL at 880 nm, 5 s) signals. These signals highlight any feldspar contamination.

3.2.3. OSL measurements

OSL measurements were conducted using a Risø DA 20 OSL/TL reader equipped with a ⁹⁰Sr beta irradiator (5.6 Gy/min). The OSL emission was stimulated with blue LEDs (470 nm) for 50 s at 125 °C and detected through a U 340 Hoya optical filter. Pre-heating (10 s) before OSL stimulation eliminated unstable signal components. The temperature was selected after checking appropriate pre-heat conditions (pre-heat 200 °C, 230 °C, 260 °C; cut-heat 160 °C, 200 °C, 230 °C, 260 °C) for each sample. Additionally, the early background subtraction was tested as suggested by Cunningham and Wallinga (2010) to guarantee the signal estimation based on the fast signal component. Equivalent doses for each aliquot were determined using the single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol according to Murray and Wintle (2000). Subsequent to the natural signal, six regeneration cycles including the control of recuperation and recycling ratio assessed the aliquot-specific relationship between given dose and observed luminescence intensity. The control of sensitivity changes

Figure 4: Terrace sampling for incision rate estimation. A: OSL sampling of the uppermost fluvial sand layer (minimum depth 50 cm) and kinematic GPS measurements of terrace heights with I) terrace surface altitude and II) altitude of present river level. B: Steep valley formed by dominant incision with alluvial fans cut by the Panj and local modern beach sediments. C: Modern beach sediments illustrate local fluvial deposition.

involved test dose cycles after each OSL measurement cycle. Dose recovery tests were performed as described by Murray and Wintle (2003) in order to assess the reproducibility of an applied laboratory dose (recovery dose). The coefficient of variation (v_{DR}) describes the standard deviation of equivalent doses against the recovery dose. It indicates the adequacy of the used measurement procedure and enables the detection of unusual luminescence behavior of a sample under laboratory conditions (Murray and Wintle, 2003).

3.2.4. Paleodose estimation

Luminescence signals were examined for equivalent dose calculation using ANALYST v3.24 (Duller, 2007). In general, fluvial sediments are prone to insufficient light exposure before deposition. As a result sediments can comprise grains that have been bleached to different levels (e.g., Duller, 1994; Olley et al., 1998; Fuchs and Lang, 2001; Fuchs et al., 2005). Therefore, it is essential to analyze the distribution of equivalent doses for differential bleaching and to select appropriate statistical procedures for paleodose calculation. Calculations were performed using the programming language R and the Luminescence R package (Kreutzer et al., 2012).

Differential bleaching is assumed in the case of a non-lognormal distribution and/or high standard deviation (e.g., Galbraith et al., 1999). For these cases statistical modeling is required to determine the true burial age (e.g., Olley et al., 1998; Murray and Olley, 2002; Rodnight et al., 2006; Bailey and Arnold, 2006; Arnold et al., 2007). A widely used statistical approach to exclude incompletely bleached

grains is the minimum age model (MAM) Galbraith et al. (1999). The MAM determines the paleodose from skewed data sets assuming well-bleached grains for the lower portion of the distribution. In the case of sediment mixing, the finite mixture model (FMM) may be utilized for unmixing the signal populations and deriving the dominant data cluster (Galbraith and Green, 1990).

Overdispersion is the essential input factor for MAM and FMM calculations. This takes into account additional data scatter that is not explained by individual measurement errors or incomplete bleaching. The Panj drainage basin does not provide suitable material (well bleached aeolian sand) to allow an independent overdispersion assessment. Arnold et al. (2007) and Arnold and Roberts (2009) found overdispersion values of 0.1-0.4 for fluvial deposits from various other study regions. We tested the influence of overdispersion between 0.05 and 0.5 on MAM results for all samples. There was no significant variation of paleodoses. Low effects of changing overdispersion resemble findings of Fuchs et al. (2013a) (supplementary data) for permafrost sediments of a high mountain setting in Switzerland. Best fit of the lowest data cluster (maximum in KDE estimates) was achieved for overdispersion values of 0.1-0.25. These were consequently used for MAM calculations. Additionally, 2mm aliquots were designed to improve the detection of the sufficiently bleached portion of equivalent doses in the observed dose distribution. The lower number of grains per aliquot reduces the averaging effect of individual signals and therefore the risk of grains with residual components masking well-bleached grains (e.g., Murray and Olley, 2002; Duller, 2008; Cun-

ningham et al., 2011).

3.2.5. Dose rate estimation

Dose rate was estimated by measuring the specific activity of radionuclides (decay chains of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K) in each sample, utilizing low-level HPG (high-purity germanium) gamma spectrometry. Radioactive disequilibrium in the ^{238}U series were identified by comparing the specific activities of subsequent nuclides, particularly ^{222}Rn daughter products to monitor potential Rn-loss (e.g., Krubetschek et al., 1994; Aitken, 1998; Kulig, 2005; Li et al., 2008). The cosmic dose rate was estimated according to the coordinates and altitude of the sample and the thickness of the sediment cover. The efficiency of the total dose rate was corrected according to the density of quartz and paleowater content for each sample (e.g., Aitken, 1998; Li et al., 2008). To estimate the paleowater content, we used the in situ water content values, and the results from water saturation analyses as a reference for seasonal and past variations in the water content. The generally dry conditions of the inner continental climate of the study area and the short water retention times of sandy sediment imply the predominance of low contents of paleowater, comparable to the measured in situ water content. An error of 10% is included to account for seasonal and site-related paleo-variations of the water content. All parameters for calculating the effective total dose rate were processed together with the estimated paleodoses for OSL age determination using ADELE software (Kulig, 2005).

3.3. Incision rate estimation

Derived OSL ages represent the age of the latest deposition of fluvial sand and therefore, maximum ages of terrace abandonment. The clear layering of the well-sorted sand, intercalated with pebble units, indicates that the fluvial transport capacity underwent rapid changes. Given the dynamic fluvial environment, we consider the OSL ages as close estimates of the onset of incision. Dividing the relative terrace heights above the present river by the OSL terrace age returns mean incision rates over the dated time range. Uncertainties of incision rates are calculated based on uncertainties of terrace height estimates, discrepancies in heights between the sampled sand layer and terrace surface, and for errors in the OSL ages.

3.4. Hack Index estimation

Calculated incision rates can only represent the response of the river at the location of the sampled terrace. To reveal the regional context of the local incision rates, we use the longitudinal profile of the Panj river and the Hack Index (Hack, 1973) and compare results to valley shape ratios (VSR; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Fuchs et al., 2013b). The longitudinal profile reveals the stage the modern river has reached in eroding towards the base level. Under steady state conditions, the profile can be represented by a logarithmic function of altitude and distance from the source, with constant stream power along

the course of the river (Hack, 1957, 1973). Deviations of the actual profile from the equilibrated river profile indicate the zones of changing controlling factors and/or stages of river adjustment (Hack, 1957, 1973; Pazzaglia et al., 1998; Snyder et al., 2000; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Demoulin, 2011).

The Hack Index is useful for locating and quantifying divergences from a non-perturbed river profile by relating the slope of a reach to the length of the upstream river (e.g., Hack, 1973; Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011b). Tectonic forcing can be inferred when convexities in the river profile do not correlate with lithologic contrasts and/or hydrological changes such as confluences with major tributaries (e.g., Hack, 1973; Demoulin, 1998, 2011; Burbank and Anderson, 2001). The extraction of the longitudinal river profile was carried out using the MATLAB based toolbox TecDEM (Shahzad and Gloaguen, 2011a,b) and a digital elevation model (ASTER GDEM, resolution 30 m). The Hack Index has been calculated for altitude intervals of 100 m along the extracted Panj profile. To reduce the effects of artifacts, we filtered out values where stream elevation was wrongly shown to increase downstream (carving) and smoothed the elevation data using a moving window of 300 m prior to Hack Index calculation.

4. Results

4.1. Dose rate estimates

Gamma spectrometric measurements revealed a trend of lower specific activities for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th downstream of the town of Khorog (TA31A - 23B) and higher values upstream of Khorog (Table 2). No radioactive disequilibrium was detected. The specific activity ^{40}K is high (> 10 times compared to ^{238}U or ^{232}Th) in most samples. The lowest contents of radionuclides in the sediment were determined in the terrace of the Vakhsh River (TA11A and B). Terrace altitudes and sediment cover imply that cosmic dose rates range between 154 mGy/kyr and 309 mGy/kyr. The in situ water contents of 0.1% to 3.7% of the sample weight reflect the dry summer sampling conditions. Saturation values of 26.4% to 46.1% allow the potential for higher paleowater content than measured but terrace heights above the modern river (> 4 m) and grain sizes of sampled sand units are assumed to limit such levels of saturation to short time intervals.

4.2. OSL signal characteristics

In general, the decay of the luminescence signals is slightly delayed in shine down curves but signal intensities are significant compared to the background level (BG) (Fig. 5, left). Early BG subtraction was not appropriate for the investigated samples as the very low remaining initial OSL signal (first second) resulted in higher curve fit errors. For most samples, low pre-heat temperatures (160 °C to 200 °C) and raised test doses yielded reliable equivalent

Table 2: Parameters for dose rate estimation: sediment-related dose rate (radionuclides ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K , sediment cover, water content) and cosmic dose rate (cosmD). Bold letters in sample names indicate notations used in the text.

Sample	Sediment			^{238}U [Bq/kg]	^{232}Th [Bq/kg]	^{40}K [Bq/kg]	cosmD [mGy/kyr]
	cover [cm]	water content					
		in situ [%]	saturation [%]				
TA090826A	50	0.2	26.4	69.1 ± 1.1	83.4 ± 3.3	1035.3 ± 9.1	302
TA090826C	50	0.2	33.8	47.2 ± 0.8	67.4 ± 2.7	780.6 ± 6.8	301
TA090825A	100	0.1	33.5	48.7 ± 0.8	92.7 ± 3.7	723.3 ± 6.2	308
TA090825B	100	0.2	30.9	59.2 ± 0.9	111.1 ± 4.4	1029.2 ± 9.1	299
TA100906A	500	2.4	29.9	50.1 ± 0.8	63.4 ± 2.5	700.5 ± 6.5	172
TA090827H	100	0.8	30.9	84.7 ± 1.4	101.8 ± 4.0	1226.3 ± 10.6	275
TA090828B	50	0.9	44.2	55.3 ± 0.9	66.4 ± 2.6	854.9 ± 7.8	291
TA090828D	50	1.3	29.4	89.8 ± 1.4	126.5 ± 5.0	1170.9 ± 10.3	291
TA090827E	100	1.6	41.7	60.2 ± 1.0	50.3 ± 2.0	1194.9 ± 10.1	272
TA090830C	100	3.2	46.1	55.9 ± 0.9	64.8 ± 2.6	855.9 ± 7.8	269
TA090831A	200	1.4	33.1	31.7 ± 0.5	32.4 ± 1.3	1299.5 ± 11.2	236
TA110831N	80	1.3	31.6	70.6 ± 3.0	91.9 ± 3.6	1325.4 ± 11.5	268
TA110831O	100	0.9	29.3	54.1 ± 0.9	59.1 ± 2.3	1288.3 ± 10.8	258
TA090902C	100	1.5	32.1	39.3 ± 0.6	64.1 ± 2.5	1048.0 ± 8.7	241
TA090908A	50	2.4	35.2	43.7 ± 0.7	58.6 ± 2.3	1036.0 ± 9.2	233
TA090923B	50	2.5	33.5	28.4 ± 0.5	36.3 ± 1.4	581.2 ± 5.5	225
TA090911A	50	3.7	31.7	25.0 ± 0.4	28.9 ± 1.1	623.1 ± 5.6	236
TA090911B	400	2.2	27.4	29.8 ± 0.5	29.6 ± 1.2	584.2 ± 5.5	154

Table 3: Results of OSL paleodose estimation for 4 mm and 2 mm aliquots using the arithmetic mean and the MAM (D_e : equivalent dose, MAM3: three parameter minimum age model (Galbraith et al. 1999), N: number of aliquots, sd: standard deviation, v_{DR} : coefficient of variation giving the deviation from the recovery dose in percent of the recovery dose, P_D : paleodose, bold values: used for age calculation. Bold letters in sample names indicate notations used in the text.

Sample	D_e (4 mm)				MAM3 P_D [Gy]	D_e (2 mm)			
	N	mean [Gy]	sd [%]	v_{DR} [%]		N	mean [Gy]	sd [%]	v_{DR} [%]
TA090826A	32	30.7 ± 1.8	33.5	5.7	28.2 ± 2.3	12	32.8 ± 3.5	37.3	27.0
TA090826C	59	100.7 ± 5.1	38.9	10.7	67.2 ± 7.4	15	71.3 ± 10.9	59.0	44.5
TA090825A	4	142.1 ± 3.0	4.2	-	-	10	108.3 ± 5.0	14.5	-
TA090825B	49	88.6 ± 2.8	22.3	5.4	69.3 ± 4.0	19	80.5 ± 3.0	16.1	12.2
TA100906A	57	118.9 ± 4.3	27.4	7.4	85.8 ± 6.1	-	-	-	-
TA090827H	27	35.4 ± 2.5	36.2	11.8	20.2 ± 3.1	20	28.5 ± 2.6	41.1	26.8
TA090828B	39	4.8 ± 0.3	41.3	11.1	3.1 ± 0.3	11	5.4 ± 0.7	41.8	6.8
TA090828D	58	24.6 ± 1.4	41.7	9.5	15.9 ± 1.8	18	22.9 ± 2.9	54.1	9.7
TA090827E	61	16.5 ± 1.0	47.9	18.8	7.8 ± 0.7	-	-	-	-
TA090830C	40	23.5 ± 1.1	28.2	11.2	18.3 ± 1.6	15	14.1 ± 0.9	25.5	17.3
TA090831A	50	94.6 ± 5.5	38.6	17.5	62.6 ± 8.3	13	64.3 ± 8.2	46.1	21.9
TA110831N^a	33	17.9 ± 1.4	45.3	11.5	17.7 ± 1.3	-	-	-	-
TA110831O	55	17.9 ± 1.7	69.1	10.6	12.9 ± 0.9	-	-	-	-
TA090902C	38	137.8 ± 6.7	30.1	10.2	96.2 ± 9.9	12	105.5 ± 14.0	46.0	34.5
TA090908A	26	68.7 ± 3.7	27.5	6.7	45.3 ± 5.1	20	62.3 ± 3.6	25.5	11.8
TA090923B	39	77.9 ± 2.6	21.1	6.7	69.6 ± 3.7	17	72.3 ± 5.2	29.8	6.5
TA090911A	20	21.6 ± 1.1	22.3	6.2	18.2 ± 1.6	20	21.2 ± 1.0	21.5	7.2
TA090911B	20	28.1 ± 0.7	11.1	6.4	25.1 ± 2.1	19	25.1 ± 1.3	22.1	9.4

^a instead of MAM3, the finite mixture model (FMM; Galbraith and Green 1990) is used to calculate the paleodose of the sample)

Figure 5: OSL signal characteristics. Results of 4 mm and 2 mm aliquots measured before and after adjusting the single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol parameters pre-heat, cut-heat and test dose from sample TA25B (left: shine down curve of natural signal, right: dose response curve, ph: pre-heat temperature, ch: cut-heat temperature, TD: test dose).

dose estimates (Fig. 5, right) and a reproducibility of v_{DR} 5% to 12% (Table 3). Only two samples show a low reproducibility with v_{DR} of 17% to 19% (TA27E and 31A).

Figure 6 (left) illustrates how lower equivalent dose errors and standard deviations were measured when using low temperatures and a higher a test dose (compare OSL1, OSL3 and OSL4 of TA25B, Fig. 6, top left). Low signal intensities increased dose response uncertainties for the 2 mm aliquots (Fig. 5, bottom) that was problematic especially for young samples. The 2 mm aliquots of TA27E yielded no equivalent dose due to inconsistent luminescence properties. The lower reproducibility in dose recovery tests of 2 mm aliquots (Table 3) did not allow for an improved detection of inhomogeneous bleaching. To allow direct comparisons paleodose was estimated on all samples using 4 mm aliquots. Sample TA25A was an exception due to limited material and so 2 mm aliquots had to be used. In this case, an overestimation of the age is possible as residual signals are not detectable or accounted for.

The dose distributions of all samples indicate differential bleaching. Standard deviations between 20% and 40% exceed the material-related variation (v_{DR}) by 10% to 20% (Table 3). For samples TA27E and TA31A, the low reproducibility of $v_{DR} > 15\%$ masks any indication of differential bleaching. However, the skewed distributions show arithmetic means above the median. Both param-

eters clearly overestimate the main data cluster indicated by the maximum kernel density estimates (cf. PDF in Fig. 6, right). To address the skewness in dose distributions, we apply the minimum age model, MAM (Galbraith et al., 1999).

4.3. OSL-based terrace ages

The OSL dating reveals maximum ages of terrace abandonment between (23.0 ± 2.9) kyr and (0.6 ± 0.1) kyr (Table 4). OSL age uncertainties range from 12% to 20%. The oldest terraces cluster with overlapping errors between 23.0 kyr and 19.0 kyr with an uncertainty of ± 2.9 kyr. This oldest generation is represented by four terraces between 191.0 m and 84.6 m in height above the modern river level (a.r.l.; Table 4). Four samples of the Panj river terraces are dated between 14.8 kyr and 9.1 kyr. Regarding the OSL age uncertainties, the age cluster overlaps with ages from older terraces but not with the ages of younger terraces along the Panj. Terrace heights range from 72.0 m a.r.l. to 57.8 m a.r.l., with the exception of one considerably lower terrace (TA26C: 24.9 m a.r.l.). The terraces older than 9 kyr are located at the southern and northern rim of the Shakh dara Dome and downstream of the Yazgulom Dome. The youngest terraces are found at the northern part of the Panj where it crosses the Shakh dara Dome and

Figure 6: Characteristics of equivalent dose distributions. Left: Comparison of applied measurement condition. Right: Statistical analyses of 4 mm aliquots for paleodose estimation (N: number of equivalent doses, sd: standard deviation, v_{DR} : coefficient of variation from dose recovery tests, ph: pre-heat temperature, ch: cut heat temperature, TD: test dose, PDF: probability density function, MAM: paleodose based on minimum age model).

further downstream before the confluence with the Bartang River from where six sampled terraces yielded OSL ages < 5 kyr with a maximum uncertainty of ± 0.7 kyr. Although most of the young terraces have ages between 2 kyr and 3 kyr, terrace heights vary considerably from 20 m to only 4 m. Two samples from the Vakhsh river date sand units of the same terrace from 0.5 m and 4.0 m below the surface. Using their age difference of 2.6 kyr a mean sedimentation rate of 1.35 m/kyr could be inferred. The terrace surface (~ 50 cm above sample TA11A) is estimated to be 5.9 kyr old, older than Panj terraces of comparable elevation above the modern river. However, age uncertainties overlap and, hence, could also be interpreted as fast

deposition of the entire uppermost fluvial layer of the terrace during 7.2–7.4 kyr. An average value (7.3 ± 1.5) kyr was used for comparisons.

4.4. Panj incision rates

The relationship between OSL ages and terrace heights is illustrated in Fig. 7. Our data show OSL age clusters that may evidence three phases of terrace sedimentation along the Panj. However, terrace heights are different for terraces of similar age. The resulting incision rates are therefore variable and range from (1.7 ± 0.3) mm/yr to (10.0 ± 2.0) mm/yr, independent of their association with one of the indicated age clusters. The solid black line

Table 4: OSL-based terrace ages and corresponding incision rates averaging over the time since deposition of the uppermost fluvial sand (P_D : paleodose, D: dose rate, m a.r.l.: meter above river level).

Sample	P_D [Gy]	D total [mGy/yr]	OSL age [kyr]	Terrace height [m a.r.l.]	Incision rate [mm/yr]
TA090826A	28.2 ± 2.3	5.9 ± 1.0	4.7 ± 0.7	13.0 ± 0.8	2.7 ± 0.6
TA090826C	67.2 ± 7.4	4.5 ± 0.7	14.8 ± 2.4	24.9 ± 0.3	1.7 ± 0.3
TA090825A	108.3 ± 5.0	4.8 ± 0.8	22.6 ± 2.8	191.0 ± 2.5	8.4 ± 1.2
TA090825B	69.3 ± 4.0	6.2 ± 1.0	11.2 ± 1.4	68.0 ± 2.5	6.1 ± 1.1
TA100906A	85.8 ± 6.1	3.9 ± 0.4	22.1 ± 2.9	151.0 ± 2.6	6.8 ± 1.0
TA090827H	20.2 ± 3.1	7.0 ± 1.2	2.8 ± 0.5	20.7 ± 0.1	7.3 ± 1.6
TA090828B	3.1 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.8	0.6 ± 0.1	6.3 ± 0.1	10.0 ± 2.0
TA090828D	15.9 ± 1.8	7.4 ± 1.2	2.2 ± 0.3	15.3 ± 0.1	7.1 ± 1.3
TA090827E	7.8 ± 0.7	5.7 ± 0.9	1.4 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.5	7.3 ± 2.2
TA090830C	18.3 ± 1.6	4.7 ± 0.8	3.9 ± 0.7	29.3 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 1.6
TA090831A	62.6 ± 8.3	5.2 ± 0.9	12.1 ± 2.1	72.0 ± 0.1	5.9 ± 1.1
TA110831N	17.7 ± 1.3	6.5 ± 1.1	2.7 ± 0.4	10.7 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 0.7
TA110831O	12.9 ± 0.9	5.6 ± 0.6	2.3 ± 0.3	4.1 ± 0.6	1.8 ± 0.5
TA090902C	96.2 ± 9.9	5.1 ± 0.5	19.0 ± 2.9	84.6 ± 0.1	4.5 ± 0.7
TA090908A	45.3 ± 5.1	5.0 ± 0.5	9.1 ± 1.6	57.8 ± 0.1	6.3 ± 1.1
TA090923B	69.6 ± 3.7	3.0 ± 0.3	23.0 ± 2.9	89.0 ± 2.5	3.9 ± 0.6
TA090911A	18.2 ± 1.6	2.9 ± 0.5	6.2 ± 1.2	21.2 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.7 ^a
TA090911B	25.1 ± 2.1	2.9 ± 0.3	8.8 ± 1.6	21.2 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.6 ^b

^a incision rate estimation based on terrace surface age of (5.9 ± 1.1) kyr inferred from the age and depth difference between the samples TA090911A and 11B from the same terrace of 350 cm and 2.6 kyr yielding a sedimentation rate of ~50 cm per 0.4 kyr)

^b incision rate estimation based on terrace surface age of (7.3 ± 1.5) kyr inferred from both samples from the same terrace with overlapping age errors of and assuming a fast deposition of the entire uppermost sand layer of the terrace

in Fig. 7 represents the linear regression for all investigated terraces (sample TA25A is not included because of differing paleodose estimation). An overall incision rate of 5.6 mm/yr is determined for the Panj. Deviations from the average incision rate (Table 4) at specific localities show no link to terrace ages. This suggests that local control factors have influenced the pattern of fluvial incision as opposed to temporal variation.

Values above the main regression line represent terraces that are located where the northward-deflected Panj cuts across the Shakhdara Dome and in the northern Panj, upstream (east) of the DFZ. Linear regression for all samples from the Shakhdara zone indicates a strong correlation between OSL ages and terrace heights, suggesting relatively constant incision over timescales of 10^3 yr to 10^4 yr with a mean rate of 7.3 mm/yr. In the north-central Shakhdara section, high incision rates of (7.1 ± 1.3) mm/yr to (10.0 ± 2.0) mm/yr are based solely on terraces younger than 5 kyr. Older terraces close to the northern and southern dome boundaries indicate that high incision rates of (5.9 ± 1.1) mm/yr to (8.4 ± 1.2) mm/yr have persisted over the last ~25 kyr. The sample TA08A east of the DFZ yielded the only incision rate (6.3 ± 1.1) mm/yr above the main regression line outside of the Shakhdara section.

Values below the regression line show variable incision rates between (1.7 ± 0.3) mm/yr and (4.5 ± 0.7) mm/yr. However, terraces north of the Shakhdara Dome (downstream of the confluence with the Gunt and Shakhdara rivers and further north, where the Panj turns to flow towards the northwest and west) also indicate a good correlation be-

tween OSL ages and terrace heights. The incision rates of the two youngest terraces range from 1.8 mm/yr to 3.9 mm/yr. These are located between the confluences with the Gunt and Shakhdara rivers and the southern rim of the Yazgulom Dome. The two 23- 19 kyr old terraces north of the Yazgulom Dome and further downstream show slightly higher incision rates of 3.9- 4.5 mm/yr (Table 4). The latter rates are similar to estimates from the Vakhsh River terrace that joins the Panj further downstream. Using the terrace surface age of ~5.9 kyr (cf. footnotes in Table 4, an incision rate of (3.6 ± 0.7) mm/yr is calculated. Regarding the overlapping errors of both ages, and assuming a terrace age of 7.3 kyr, the incision rate is (2.9 ± 0.6) mm/yr.

The lowest incision rates were determined for Panj terraces immediately upstream of where the river starts cutting through the Shakhdara Dome. Two terraces yielded incision rates of (1.7 ± 0.3) mm/yr and (2.7 ± 0.6) mm/yr. Two nearby terraces yielded much higher incision rates (cf. TA25A and B compared to TA26A and C with ~5 mm/yr, see Table 4). The contrast is especially apparent when comparing the low incision rate of sample TA26C to the similarly-aged sample TA25B from a separate terrace. The same applies to the < 5 kyr old sample TA26A when compared to samples from terraces of similar age from the north-central Shakhdara zone (e.g. TA30C, Fig. 7). The strongest contrasts in incision rates coincide with the southernmost deflection of the Panj, where the river crosses the SPSZ, and for terraces south and north of the GSZ.

Figure 7: Correlation between OSL ages and terrace heights. Indication of location-related incision rates along the Panj. Similar depositional ages are derived from terraces with varying heights above the modern Panj (solid black line: linear regression of all sampled terraces excluding TA090825A, blue dotted line: linear regression for samples from Panj reach cutting the Shakhudara Dome, green dotted line: linear regression for samples north of the Shakhudara Dome (north) excluding TA090908A, R^2 : correlation coefficient, mean incision: arithmetic mean of respective incision rates in mm/yr, m a.r.l.: meters above river level, SAD: Shakhudara-Alichur Dome, DFZ: Darvaz Fault Zone).

4.5. Geomorphometric analyses

The Panj has a non-equilibrated longitudinal river profile (Fig. 8). The fit of graded river profile segments (Fuchs et al., 2013b) suggests a composite river by detecting several local base levels in areas of low riverbed slope. The local base levels coincide with Panj reaches where it flows westward, parallel to the southern boundaries of the Shakhudara and Yazgulom domes. Downstream of the local base levels, northward-deflected reaches of the Panj display prominent convex profiles and increased riverbed slopes.

The deviations of the Panj profile from a graded river are expressed by the Hack Index (Fig. 8). The Hack Index highlights an abrupt increase in riverbed steepness directly upstream of the Wakhan confluence and corresponding base level at the southern boundary of the Shakhudara Dome. The second zone of high Hack Index corresponds

to a knickpoint downstream of the local base level at the southern boundary of the Yazgulom Dome. The Hack Index also indicates deviations from an equilibrated river downstream of the Vanj confluence. However, the transitional stage is difficult to evaluate because of uncertainties in the extracted river profile. Transitional stages of profile adjustment are further indicated by two zones of elevated Hack Index that coincide with convex profile zones, such as where the northward-deflected Panj cuts across the Shakhudara Dome.

5. Discussion

5.1. Effects of temporal averaging

The mean incision rates represent average conditions over the dated time interval. If the fluvial dynamic is disturbed by climatic, tectonic or hydrological forcing (e.g.

Figure 8: Longitudinal profile of the Panj. Summary of parameters for fluvial incision including OSL-based incision rates, modeled profiles of graded river segments and catchment area compared to river orientation and tectonic structures. Terrace heights and ages are given below the profile (kyr: thousand years, m a.s.l.: meters above sea level, VSR: valley shape ratio, SPSZ: Southern Pamir Shear Zone, GSZ: Gunt Shear Zone, RPS: Rushan-Psart Suture, TS: Tanymas Suture, KS: Kunlun Suture, DF: Darvaz Fault Zone). The longitudinal profile and VSR were modified after Fuchs et al. (2013b).

deglaciation, local uplift, river capture), fluvial response will depend on the magnitude frequency distribution of geomorphic events (Wolman and Miller, 1960). Incision rates from young terraces likely record the effects of high-frequency low-magnitude disturbances, while old terraces reveal conditions that likely average also over low-frequency high-magnitude disturbances.

We did not find increasing or decreasing incision rates over the last ~26 kyr although climatic conditions changed considerably since the last glaciation at the Pamir Plateau. Timescale independent incision is indicated by the correlation of heights and ages between terraces along the Shakh dara Dome and between terraces associated to westward river reaches. Determined rates also correspond to the long-term indication from the river profile and valley morphology. The consistency over timescales suggests no influence from the Sadler effect (Sadler, 1981). In other words, we use the hiatus in incision that is represented by local, brief sedimentation. This hiatus is of short duration compared to the averaged time interval of incision recorded in the studied terraces.

5.2. Role of climate on terrace formation

OSL ages of sampled terraces date the local deposition of fluvial sediments over the last 26 kyr along the Panj at the western Pamir margin. The dated time range spans the period since the last glacial advance during early MIS 2 on the Pamir Plateau (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The oldest dated terraces of (23 ± 2.9) kyr to (19 ± 2.9) kyr coincide exposure ages of moraines from the last glacial advance (cf. Fig. 2). Panj terraces with ages of (14.8 ± 2.4) kyr to (9.1 ± 1.6) kyr may correspond to minor re-advances or recessional glacial stages during the transition of MIS 2 and MIS 1 (cf. Fig. 2) reported by Röhringer et al. (2012).

Apart from these two cycles of contemporaneous deposition of fluvial sediments in the Panj valley and glacial sediments on the plateau, there is no further evidence of glacial cycles driving terrace aggregation. We did not find older terraces along the Panj that would coincide with the pre-MIS 2 glaciations on the plateau (Zech et al., 2005a; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The glacial advances during MIS 4 and earlier were more extensive and therefore probably had a greater impact on the river system. Fluvial sediments were either not deposited

in the Panj valley before MIS 2 or else have been removed by erosion. Alternatively, the long-lasting melting inferred from the MIS 3 hummocky moraines (Zech et al., 2005b) may have smoothened the effects of discharge and sediment transport and hence on terrace aggradation corresponding to glacial cycles before 23 kyr. In addition, during MIS 2 and MIS 2/1 there is little distinction between the two older terrace generations due to overlapping age errors. There is no evidence to suggest that deposition of the youngest terraces of < 5 kyr was coeval with a glacial event on the plateau. However, there is a lack of data on glacial advances since MIS 1 on the Pamir Plateau. The different timing of the Vakhsh terrace formation is attributed to the catchment north of the MPT, with no link to the glacial cycles on the Pamir Plateau.

Assuming climatic control on terrace formation would imply regionally consistent terraces ages and heights above the modern river. The older Panj terraces that are contemporaneous with glacial cycles are located close to confluences with tributaries draining the plateau or along reaches with a westward flow direction. In contrast, no terraces of comparable age to the glaciations (MIS 2 and MIS 2/1) were found in the widened valley at the confluence with Bartang River or at the junction with the Yazgulom River. The < 5 kyr terraces show no links to the Plateau glaciations as they are not located close to a westward-draining tributary. Furthermore, the lack of paired terraces, terrace staircases or thick fluvial deposits is not consistent with prolonged, regionally consistent periods of sedimentation. The considerable variation in the height of terraces above the modern Panj cannot be explained by regional climatic forcing alone.

5.3. Role of rock types, catchment geometry and tectonic structures

The OSL-based terrace incision rates correlate with location along the Panj rather than timing of terrace formation (Fig. 7). Local rates agree to the pattern shown in the river profile, Hack Index and VSR (Fig. 8). Accordingly, incision rates derived from terraces within the lowermost ~200 m of the valley are consistent with the long-term fluvial conditions recorded in stream gradient and valley morphology. Westward flowing reaches along southern dome boundaries show consistently low fluvial incision. Across the domes, incision shows high rates. The pattern fits with the idea of river capture across the Pamir domes that connect local base levels in westward reaches where the river corresponds to the predominant drainage orientation in Pamir.

A strong contrast in incision rates suggests a change in local conditions at the Shakh dara Dome, where the Panj turns to flow northwards (Fig. 8). Low incision rates of 1.4-3.3 mm/yr (including the uncertainty range) relate to the river flowing parallel to the SPSZ along the southern rim of the Shakh dara Dome. This river reach is characterized by wide valleys and low riverbed slopes. The graded river profile indicates a local base level at

2800 m a.s.l. (Fig. 8). All terraces along the reach crossing the Shakh dara Dome yield an average incision rate of 7.3 mm/yr (Fig. 7) that is high compared to the Panj average (5.6 mm/yr). The high rates are consistent between terraces with ages covering the last ~25 kyr. The intense fluvial incision corresponds to elevated Hack Indices and steepened valleys (Fig. 8). The abrupt change of fluvial incision parallel to and across the Shakh dara Dome suggests structural control, while rock type or catchment show no major changes. The change in fluvial response supports an assumed northward river capture across the Shakh dara Dome. In addition, the convex shape in the river profile may serve as an indication of relative uplift along active or re-activated dome-bounding faults.

Low incision rates of 1.3-4.6 mm/yr (including the uncertainty range) correspond to low Hack Indices north of the Shakh dara Dome. VSR reveal relatively steep valleys until the river deflects westward and the valley widens parallel to the Yazgulom Dome (Fig. 8). The Panj develops a concave profile that indicates a local base level at ~2000 m a.s.l. along the southern rim of the Yazgulom Dome (Fig. 8). The discharge increase at the confluences with the Gunt and Shakh dara rivers has not led to the development of a knickpoint in the river profile nor did that with the Bartang River. An influence from changes in rock types is not evident in the river profile. No terraces were found close to the main knickpoint in the Panj profile that coincides with the northward deflection at the Yazgulom Dome. Here, maximum values in both Hack Index and VSR suggest very high fluvial incision. Fuchs et al. (2013b) suggested that river capture linked the downstream reaches across the Yazgulom Dome.

Terraces downstream of the Yazgulom Dome reveal incision rates between 3.3 mm/yr and 5.2 mm/yr (including the uncertainty range) for the last ~26 kyr. These incision rates are similar to that determined for the Vakhsh terrace. The river profile indicates a transient stage and shows no major effects from different rock types or river catchment increases. High Hack Indices and low VSR suggest high river incision over the long-term. The slightly higher incision rate of (6.3 ± 1.1) mm/yr represents a terrace sampled upstream of the DFZ (Fig. 8), the fault zone that forms the western boundary of the Pamir.

6. Conclusion

OSL dating of 16 Panj terraces reveals temporal patterns in terrace sedimentation and spatial variations in incision rates along the northward-deflected Panj and its downstream reaches. Sedimentation along the Panj has been locally restricted and short-lived during the last ~26 kyr. The oldest terraces of (23.0 ± 2.9) kyr to (19.0 ± 2.9) kyr and those of (14.8 ± 2.4) kyr to (9.1 ± 1.6) kyr are located where west-flowing reaches of the Panj river system connect to the north-flowing trunk at the western Pamir margin. The timing of terrace formation coincides with glacial advance and possible re-advances on the Pamir Plateau

during early MIS 2 and the transition of MIS 2 to MIS 1. Such a link with glacial cycles was not found for terraces at the confluences between the Panj and the Bartang and Yazgulom rivers and for the young terraces of < 5 kyr. However, the timing of glacial cycles on the plateau is not sufficient to explain the considerable differences in terrace heights above the modern Panj for terraces of similar age.

The local incision rates yield an average of 5.6 mm/yr for the terraces along the Panj. Variations are consistent with spatial patterns in the river profile and valley morphology. Overall, the differences in incision rates do not correspond to changes in rock type or catchment increases. Instead, they appear to vary depending on the underlying structural unit of the Pamir through which the Panj cuts. Low incision rates of 1.4–3.3 mm/yr and 1.3–4.6 mm/yr were derived for the west-flowing reaches of the Panj, parallel to the southern boundaries of the Shakh dara and Yazgulom domes. Here, Hack Index and VSR values suggest a graded river that is approaching its local base level. The northward-deflected reach of the Panj crossing the Shakh dara Dome is characterized by an average incision rate of 7.3 mm/yr. The high incision rates during the last ~26 kyr are consistent with high Hack Indices and low VSR. The contrast in fluvial incision parallel to and across the Pamir domes supports the interpretation of northward river captures. Especially the coincidence of convex zones in the Panj profile with the location of Pamir domes may be explained by relative uplift along dome-bounding faults. Downstream of the Yazgulom Dome, fluvial incision of 3.3–5.2 mm/yr reflects a transient river reach. Rates are similar to that from the Vakhsh River terrace north of the Pamir. A terrace upstream of the DFZ indicates an increased river incision of (6.3 ± 1.1) mm/yr at the western boundary of the Pamir.

Acknowledgments

We are indebted to our friend and colleague M. Kr-betschek who left us abruptly in 2012. Matthias was, still is, the spirit of the OSL lab at TU Bergakademie Freiberg. We owe him the possibility for dating these very complex samples. We thank the DFG for funding our research associated with the TIPAGE project. We also thank the Academy of Science of Tajikistan for supporting our fieldwork in 2009. We used GMT (Wessel, P. and W. H. F. Smith, New, improved version of the Generic Mapping Tools released, EOS Trans. AGU, 79, 579, 1998), QGIS (<http://qgis.org/>) and the R environment (<http://www.r-project.org/>) for most of the topographic data processing and the resulting figures. Topographic and land cover data are based on ASTER GDEM and MODIS MCD12Q1 data products that were obtained through the online Data Pool at the NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC), located at the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center, Sioux Falls, South Dakota (https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/data_access).

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4.3 Implications on the pace of the drainage evolution

The OSL-based rates of fluvial incision provide the quantitative estimates that confirm the pattern outlined by geomorphometry in Paper I (chapter 2.2). Especially the terrace age-height relation demonstrates that fluvial incision is controlled by local conditions rather than climatic changes during the last ~ 26 kyr. Although the timing of terrace sedimentation suggests links to the early MIS 2 and MIS 1/2 glacial events at the Pamir Plateau reported by ??? there is no evidence that climate controls the variations of fluvial incision recorded along the Panj. As discussed in Paper I (chapter 2.2), local changes in rock type and drainage area are not plausible for explaining the variations in fluvial incision. Instead, OSL-based incision rates support geomorphometric indication of intensified fluvial incision across the structural domes and their bounding faults (cf. Paper I, chapter 2.2).

Incision rates of roughly 7-10 mm/yr and ~ 6 mm/yr identify fluvial incision above the Pamir average, where the Panj cuts through the Shakh dara Dome and where it flows across the Darvaz Fault Zone (DFZ), respectively. Lower incision rates of roughly 2-4 mm/yr correspond to river reaches parallel to the southern dome boundaries where the Panj resembles a graded river. The coincidence of high fluvial incision with northward river deflections of the Panj provide further arguments for the interpretation of river captures across the domes. The river captures imply a re-organization of the Pamir river network by connecting reaches of the predominantly east-west orientated drainage system and consequently, by changing the local base level of those reaches.

The Panj could not (yet) adjust to the perturbations of its fluvial dynamics caused by the river captures. The Panj longitudinal profile provides relative temporal constraints of successive upstream river captures (cf. Paper I, chapter 2.2), but the exact timing is not resolved. The fluvial terrace age of ~ 26 kyr gives a minimum estimate of the river capture across the Shakh dara Dome. Older fluvial terraces were not found or eroded. Also the lack of terrace material along the Panj, where it cuts through the Yazgulom Dome, prevents further interpretation of the degree of river adjustment and of related response times to the inferred river captures.

However, the fluvial incision of the Panj averages conditions not only in time, but also in space. It has to be noted that in downstream direction the fluvial incision responds to the conditions within an increasingly large area. The related increase in discharge may imply a reduced sensitivity to local conditions of downstream areas. Consequently, upstream reaches are more susceptible to variations in control factors, while downstream incision tends towards an averaged signal, or at least the already high discharge smoothens local differences in downstream reaches. Hence, the identification of distinct controlling factors remains obscured. For example, to the north the predominantly winter precipitation from the Westerlies causes peak discharge during the melting season. This efficient sediment transport mechanism is not represented by significantly higher incision rates.

Also differences in surface processes between the two main morphometric units, the Pamir Plateau and its margins, can not be constrained from the fluvial incision along the Panj alone. Hence, data from the major tributaries or their respective basins are needed and will be addressed in the following chapter that employs basin-wide erosion rates to differentiate further rates and control factors of landscape change in the Pamir (Paper V, chapter 5.2).

5 CN-based erosion rates in Pamir

5.1 Variability of erosion in Pamir

Erosion in Pamir is controlled by the efficiency of the Panj to incise and hence, to lower the local base level for its tributaries and hill slope adjustment. The OSL-based incision rates presented in Paper IV (chapter 4.2) record structural control and successive river captures at the western Pamir margin. But a large portion of the entire drainage basin extends across the Pamir Plateau to the east. The topographic cross sections and climatic gradients (Paper I, chapter 2.2) indicate clear differences in the conditions at the Pamir margins and its plateau. The pattern suggests changes in the factors that control the surface processes. In particular, variations in the predominantly east-west elongated sub-basins of the Panj are not resolved by the fluvial incision rates along the trunk stream. Also the influence of precipitation gradients and coverage of permanent snow and ice (cf. Paper I, chapter 2.2) are difficult to evaluate based on the fluvial incision rates of the Panj (cf. Paper IV, chapter 4.2 and discussion in chapter 4.3).

To derive further information on the variability of surface processes in the Pamir, Paper V (chapter 5.2) uses basin-wide erosion rates. Analyses of the factors driving the erosion in individual basins are based on:

- Characteristics of drainage basins
- Quantitative data on erosion variability in Pamir
- Discussion of factors explaining the variations in erosion rates
- Time scales of basin-wide erosion rates in Pamir

Analyses of the basin characteristics address the effects of topography and climate on erosion. The typical basin parameters can be compared to the quantitative estimates of basin-wide erosion. The relation of both, basin configuration and erosion is studied by means of regression analyses to elucidate the role of individual factors on explaining the variability of erosion in Pamir. Scale dependencies influence the representativity of basin-wide erosion rates. Hence, Paper V includes a discussion on spatial effects from averaging over different geomorphic domains and grain transport times through large basins as well as temporal effects with respect to paleo-climatic variations.

- **Paper V (chapter 5.2)**

Fuchs, M.C., Gloaguen, R., Merchel, S., Pohl, E., Sulaymonova, V., Andermann, C., Rugel, G. (in preparation): Variability of erosion rates across the Pamir identified based on ^{10}Be concentrations in modern river sediments.

5.2 Paper V: Variability of erosion rates across the Pamir identified based on ^{10}Be concentrations in modern river sediments

Millennial erosion rates across the Pamir based on ^{10}Be concentrations in fluvial sediments: Dominance of topographic over climatic factors

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Abstract

The understanding of erosion processes is fundamental to study the evolution of actively deforming mountain ranges, whereas the relative contributions tectonic and climatic factors and their feedbacks are debated. The Pamir is peculiar in both, high deformation rates induced by the India-Eurasia collision and its position at the transition between Westerlies and Monsoon. In order to contribute to this debate we quantify basin-wide erosion rates from cosmogenic ^{10}Be concentrations in modern river sediments measured by accelerator mass spectrometry. Sample locations represent the Panj basin at six sites along its trunk stream, and the major, east-west elongated tributary basins at five sites. An average erosion of ~ 0.64 mm/yr for the entire Pamir reveals a rapid landscape evolution. Erosion rates of tributary sub-basins highlight the strong contrast between the plateau (0.05 mm/yr to 0.16 mm/yr) and the Pamir margins (0.54 mm/yr to 1.45 mm/yr).

The intensity of erosion is primarily (R^2 of 0.81) correlated to slope steepness (0.75 quartiles) suggesting either tectonic uplift or base level lowering. Multiple linear regression reveals that precipitation may contribute also to the efficiency of erosion (R^2 of 0.93) to a lesser extent. Dry conditions and low slopes hinders sediment transport and consequently, erosion on the plateau. The highest erosion coincides with the predominant winter precipitation from the Westerlies. The concentrated discharge during spring and early summer favors pronounced erosion along the north-western Pamir margin by driving the sediment flux out of the basins. The magnitude of erosion in Pamir is similar to rates determined in the south Himalayan escarpment, whereas climatic and tectonic conditions are very different. Millennial erosion does not balance the roughly ten times higher fluvial incision implying a transient landscape. We propose that river captures are responsible for the strong base level drop driving the incision along the Panj and consequently, initiate steep hillslopes that will contribute to high erosion at the Pamir margins. Precipitation may act as limiting factor to hillslope adjustment and consequently to erosion processes.

Keywords: Pamir, erosion, denudation rates, cosmogenic nuclides, Beryllium-10, fluvial sediments

1. Introduction

Several recent studies with a focus on high mountains highlight the complexity of the interactions between tectonically triggered rock uplift and climate-driven processes, and their respective roles on erosion rates (e.g. Montgomery and Brandon, 2002; Burbank et al., 2003; Huntington et al., 2006; Godard et al., 2012, 2014). Spatial and temporal variations of erosion rates allow to constrain the specific factors that control mountain evolution (e.g. Molnar and England, 1990; Burbank and Anderson, 2001). But erosion in turn also affects tectonic processes for example by inducing a sediment flux out of the orogen and a mass loss that will be compensated by isostatic uplift (e.g. Molnar and England, 1990; Champagnac et al., 2009).

The peculiar tectonic and climatic setting of the Pamir provides the necessary conditions that allow to study erosion in response to variable drivers. The orogen lies at the westernmost part of the India-Asia collision zone, one of the Earth's largest and most rapidly deforming intra-continental convergence zone (e.g. Reigber et al., 2001; Mohadjer et al., 2010). This position coincides with the transition between the atmospheric circulation systems of the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) and the Westerlies, making this region particularly interesting when studying the role of climate in evolving mountains. However, the magnitude of erosion and the factors behind spatial and temporal variations are poorly constrained in the Pamir. So far, erosion was only studied in the context of the mainly Miocene dome exhumation in the southern Pamir. Stübner et al. (2013) inferred roughly 0.5 mm/yr from thermochronological modelling of the peak exhumation and geometric reconstructions of the Shakh dara Dome. Such long-term erosion integrates over variable climatic conditions during the Quaternary

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and cannot resolve spatial variations of the erosional response to climatic gradients or changes in uplift across the Pamir.

Regional studies of erosion rates in the India-Asia collision zone concerned mainly the southern escarpment of the Himalayas. Variations in erosion were found to correlate to long-term climate fluctuations that govern glacial processes (Gabet et al., 2008; Godard et al., 2012) and the intensity of the ISM (e.g. Bookhagen et al., 2005). Links between precipitation and erosion correspond also to regional relief characteristics that induce orographic effects (e.g. Garzanti et al., 2007; Gabet et al., 2008). Orographic rain shadow leads to a shift from precipitation- to temperature-sensitive erosion across the southern Himalayan escarpment resulting in an increased influence of concentrated peak discharge during the melting season on erosion (e.g. Burbank et al., 2012). Additionally, the availability of sediment to be transported (Burbank et al., 2012) and the magnitude-frequency distribution of direct runoff (Andermann et al., 2012) modulate rates of erosion. The generation of sediment and direct runoff are genetically linked to slope or relief as a consequence of base level lowering, hillslope thresholds or landslide frequency, factors that were found to control erosion (e.g. Montgomery and Brandon, 2002; Ouimet et al., 2009). In particular, the correlation between erosion and long-term tectonic uplift in the Greater Himalaya is debated as rates are suggested to adjust fast to climatic variations (Burbank et al., 2003; Godard et al., 2014).

The debated control factors outline the fact that measured erosion rates highly depend on the chosen method and the captured time interval (e.g. Garzanti et al., 2007; Lupker et al., 2012). The short-term variability in erosion rates of 10^1 to 10^2 years may be estimated using river sediment loads (Andermann et al., 2012), while depositional site studies or exhumation histories based on thermochronology may be associated to the long-term mass transfer over up to 10^6 years (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001; von Blanckenburg, 2005). In the case of mountain areas, high discharge variability and the mainly local, short-term character of depositional sites complicate the assessment of representative erosion rates. Cosmogenic nuclide (CN) techniques allow to quantify erosion rates representative of the average conditions in upstream areas (e.g. Brown et al., 1995; Bierman and Steig, 1996; Granger et al., 1996; Schaller et al., 2001; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). The production of CN in the Earth's surface implies that the CN concentration of the material removed from the surface inversely scales to erosion (Lal, 1991; Cerling and Craig, 1994; Bierman and Steig, 1996; Granger et al., 1996; Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Dunai, 2010). Measuring the concentration of CN in fluvial sediments then allows to infer basin-wide erosion rates that integrate over time scales of 10^2 - 10^4 years and deliver a reference of the "natural background" erosion (e.g. Kirchner et al., 2001; von Blanckenburg, 2005).

In this study, we aim at determining the magnitude of erosion in Pamir at the millennial time-scale and at identifying the factors that explain its variability. We analyze eleven samples of fluvial sediments from the active channels of the Panj river network. The locations selected for sampling allow us to resolve the spatial variations of basin-wide erosion rates for all major

sub-basins as well as record changes with increasing basin sizes along the trunk river. We measured the long-lived cosmogenic radionuclide ^{10}Be in the target mineral quartz by accelerator mass spectrometry at DREAMS (Akhmadaliev et al., 2013). For our calculation of production rates and shielding factors, we account for the topography of individual basins upstream of each sampling site. We apply a multiple linear regression analysis including geomorphic (altitude, relief, slope) and climatic (snow and ice cover, and precipitation) basin parameters to find the variables that explain variations in basin-wide erosion. Based on the best correlation and our own previous results, we discuss the variations of basin-wide erosion rates and the influence of spatial and temporal averaging.

2. Regional setting

2.1. Geological setting

The Pamir is located at the northwestern end of the India-Asia collision zone. The series of sutures, magmatic belts and crustal blocks are assumed to consist of along-strike equivalents of the Tibetan Plateau that accreted to the Eurasian plate during the Paleozoic to Mesozoic (e.g. Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Schwab et al., 2004; Cowgill, 2010; Bershaw et al., 2012). The main tectonic structures allow the distinction between three distinct terranes: the Northern, Central, and Southern Pamir (Burtman and Molnar, 1993; Schwab et al., 2004). The bulk of the Pamir comprises a steady-state elevated plateau of Cenozoic domes that cover up to 30% of the Pamir (Ducea et al., 2003; Schwab et al., 2004; Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2013). The structural domes (Fig. 1A) expose Cretaceous arc-type granitoids, mantled by lower-grade to non-metamorphic rocks (Schwab et al., 2004; Robinson, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2013). The northern Kurgovat Dome consists of high-grade metamorphosed Triassic rocks. The central Yazgulom, Sarez, Muskol, Shatput and the southern Shakh dara and Alichur Domes exhumed high-grade metamorphic rocks of Oligocene to Miocene ages with peak exhumation at ~ 15 Myr (Schmidt et al., 2011; Stübner et al., 2013).

The active frontal range of Pamir bends nearly 180° from northern Afghanistan to western China (Bershaw et al., 2012). Neotectonic activity is governed by the northward propagation of the Indian plate inducing east-west striking mountain ranges. Crustal shortening is mainly accommodated at the Main Pamir Thrust (MPT) by subduction beneath the frontal part of the orogen where most of the seismicity occurs (e.g. Koulakov and Sobolev, 2006; Schneider et al., 2013; Sippl et al., 2013). Recently published shortening rates reach 10 - 15 mm/yr across the MPT (Ischuk et al., 2013). The lateral margins of the orocline display strike-slip motion of ~ 12 mm/yr along the western Darvaz Fault Zone (DFZ) (Trifonov, 1978; Mohadjer et al., 2010) and < 1 mm/yr along the eastern Karakoram Fault Zone (KFZ) (Strecker et al., 1995). The Southern Pamir Shear Zone (SPSZ) delineates the Pamir to the south from the Hindu Kush. This major east-west, low-angle normal fault comprises the southern boundary of the giant Shakh dara Dome. Plateau-internal neotectonic seismicity is related to the gravity driven collapse

Figure 1: Regional setting of the Panj river system and sample locations (CN: cosmogenic nuclide, a.s.l.: above sea level). A: Topography and main tectonic structures (DFZ: Darvaz Fault Zone, MPT: Main Pamir Thrust, KS: Kunlun Suture, TS: Tanyamas Suture, RPS: Rushan-Psart Suture, GSZ: Gunt Shear Zone, SPSZ: Southern Pamir Shear Zone, KD: Kurgovat Dome, YD: Yazgulom Dome, SAD: Shakhdara and Alichur Dome, modified after e.g., Schwab et al., 2004; Stübner et al., 2013). B: Sample locations along the Panj and major tributaries (1: Shakhdara, 2: Gunt, 3: Bartang, 4: Yazgulom, 5: Vanj, 6: Shiva, 7: Vakhsh, 8: Wakhan) and related drainage basins. The climate is shown by the distribution of annual precipitation (TRMM 3B42 V7, 1998-2012, Huffman et al., 1997, 2007) and permanent snow and ice cover (MODIS MCD12Q1, Strahler et al., 1999, year 2010).

of the Plateau and the induced east-west extension and conjugated strike-slip (Fan et al., 1994; Strecker et al., 1995; Sippel et al., 2013)

2.2. Climatic setting

The setting of the Pamir at the transition between the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) makes the region highly sensitive to variations in atmospheric circulation patterns. Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) spatial product 3B42 V7 (Huffman et al., 1997, 2007) reveals strong variations of annual precipitations (mean 1998 - 2012) from almost nil to more than 500 mm in Pamir (Fig. 1B). The Westerlies supply precipitation during winter and spring to the north-western Pamir margins. The precipitation from the south during the ISM strongly attenuates over the Hindu Kush and Karakoram Range. The central Pamir receives very little annual precipitation, mainly in form of snow. The westward increase of permanent snow and ice cover (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer, MCD12Q1, version 057, 2010, Strahler et al. (1999)) illustrates the superimposition of concentrated precipitation at the Pamir margins and low temperature due to high altitudes (Fig. 1B).

The efficiency of glacial processes on erosion is highly debated (Norton et al., 2010; Godard et al., 2012, e.g.), which, dependent on the averaging time of erosion rates, requires precise knowledge on temporal fluctuations of glacial extents. Glacial remnants attest for significant climatic variations during the Late Quaternary on the Pamir Plateau. Successively less extensive glacial advances correspond to an increasing aridity in Central Asia (Zech et al., 2005; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer

et al., 2012). Beryllium-10-based dating of moraines on the Pamir Plateau puts the most extensive glaciation during the marine isotope stage (MIS) 4 or earlier, during MIS 5 to MIS 6. The glaciers of this most extensive glacial advance reached the inner-plateau valley floors 136 - 93 kyr and 86 - 60 kyr ago. A potential ISM driven MIS 3 advance related to hummocky moraines is ambiguous due to high age scatter. Two less extensive advances are dated at 30 - 27 kyr (MIS 3/MIS 2) and 24 - 22 kyr (MIS 2). Younger glacial sediments are associated to deglaciation or minor re-advances.

3. Material and methods

3.1. Beryllium-10-based modern erosion rates

Beryllium-10 concentrations in modern fluvial sediments scale to the rate of landscape lowering by weathering and physical erosion and average the time of exposure to cosmic ray interaction in rock surfaces (von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). The generally dry conditions in Pamir (Fig. 1) suggest weathering to be of less importance in the total erosion budget. In this case, landscape lowering is dominated by the physical material removal at the landscape's surface, which means that denudation rates narrow down to erosion rates (e.g. Dunai, 2010), and it may be convenient to use both terms interchangeably in the following.

The relation between the ^{10}Be concentration in a target mineral and modern erosion rates is based on the fact that the nuclide is produced by cosmic rays at rock surfaces within a rock-characteristic attenuation depth, while material removal brings constantly new material from shielded depth to the surface (Lal,

1991; Brown et al., 1995; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). Being highest at the rock surface, the ^{10}Be production decreases approximately exponentially with depth (Lal, 1991; Dunne et al., 1999; Braucher et al., 2011). The mean attenuation path length z^* of cosmic rays into rocks depends on the attenuation coefficient of the nucleonic component ($\sim 160 \text{ g/cm}^2$) and the rock density (e.g. Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Balco et al., 2008) of the bulk, often polymineral material. Accordingly, in silicate rocks z^* is typically $\sim 60 \text{ cm}$ (Lal, 1991; von Blanckenburg, 2005). The ^{10}Be concentration C is then proportional to the time the mineral grains reside within z^* until being removed from the surface. Consequently, C is inversely proportional to the erosion rate ε (Lal, 1991; Brown et al., 1995; von Blanckenburg, 2005). This relation can be described by:

$$\varepsilon = \left(\frac{P}{C} - \lambda \right) * z^* \quad (1)$$

where λ is the decay constant of the nuclide and P its production rate. For λ we used the ^{10}Be half-life of $(1.387 \pm 0.012) \text{ Ma}$ (Korschinek et al., 2010). The parameter z^* may be treated as a constant when determining basin-wide erosion rates that averages over local variations in rock densities affecting the attenuation path length. The central estimates required for solving the equation are the ^{10}Be concentration of the sample and the rate of nuclide production at the corresponding location (details given in sections 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4). The equation is valid under steady-state conditions of ^{10}Be production and material removal at the surface. This implies constant conditions over a period that is long compared to the averaging time T_{ave} , the time it takes to erode z^* and hence, to remove the ‘cosmogenic memory’ of the material (Brown et al., 1995; Bierman and Steig, 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010).

Assuming uniform erodibility, mineral composition and grain size release of the eroding rock surface, erosion rates represent averages for all upstream surfaces at the basin scale (Bierman and Steig, 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Carretier et al., 2009). Well mixed sediment representative of all process domains within the basin require sample basins large enough to minimize the influence of single and only local processes (e.g. von Blanckenburg, 2005). Although large basins imply longer grain travel times, nuclide concentrations revealed negligible increases compared to the concentration already acquired at their initial position in non-aggrading basins (Carretier et al., 2009).

3.2. Sampling strategy

We sampled 11 locations of the Panj river network (Fig. 1B). Five sampling sites represent the increasing basin along the trunk river reach of the Panj until it crosses the DFZ. Three major tributaries (Gunt, Bartang and Vanj River, Fig. 1B) were sampled near their confluence with the Panj and three additional sites were selected to represent upstream sub-basins. Difficulties to find suitable sites of modern fluvial sediments arose from the high stream power of the Panj that limits the deposition of sand in Pamir.

To ensure complete mixing of sediment grains that are representative for all upstream source areas, we chose locations

before confluences as far as possible from upstream tributaries. Locations have been avoided where slope failure or fan sedimentation from minor tributaries indicated local perturbations. We sampled directly the uppermost 1-3 cm of the sediment in the active river channel. All samples consisted of predominantly sand-sized, quartz-rich polymineral material. Sufficient material for quartz and subsequent ^{10}Be extraction was addressed by collecting 3-5 kg of fluvial sediment per sample.

3.3. Sample preparation and ^{10}Be measurements

The polymineral sediment samples required quartz enrichment before starting chemical cleaning and ^{10}Be extraction. To narrow the grain size fraction, we first sieved the samples to 250-500 μm and 500-1000 μm , and focussed on the 250-500 μm fraction. For two samples (TA28C and TA30P) only the coarser fraction yielded sufficient material. After magnetic separation and ultrasonic bath, we cleaned the quartz with a 1:1 solution of HCl (32 %) and H_2SiF_6 (34 %) (Brown et al., 1991). Inspection of the sample’s mineral composition under the binocular revealed relatively high proportions of feldspars (up to 50 %) for most of our samples, even after repeating the partial dissolution for six cycles. Feldspars cause bias in quartz results due to differing rates of ^{10}Be production. Additionally, the lower chemical resistance compared to quartz as well as high aluminum contents affect chemical procedures. This motivated us to introduce a standard feldspar flotation (Herber, 1969) to further enrich the quartz fraction. The feldspar flotation was carried out in a solution of 0.2 % HF and pH of 2.4-2.7 to activate feldspar adherence to bubbles using the foam agent dodecylamine.

The BeO separation followed the procedures by Merchel and Herpers (1999). Atmospheric ^{10}Be was removed by dissolving 30 % of the extracted quartz fraction with 48 % HF during three cycles. After the addition of about 300 μg of a ^9Be carrier (Phena DD, $(3.025 \pm 0.009) \times 10^{-3} \text{ } ^9\text{Be/g}$, Merchel et al., 2008), samples were totally dissolved using 48 % HF. The Be extraction from the dissolved quartz included repeated hydroxide precipitation by NH_3 aq, anion and cation exchanges. For high Ti-containing samples, Ti was diminished by precipitation of $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_4$ before ignition of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ to BeO. Then, target preparation involved adding Nb (six times of the dry oxide weight). AMS measurements were conducted at DREAMS (DREsden AMS, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, 6 MV, Cu cathode) using the in-house standard SMD-Be-12 (Akhmadaliev et al., 2013) normalized against the NIST SRM 4325 standard ($^{10}\text{Be}/^9\text{Be}$ ratio of $(2.79 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-11}$, Nishizumi et al., 2007). A round-robin exercise of AMS facilities confirmed robust standard calibration and measurement configuration (Merchel et al., 2012). Processing blanks were treated and measured parallel to the sediment samples. The blank isotope ratios in the order of 0.3 % to 1.7 % ($^{10}\text{Be}/^9\text{Be}$ ratio of 1.933×10^{-15} and 2.133×10^{-15}) were subtracted from the measured ratios of all samples.

3.4. Production rates and shielding factor

The production of ^{10}Be in quartz is primarily dependent on the cosmogenic particle flux from nucleons and muons (Lal,

1991; Granger and Muzikar, 2001) as a function of the geomagnetic field, altitude and shielding (Lal, 1991; Brown et al., 1995; Bierman and Steig, 1996; Stone, 2000; Gosse and Phillips, 2001). Accounting for the location-specific modulation, reference sea level and high latitude (SLHL) production rates need to be scaled to the conditions at the site of sampling. In the case of fluvial sediment samples, the cosmogenic nuclide inventory was acquired in source areas of the sediment upstream of the sampled site (e.g. Brown et al., 1995; Bierman and Steig, 1996; Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005). Consequently, the calculation of representative production rates requires attention to the hypsometry of the whole basin (von Blanckenburg, 2005; Norton and Vanacker, 2009; Dunai, 2010).

Representative values for the ^{10}Be production rate and shielding of individual sample basins requires the identification of the upstream area for each sampling site. The drainage area calculation included basic data processing of a ASTER GDEM of 30 m resolution (NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center) for flow directions, accumulation area and stream segments (QGIS Development Team, 2010; GRASS Development Team, 2012). Assuming total shielding by permanent ice and snow cover, we excluded respective areas from further calculations of ^{10}Be production rates. The areas of permanent snow and ice cover are based on MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer) Land Cover Type data MCD12Q1 (Strahler et al., 1999) and the classification scheme according to the IGBP (International Geosphere Biosphere Program). The available data covers the years 2000–2012. For our calculations, we use the year 2010 that is among those with most extensive snow and ice cover. The area upstream of the Lake Yashilkul was not included into basin analyses as a large landslide dams the plateau discharge and sediment flux. The dam is assumed to have been in place for several 10^4 years (Zech et al., 2005; Brookfield, 2008).

For each sampled basin, we then calculated ^{10}Be production rates from neutrons, and fast and stopped muons by raster cell-resolved scaling of a SLHL reference according to (Stone, 2000). We used the SLHL production rate of 4.5 at/g quartz/yr (cf. Balco et al. 2008 along with the half-life of ^{10}Be of $(1.387 \pm 0.012) \times 10^6$ years, Korschinek et al. 2010) and the attenuation parameters according to Braucher et al. (2003) and Sime et al. (2004).

Topographic shielding plays an important role in high relief terrain (Dunne et al., 1999) as steep slopes reduce the exposure to the cosmic particle flux (e.g. Gosse and Phillips, 2001; Codilean, 2006; Norton and Vanacker, 2009). Shielding from other sources is considered negligible as glaciated areas are excluded from production rate calculation and vegetation is scarce due to the dry climate and high basin altitudes. The shielding factor was estimated for each GDEM raster cell based on the horizon line within a 10 km distance according to the method of Codilean (2006). Norton and Vanacker (2009) found only low underestimation of shielding when using a DEM of 30 m resolution in steep terrain.

The raster-cell resolved production rates and shielding factors of each sampled basin show non-normal, skewed to poly-modal distributions due to topographic variations. We use the

arithmetic mean to represent the conditions within the basins. Uncertainties are calculated based on the standard variation to refer to the high value variability within basins. The uncertainties of erosion rates refer to the sum of errors from AMS measurements of the ^{10}Be concentration, and the variation of production rates and shielding.

3.5. Sample basin parameters

Basin-wide denudation rates have been found to correlate with altitude, slope, relief, precipitation or glaciated area (e.g. Schaller et al., 2001; Montgomery and Brandon, 2002; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Norton et al., 2010). We describe the sampled basins in Pamir by probability density estimates of altitude, slope and precipitation (TRMM product 3B42 V7) using the R programming environment (R Core Team, 2013). The median, 0.25 and 0.75 quartiles of each parameter serve for (multiple-) linear regression analyses to infer the importance of individual parameters for explaining the variations in erosion. We examine the influence of glacial processes using the proportion of permanent snow and ice cover in sampled basins. From the MODIS data of the year 2010 (see above), we calculate the area covered by snow and ice proportional to the basin size.

We characterize the relief of each sample basin using the altitude difference at different scales. The basin relief determines the overall altitude difference within sampled basins. We calculate the basin relief using the difference between the 0.75 and 0.25 quartiles of basin altitudes, to compensate for the bias towards highest relief for largest basins. The local relief represents altitude differences normalized to a given area. We use a moving window of 1 km and 4 km width to analyze the GDEM data and determine the relation between relief and erosion at the sub-basin scale. A smaller window size narrows relief estimates down to slope, a wider window size produces trends of basin relief.

4. Results

4.1. Sample basin properties

The basins of the southern Panj and of the major Panj tributaries show strong east-west elongations (Fig. 1B). The basin elongation allow to integrate gradients from the Pamir Plateau to its western margin, while their parallel configuration enables to resolve south-north changes in controlling factors. The trunk reach connects tributary outlets from south to north close to the western drainage divide of the entire investigated Panj basin. The median basin altitudes gently decrease from 4800 to 4200 m a.s.l. along the course of the Panj (cf. Fig. 1). The minimum altitudes representing the river bed sharply drop from 3600 to 700 m a.s.l. (Tab. 1) and reveal the downstream (northward) increase in total altitude differences for larger basins. The strong decrease of minimum altitudes witnesses strong incision at the Pamir margins.

On the plateau, altitudes cluster between 3800 m a.s.l. and 5000 m a.s.l. with significantly less frequent lower altitudes (Fig. 2A, bottom). The basins of the southern Panj are slightly higher compared to those at the western Pamir margin. A strong

Figure 2: Frequency distributions of altitude (A), slope (B) and precipitation (C) for individual sample basins grouped due to their location at the southern or western margin of Pamir or at the Pamir Plateau. Relative frequencies of altitude and slope were calculated from a ASTER GDEM of 30 m resolution and precipitation from the TRMM product 3B42 V7 (Huffman et al., 1997, 2007) (notation of basins refers to bold fonts used for sample names in Fig. 1 and Tab. 1).

drop in altitude frequencies delineates the Pamir Plateau from its margins (Fig. 2A). The main frequency contrast occurs at ~ 3800 m a.s.l. at the southern Pamir margin and less sharply at ~ 3600 m a.s.l. at the the western margin. Two minor peaks at ~ 3300 m a.s.l. and ~ 2800 m a.s.l. indicate local base levels below the Pamir Plateau (cf. Fig. 2A, top) in the southern Panj basins. The local base levels are masked in western Pamir basins by the increasing basin size. The Vanj basin (TA02A) stands out by its high proportion of margin-related altitudes indicating low influence from plateau-related areas.

The relative proportions of slopes within basins correspond to respective altitude distributions. Highly variable slopes display strongly bimodal distributions in the east-west elongated basins that range over plateau and marginal basin portions (Fig. 2B, middle). The narrow peak of slope frequencies below 5° scales with the plateau-related, very flat basin portions between 4000 m and 5000 m a.s.l. (cf. upper Bartang, TA08N, Fig. 2B, bottom). Such areas are less extensive in the southern Panj basins that contour the Pamir at its southern margin (Fig. 2B, top). The second, much broader frequency peak in-

dicates hillslopes to cluster at roughly 35° . The Vanj basin (TA02A, Fig. 2, center) stands out with a negatively skewed slope distribution and maximum frequencies at $\sim 40^\circ$. Although draining the Plateau, the Shakh dara basin (TA30P, Fig. 2B, bottom) displays a broad slope distribution with a plateau of high frequencies between 10° and 30° that suggests a transient position of the basin located on the edge of Pamir Plateau.

Areas of permanent ice and snow cover reflect the predominant moisture supply from the northwest and south, and evidence the aridity of the central-eastern parts of Pamir (Fig. 1B). The Pamir basins are very heterogeneously affected by ice and snow. The largest coverage of permanent ice and snow cover show the small basin of an upper Panj (Pamir River) tributary (TA23P, 55%) and the northernmost basin of the Vanj River (TA02A, 37%). In contrast, only 5% of the upper Bartang (TA08N) basin at the eastern plateau are permanently covered by snow and ice (Tab. 1). A similar picture can be drawn from the median of TRMM-based mean annual precipitation (1998 - 2012). The largest basins TA23A and TA08B indicate a regional average of ~ 300 mm/yr. Variations in precipitation are

Table 1: Details on sampling sites and related upstream drainage area (sample basin). Ice: Permanent ice and snow cover based on the year 2010 from MODIS MCD12Q1 (Strahler et al., 1999), the given uncertainty represents the standard deviation of MODIS MCD12Q1 between 1998 and 2012. Altitude, slope and precipitation represent the median of the value distribution within sampled basins (see Fig. 2) calculated from the ASTER GDEM (30 m resolution). The rainfall data reflects the annual mean precipitation based on the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) product 3B42 V7, 1998-2012 (Huffman et al., 1997, 2007). Bold letters in sample names indicate notations used in the text and figures.

Sample	River	Location			Sample basin				
		Lon [°E]	Lat [°N]	Altitude [m a.s.l.]	Area [km ²]	Ice [%]	Altitude [m a.s.l.]	Slope [°]	TRMM [mm/yr]
<i>Panj:</i>									
TA090923A	Panj	70.177	37.901	731	71727	16.3 ± 2.9	4213	24.3	316
TA090908B	Panj	70.787	38.456	1220	67749	17.1 ± 3.0	4255	24.1	309
<i>Vanj:</i>									
TA090902A	Vanj	71.378	38.293	1551	2079	37.0 ± 6.5	3869	31.4	364
<i>Bartang:</i>									
TA090901C	Bartang	71.610	37.490	2030	29243	13.6 ± 2.4	4351	21.4	239
TA110808N	Aksu	73.965	38.161	3603	13548	4.0 ± 0.7	4283	14.5	176
<i>Gunt:</i>									
TA090831B	Gunt	71.527	37.490	2078	8437	18.7 ± 3.3	4294	23.3	376
TA110830P	Shakhdara	71.845	37.210	2785	3507	13.5 ± 2.4	4281	20.8	390
<i>southern Panj:</i>									
TA090828C	Panj	71.460	37.220	2275	15230	26.1 ± 4.6	4519	23.8	298
TA090825C	Panj	71.596	36.730	2491	13625	28.2 ± 4.9	4574	23.2	290
TA110824O	Panj	72.206	36.929	2754	11064	29.2 ± 5.1	4591	21.6	272
TA110823P	(Pamir)	72.737	37.173	3552	84	55.1 ± 9.6	4770	25.6	321

mainly controlled by orographic gradients of the predominant atmospheric circulations.

4.2. Erosion rate parameters

The ¹⁰Be concentrations show a high variability between sample basins (Tab. 2). Nuclide concentrations are comparable (5.7 - 7.6 at/g) along the Panj and do not show any trend from upstream, smaller basins towards downstream basins of largest size. The tributary basins display a northward decrease in concentrations (TA31B, TA01C, TA02A) but the east-west elongated basins cause averaging of plateau-related and marginal basin portions. Especially concentrations measured for the Bartang basin (TA01C) is affected by including the upstream basin (TA08N) of highest ¹⁰Be concentrations of (98.5 ± 2.1) at/g, while the downstream basin portion can be assumed to contribute very low concentrations to the sediment mix. Similarly, the Gunt basin (TA31B) comprises also the conditions in the Shakhdara River sub-basin (TA30P) that has two times the concentration found in the entire Gunt basin. The Vanj basin (TA02A) yields the lowest concentration with (1.9 ± 0.1) at/g.

Estimated production rates of ¹⁰Be (cf. ¹⁰Be production rates due to neutrons in Fig. 3, top) correspond to the basin topography with one prominent maximum at ~80 at/g/yr. Increased altitude variations at the western Pamir margin cause skewed distributions. Excluding areas covered by snow and ice lowers production rates in systematic manner, modulated by the amount of precipitation (Fig. 4A). The limited snow and ice coverage at the eastern plateau affects production rates less compared to the more extensive coverage in the northwestern marginal basins. The high proportion of snow and ice covered areas in northwestern Pamir basins implies discarding mainly high elevated areas prone to high production rates as most evident for the Vanj basin (TA02A). The effect amounts to less than 10 % for all sample basins but TA23P and TA02A with up to 20 %

lower values. Erosion rates corrected for the basins proportion of snow and ice cover display an exponential relation with AMS-based ¹⁰Be concentrations (Fig. 4B) as an expression of the attenuation of cosmic rays in rock surfaces.

Topographic shielding factors range from roughly 0.8 to 1.0 with a narrow and a wide maximum in frequencies (Fig. 3, bottom) that mimic the distribution of slopes. The correction of production rates according to the basin's topographic shielding factors enhance differences between basins. Low altitude areas commonly relate to marginal Pamir basins that are more shielded by steep slopes than plateau-related basins with a high proportion of altitudes above 3600 m a.s.l. and large areas of slopes <5 %. Consequently, elevated central and eastern basin portions deliver sediments of high ¹⁰Be concentrations (e.g., TA08N) to the river channels due to high production and low shielding. Lowest production rates occur within north-western basins (e.g. TA02A) due to both, high topographic shielding and high snow and ice cover. The rates of nuclide production (Tab. 2) are similar, with only ~9 % variability for plateau-related basins (TA08N and TA30P) and those of the southern Panj basins (TA23P, TA24O, TA25C and TA28C). The shielding corrected production rates in tributary basins indicate a slight decrease (Fig. 4C) corresponding to northward lower altitudes and steepened topography.

4.3. Basin-wide erosion rates

The two largest basins (TA23A and TA08B) reveal a high average erosion for the entire Pamir with ~0.64 mm/yr (Fig. 5). Erosion rates determined along the Panj resemble the average conditions and stay relatively consistent despite significant changes in basin sizes. Minor variations indicate a slight, westward decrease in erosion with increasing size of the southern Panj basins. The erosion rate of (0.79 ± 0.19) mm/yr for the eastern, upper Panj (TA23P, small Pamir River tributary) low-

Figure 3: Spatial variations of ^{10}Be production rates and topographic shielding according to the hypsometry of the Pamir, and individual frequency distributions of production and shielding within sampled basins (cf. Figs. 1 and 2). As an example of the spatially variable production, rates are given for the neutron induced ^{10}Be built-up (CN: cosmogenic nuclide, color code for CN sample locations in map refers to individual basins in the legend of frequency distribution plots: reddish: southern Pamir margin, greenish: western Pamir margin, blueish: plateau-related basins, cf. Fig. 1; notation of basins refers to bold fonts used for sample names in Fig. 1 and Tab. 1).

ers to (0.58 ± 0.18) mm/yr for the entire southern Panj basin before the river course deflects to the north. The erosion rates rapidly increases downstream to (0.74 ± 0.24) mm/yr despite a relatively modest increase of drainage ($\sim 13\%$).

The major tributaries of the Panj (Gunt, Bartang, Vanj) reveal strong contrasts in erosion across the Pamir ranging from (0.05 ± 0.01) mm/yr to (1.45 ± 0.56) mm/yr (Tab. 2). The pattern of erosion illustrates increasing rates from the south-eastern central plateau towards the north-western margins. Two upstream sub-basins determine low erosion on the Pamir Plateau with (0.05 ± 0.01) mm/yr for the easternmost inner plateau (TA08N) and (0.16 ± 0.05) mm/yr for the south-western Shakh dara basin (TA30P). The morphometry of those plateau-related areas is characterized by the predominance of altitudes above 3600 m a.s.l. and large areas of slopes below 5° (cf. Tab. 2). Erosion rates determined immediately before the confluence with the Panj show a northward increase from ~ 0.37 mm/yr to 1.45 mm/yr in major tributary basins (Gunt,

Bartang, Vanj). Rates of the elongated Gunt (TA31B) and Bartang (TA01C) basins integrate the low erosion of upstream plateau-related sub-basins (TA08N and TA30P). Consequently, erosion in downstream basin portions across the Pamir margin lies above the basin-wide average. The differentiation of high erosion in marginal sub-basins fits to the erosion rate of (1.45 ± 0.56) mm/yr for the Vanj basin (TA02A) that reflects conditions at the northwestern Pamir margin without significant portions of the typically flat, plateau-related basins.

We estimate the erosion rates of the lower portions of the Gunt (GUNT) and the Bartang (BARlow) by relating rates of the upstream basin area for which we have data to those of the entire basins. We scaled the erosion rates by their relative area as a simple approximation. The average erosion rate for the entire basin (ϵ_{total}) represents the sum of area-weighted erosion rates in its upper and lower sub-basins (up and $down$) by

$$\epsilon_{total} = a * \epsilon_{up} + (1 - a) * \epsilon_{down} \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: Relationship between basin-wide erosion rates and respective parameters used for calculations and corrections. A: Erosion rates with and without correction for areas covered by permanent snow and ice. B: Exponential relation between erosion and ^{10}Be concentrations from AMS measurements. C: Low variability of production rates corrected for topographic shielding (color code refers to individual basins in the legend, reddish: southern Pamir margin, greenish: western Pamir margin, blueish: plateau-related basins, cf. Fig. 1; notation of basins refers to bold fonts used for sample names in Fig. 1 and Tab. 1, shaded areas provide a quick demarcation of margin or plateau-related samples, the sample TA01C between the two units illustrates the integration of both, marginal and plateau-related portions).

Table 2: Parameters and results of erosion rate calculation. AMS measurements were performed at DREAMS, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf. The ^{10}Be concentrations are corrected for processing blanks ($^{10}\text{Be}/\text{Be}$ ratios of 1.993×10^{-15} and 2.133×10^{-15} , i.e. 0.3 - 1.7 % of the sample values). The effective production rate represents the sum of the neutron- and muon- (fast and stopped muons) induced production of ^{10}Be in quartz (P_{sum}), calculated using the scaling system of Stone (2000), and corrected for topographic shielding using the method of Codilean (2006). The values for individual basins are based on the arithmetic mean. T_{ave} gives the average time needed to erode the typical attenuation depth of ~ 60 cm as a proxy of ‘cosmogenic memory’, describing the time over which the cosmogenic nuclide inventory averages. Bold letters in sample names indicate notations used in the text and figures.

Sample	AMS ^{10}Be conc. [$\cdot 10^4$ at/g]	Production rate P_{sum} [at/g/yr]	Shielding [factor]	Erosion rate [mm/yr]	T_{ave} [yr]
<i>Panj:</i>					
TA090923A	5.7 ± 0.2	70.5 ± 17.3	0.92 ± 0.06	0.68 ± 0.23	880
TA090908B	6.7 ± 0.2	72.4 ± 17.3	0.92 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.20	1010
<i>Vanj:</i>					
TA090902A	1.9 ± 0.1	52.0 ± 13.3	0.87 ± 0.06	1.45 ± 0.56	410
<i>Bartang:</i>					
TA090901C	5.3 ± 0.2	79.5 ± 12.8	0.93 ± 0.06	0.83 ± 0.22	720
TA110808N	98.5 ± 2.1	80.2 ± 11.0	0.95 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.01	13010
<i>Gunt:</i>					
TA090831B	11.1 ± 0.4	73.1 ± 13.6	0.92 ± 0.06	0.37 ± 0.11	1640
TA110830P	25.5 ± 1.5	75.4 ± 12.0	0.93 ± 0.06	0.16 ± 0.05	3650
<i>southern Panj:</i>					
TA090828C	5.9 ± 0.3	78.3 ± 16.5	0.92 ± 0.06	0.74 ± 0.24	810
TA090825C	7.6 ± 0.3	80.4 ± 16.4	0.92 ± 0.06	0.58 ± 0.18	1030
TA110824O	6.3 ± 0.6	81.7 ± 14.2	0.93 ± 0.06	0.72 ± 0.24	830
TA110823P	5.7 ± 0.2	84.7 ± 11.1	0.89 ± 0.06	0.79 ± 0.19	760

The area factor a (normalized to 1) describes the portion of the upstream sub-basin relative to the area of the entire basin. The approach yields area-weighted erosion rates of 0.53 mm/yr (GUNT) and 1.64 mm/yr (BARlow) for downstream basin portions (ε_{down} , Tab. 3). Applying the same approach to the southern Panj basins enhances the contrast in erosion where the southern Panj deflects to the north at the western Pamir margin. The relative areas of the basin TA24O and TA25C indicate an erosion rate of only 0.02 mm/yr for the inferred sub-basin ISHs. In contrast, the inferred sub-basin between TA25C and TA28C (ISHn) suggests a very high erosion rate of 1.81 mm/yr, comparable to those of the lower Bartang basin (BARlow) and the

Vanj basin (TA02A). However, the area-weighted erosion rates may be biased as the actual contribution of individual basin portions to the sampled mix of material remains unresolved.

The area factor a can be replaced by a slope factor s to account for morphometric differences in basin portions. The factor s describes the ratio of the sub-basin slope scaled the slope of the entire basin and normalized to 1 (i.e. division by 2 in the case of two basins). Slope-weighted erosion rates are then determined by using the equation 2. Inferred rates indicate an improved fit to morphometric units and respective trends in basin-wide rates of measurement data. The slope-weighted erosion rates are 0.54 mm/yr for the sub-basin GUNT, 1.23 mm/yr

Figure 5: Basin-wide erosion rates of along Panj and major tributary samples (CN: cosmogenic nuclide, color code represents magnitude of erosion with green for low and red for high rates). Calculations base upon AMS measurements of ^{10}Be concentrations in modern fluvial sediments and GDEM processing for production rates and topographic shielding. Erosion rates of the sub-basins ISHn, ISHs, BARlow and GUNT represent slope weighted estimates inferred from sampled basins (respective *up* and *down*-stream basins) and using derived measurement results in equation 2 (for details see text and Tab. 3).

for BARlow, 0.46 mm/yr for ISHs and 0.89 mm/yr for ISHn (Tab. 3).

4.4. Relationship between erosion rates and basin parameters

Linear regression analyses deliver a simple, straightforward evaluation of basin characteristics. The absence of any trend with increasing basin size suggests no significant nuclide acquisition during grain transit through the basin. Results reveal a primary role of topographic basin parameters on variations of erosion rates (Fig. 6). The basin-wide erosion rates are proportional to altitude difference within basins, but highlight the scale-dependent relation between relief estimates and erosion rates. The basin relief (BR, Fig. 6A) shows no correlation, while reducing the window size of the local relief (LR, Fig. 6A) to 1 km yields an R^2 of 0.68. The highest correlation to erosion rates is attained with basin slopes. Using the median slopes yields an R^2 of 0.73 and the 0.75 quartiles an R^2 of 0.81 (Fig. 6B). The correlation of erosion with slopes suggests that the slope-weighted erosion rates for the inferred sub-basins GUNT, BARlow, ISHs and ISHn suite the primary relationship found in regression analyses (Tab. 3).

The variations in mean annual rainfall between 270 mm and 380 mm (based on TRMM rainfall data) cannot explain the pattern of erosion (R^2 of <0.1). Similar basin erosion rates cluster regardless of low or high precipitation, although high erosion relates to basins receiving highest annual precipitation. The limited influence of precipitation on erosion may relate to the overall low precipitation, predominantly in form of snow and temperature induced peak discharge in the melting season. The relative area covered by snow and ice shows no strong relation to erosion rates with an R^2 of <0.4 .

We performed a multiple linear regression analysis with two components as predictors for erosion. Including more components result in multi-collinearity and insignificant effects on the

goodness of correlation. The best results were obtained by combining the 0.75 quartiles of slope and TRMM data with a R^2 of 0.93 (Fig. 6C). The regression with slope and TRMM rainfall data indicates that low slopes imply low erosion despite variations in precipitation, while high rainfall contributes to high erosion rates in the case of steep slopes. All other parameter combinations yielded lower correlations.

5. Discussion

5.1. Averaging times of Pamir erosion rates

For a robust interpretation of the Pamir erosion rates, it is important to consider the scales of averaging in terms of time and space. As stated above, the ^{10}Be -based erosion rates average over the time interval needed to erode the characteristic attenuation depth of about 60 cm. The erosion rates in Pamir average over time scales of 10^2 to 10^4 years i.e. the Holocene (Tab. 2). The high erosion rates for most of the Pamir basins imply a T_{ave} of less than 10^3 years. Such short time intervals for the renewal of the nuclide inventory suggest that the erosion rates represent modern conditions. Although the climate likely underwent fluctuations, there is no evidence for major changes during that time in glacial records (Zech et al., 2005; Abramowski et al., 2006; Röhringer et al., 2012). The moderate erosion rates (about 0.16 - 0.37 mm/yr) calculated for the Gunt (TA31B) and the Shakh dara basins (TA30P) average over the time since the middle/late Holocene. Only the eastern Pamir Plateau basin (TA08N) has a significantly longer T_{ave} averaging erosion over the time since the MIS 2 - MIS 1 transition (Tab. 2). Changes in conditions during this period are likely but the large areas of low slopes formed by sediment-filled valleys of the inner Pamir are indicative of low erosion persistent over long time scales. However, the estimated T_{ave} means that variations in the absolute extent of glaciated areas are possible. T_{ave} is largely

Table 3: Approximated erosion rates of sub-basins using weighting factors according to basin area and basin slope. The weighting factors a and s are applied to address averaging effects of entire basins over variations in sub-basins (ϵ : erosion rate, total: entire basin, up: upper sub-basin, down: lower sub-basin, a : area factor describing the proportion of the respective sub-basin normalized to 1, s : slope factor describing the slope variations of sub-basins normalized to 1).

Basin	Erosion rate [mm/yr]				Basin area		Basin slope	
	ϵ_{total}	ϵ_{up}	$\epsilon_{down(area)}$	$\epsilon_{down(slope)}$	a_{up}	a_{down}	s_{up}	s_{down}
Gunt	0.37 ± 0.11	0.16 ± 0.05	0.53 ± 0.16	0.54 ± 0.16	0.44	0.56	0.45	0.55
Bartang	0.83 ± 0.22	0.05 ± 0.01	1.64 ± 0.38	1.23 ± 0.29	0.51	0.49	0.34	0.66
Southern Panj (TA25C)	0.58 ± 0.18	0.72 ± 0.24	0.02 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.15	0.80	0.20	0.47	0.53
Southern Panj (TA28C)	0.74 ± 0.24	0.58 ± 0.18	1.81 ± 0.57	0.89 ± 0.28	0.87	0.13	0.49	0.51

Figure 6: Linear regression analyses for erosion rates and the basin parameters relief (A), slope (B) and slope combined with precipitation (C). A: Scale-dependent relief calculation (BR: Basin relief representing the difference between the 0.75 and 0.25 quartiles of basin altitudes, LR: Local relief determining the altitude difference within a moving window of 1 km and 4 km, respectively). Values of each basin represent the median and the range between the 0.75 and 0.25 quartiles). B: Basin slopes representing the median of slopes within individual basins. Slope variations are shown according to the 0.25 and 0.75 quartiles. C: Multiple linear regression revealed highest correlation of erosion rates with the 0.75 quartiles of basin slope and TRMM-based precipitation. Solid lines show the linear regression for median values, dashed lines that of respective quartiles. R^2 gives the correlation coefficient.

longer than the period covered by available MODIS data on permanent snow and ice distribution and mostly too short to be resolved by glacial chronologies at the Pamir Plateau. We assume persistent climatic circulations and dry conditions during the last 10^3 with only slightly more extensive glaciations compared to today.

Another point to consider in terms of time scales is the nuclide built-up during grain transport from the source rock to the sampled site. Robust cosmogenic nuclide-derived erosion rates require that grain travel time through the sampled basin should be short compared to T_{ave} (Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). A significant nuclide built-up would result in a downstream increase of ^{10}Be concentrations (Schaller et al., 2001), which is not indicated along the Panj. Concentrated discharge during the melting season and also the generally high slopes especially in marginal downstream basin portions suggest that sediment is annually transported over long distances. Only valleys in the plateau-related basins contain significant sediment fills witnessing relatively long storage periods. Nevertheless, this is in agreement with determined erosion rates.

Millennial scale ^{10}Be -based erosion rates in tectonically active landscapes such as the Pamir can be dependent on the magnitude-frequency distribution of mass wasting (e.g., Wol-

man and Miller, 1960; Korup et al., 2010; Korup, 2012; Lupker et al., 2012). High-magnitude low-frequency events may not be captured by millennial scale erosion rates. Their high effects on sediment delivery to river channel decrease fast within time intervals at decadal scale or longer (Wolman and Miller, 1960; Korup, 2012). The low abundance of such events in the study area (e.g. Lake Yashilkul) indicates their minor relevance.

On the 10^6 year time scale, Stübner et al. (2013) estimated syn- to post-tectonic erosion rates of 0.3-0.5 mm/yr for the southern Pamir Shakh dara Dome and 0.1-0.3 mm/yr between the Shakh dara and Alichur Dome based on geometric constraints. These long-term estimates agree to the cosmogenic nuclide-based erosion rates of the same area. The higher rates fit to the marginal conditions of the Gunt basin, while the lower rates agree to conditions related to the inner southern Pamir (Skakh dara basin). The agreement suggests long-term persistence of erosion over time scales of 10^4 to 10^6 . The erosion rates of <0.5 mm/yr are low compared to the Pamir average and most other Panj as well as tributary basins. This delineates areas with long-term steady-state on the plateau of Pamir from marginal basins undergoing a transient stage with higher erosion rates of ~ 0.7 at a millennia scale. Erosion rates from river load gauging are not available yet, but may greatly differ from the ^{10}Be -based rates due to the mostly decadal period

of records that imply dependence on the frequency of high-magnitude event and hillslope - river channel connectivity.

5.2. Spatial variations in erosion rates

The basin-wide erosion rates represent average values for their upstream areas. They may be biased in tectonic active landscapes when certain basin portions deliver unproportionally high amounts of sediments to the river channels, for example in form of landslides (e.g. Granger et al., 1996; von Blanckenburg, 2005; Dunai, 2010). For our samples, most basins are large enough to average effects of single basin portions and sampling sites are distant from major landslides or debris flows (e.g. the debris flow damming the Lake Yashilkul). Besides, they also average over differences in the erodibility and quartz abundance of rock types. However, the sediment release from individual geomorphic units within sample basins is certainly not uniform. Hence, small scale in situ data are needed to bridge this lack for a more detailed resolution of erosional domains within the studied Pamir basins. In particular, the sediment delivery from glaciated areas requires attention. Such areas contribute sediments that likely experienced negligible ^{10}Be production rates. Excluding glaciated areas (Fig. 6A) lowers the production rates on the basin scale but this may be insufficient in the case of large quantities of glacial sediments in the sampled material.

The average erosion rates of basins along the Panj outline an overall agreement with the Pamir average of ~ 0.64 mm/yr without any clear trend from smaller to larger basins (Fig. 5). In contrast, the studied tributaries reveal strong spatial variations in erosion. The major tributary basins indicate increasing erosion to the northeast. The east-west elongation of the tributary basins cause averaging across the plateau and its margins, while the Vanj basin (TA02A) is de-coupled from the plateau. The slope-weighted calculation of erosion rates enables to differentiate between conditions according to morphometry that are averaged by rates of the entire Gunt (TA31B) and Bartang basins (TA01C). This confirms upper sub-basins with very low erosion (about 0.05 - 0.16 mm/yr) in plateau-related regions and higher rates (about 0.54 - 1.45 mm/yr) in the lower marginal sub-basins.

Overall, the ^{10}Be -based basin-wide erosion rates are 10 times lower than OSL-based incision rates. Those incision rates cover the last major deglaciation period (the last 26 kyr, Fuchs et al. 2014), but indicate dominant control from local rather than temporal factors. The discrepancy between rates implies that the basin-wide erosion does not balance the lowering of the local base levels induced by the intense fluvial incision of the Panj at the Pamir margins. Despite the difference in magnitude, the spatial pattern agrees between fluvial incision along the Panj river profile and variations in erosion rates (Fig. 7). The decreased erosion rate of (0.58 ± 0.18) mm/yr for the whole southern Panj basin (TA25C) and abrupt increase to (0.74 ± 0.24) mm/yr agrees to intensified fluvial incision of 7 - 10 mm/yr, where the Panj turns to the north cutting across the Shahdara Dome (Fig. 7; Fuchs et al., 2013, 2014). The change in process rates corresponds to morphometric evidence given by

valley shape ratios (VSR), Hack Indices and riverbed convexity. The slope-weighted estimates (ISHs and ISHn) enhance the contrast in erosion by an increase from (0.46 ± 0.15) mm/yr to (0.89 ± 0.28) mm/yr and suggest a better representation of the local morphometric conditions as respective estimates do not average over the entire upstream area. Lower erosion rates of (0.37 ± 0.11) mm/yr for the entire Gunt basin (TA31B) coincide with lower incision rates determined north of the confluence with the Gunt River where the Panj develops a more graded river profile (Fig. 7). Further north, average erosion rates of the Bartang (TA01C) and Vanj basins (TA02A) increase from 0.83 mm/yr to 1.45 mm/yr. This trend is not resolved in OSL-based incision rates that vary between 4 mm/yr and 6 mm/yr and are, on the relative scale, better comparable to the Pamir-wide average erosion rates of ~ 0.64 mm/yr. The de-coupling of the trends in erosion rates of northern tributary basins from the incision may relate to the already large Panj basin that becomes less sensitive to signals recorded by smaller tributary basins.

The magnitude of erosion is comparable with rates determined across the steep escarpment of the Himalaya (e.g. Godard et al., 2010; Andermann et al., 2012; Burbank et al., 2012; Lupker et al., 2012; Scherler et al., 2014), although conditions are different in Pamir. The monsoon-controlled southern flank of the Himalaya receives precipitation of up to 4 m/yr, where erosion rates exceed 2 mm/yr, while rates lower to ~ 0.1 mm/yr in the northern rain shadow of the Higher Himalayan and Tibetan Plateau (Burbank et al., 2012, e.g.). Gabet et al. (2008) correlated erosion based on sediment flux in Nepal rivers to average monsoon precipitation with an R^2 of ~ 0.9 . The sediment flux broadly scales with discharge. Suspended load data shows sediment flux dependent on the magnitude-frequency distribution of rainfall such that sediment pulses require an initial amount of precipitation (Andermann et al., 2012; Burbank et al., 2012). Andermann et al. (2012) emphasize the role of intense precipitation on generating direct runoff and sediment supply from hillslopes. The temperature-sensitive discharge in the high elevated northern rain shadow modulates the relation by peak discharge during the melting season. The hysteresis of sediment load and discharge suggests a supply limited behavior (Andermann et al., 2012; Burbank et al., 2012). Godard et al. (2014) describe a strong increase in erosion from 0.5 - 1 mm/yr in the Lesser Himalaya to 2 - 3 mm/yr in the Greater Himalaya despite relatively similar precipitation rates (R^2 of 0.13). They suggest erosion adapting fast to climatic changes and infer first-order control from large-scale tectonic uplift rates (R^2 of 0.78). The control of tectonic uplift on long-term erosion ($\sim 10^5$ years, based on thermochronology) agrees in uniform rates across the Greater Himalaya despite a fivefold increase in precipitation (Burbank et al., 2003). A primary control of tectonic-driven topographic steepness on erosion suggests that changes in precipitation are balanced by complex interactions between channel steepness and width, and concentrated sediment transport (Burbank et al., 2003; Scherler et al., 2014).

Steep slopes are also the primary factor controlling erosion in Pamir (R^2 of 0.81). Low erosion rates of < 0.2 mm/yr are linked to the high-elevated, low-relief inner-plateau areas that are basically comprise the Cenozoic domes of the southern,

Figure 7: Variation of millennial, basin-averaged erosion rates and fluvial incision along the Panj (CN: cosmogenic nuclide, OSL: optically stimulated luminescence). The along Panj samples (filled circles) represent ^{10}Be -based erosion rates that integrate over related upstream areas (grey shaded areas). Major tributaries and their sub-basins show local differences in erosion between marginal and plateau-related basin portions. The color code illustrates the magnitude of erosion rates (green: low, red: high) and indicates the respective basin area. OSL-based incision rates, valley shape ratios (VSR) and Hack indices (Fuchs et al., 2013, 2014) along the Panj represent the pattern of fluvial incision that determines the lowering of local base levels at the Pamir margins.

central and eastern Pamir. At the Pamir margins, rapid base level lowering by the Panj facilitates steep slopes. But the high erosion rates of 0.54 - 1.45 mm/yr in marginal basin do not balance the fast incision driven by river captures across the Pamir domes. Highest rates coincide with increased precipitation at the north-western Pamir margin and suggest complex links between erosion, slopes and precipitation. Although precipitation alone does not reveal any correlation to erosion rates (R^2 of <0.1), combined with the parameter slope multiple regression analyses yields a strong relationship by R^2 of 0.93. This multiple relation shows that steep slopes are the important precondition for the efficiency of precipitation for triggering erosion. In the overall dry Pamir, precipitation is a limiting factor for high erosion rates. Basins of highest erosion receive precipitation mainly in winter in form of snow that causes a temperature-sensitive concentration of discharge during the melting season. Less precipitation at the southern Pamir margins reduces the efficiency of sediment transport from hillslopes and out of basins. Consequently, basin-wide erosion cannot adjust to the high fluvial incision. Steep slopes as the first order control persist at the Pamir margins due to rapid, river capture controlled inci-

sion, but require sufficient precipitation for efficient sediment flux from hillslopes to the river channels. The lowest discrepancy between between hillslope processes and fluvial incision is then reached in the north-eastern Pamir where sufficient winter precipitation causes seasonal peak discharge and drives the sediment flux out of basins.

6. Conclusion

The millennial, basin-wide erosion rates of ~ 0.64 mm/yr for the entire Pamir highlight a rapid landscape evolution. This regional-scale erosion averages over very different morphometric units of the orogen. Individual sub-basins of the major tributaries emphasize strong contrasts in erosion between the Pamir margins (0.54 mm/yr to 1.45 mm/yr) and the inner plateau (0.05 mm/yr to 0.16 mm/yr). The pattern of erosion reveals fast material removal related to high variations in altitude and local base levels at the margins, and much longer residence of material where large flat areas define the constant local base level of the Pamir Plateau.

Topography affects erosion rates in Pamir especially through the prevalence of steep slopes (0.75 quartiles) that explain about

80 % of the variations in erosion (R^2 of 0.81). The persistence of steep slopes implies either tectonic uplift or base level lowering. The steep slopes drive fast material supply to the river channels. Maintaining the steep slopes and related sediment flux largely depends on the capacity of rivers to transport the sediment out of the basins. Consequently, this also could indicate a climatic component affecting the river discharge.

Highest erosion rates at the Pamir margin coincide spatially with orographic precipitation delivered by the Westerlies, but our estimated erosion rates show no correlation to mean annual precipitation. The snow and ice coverage does not correlate (R^2 of <0.4) with erosion. Multiple linear regression analyses with an R^2 of 0.93 outlines that steep slopes are an important precondition for the efficiency of erosion but also that a minimum of precipitation is required to allow the sediment transport in Pamir.

The water available for erosion shows high spatiotemporal variations (Pohl et al., 2014). It is largely controlled by the predominance of winter precipitation and its delayed release during the melting season. The resulting seasonal peak discharge during spring and early summer provides the condition for an effective sediment mobilization out of basins (Pohl et al., 2014) and hence, favors high erosion especially at the north-western Pamir margin. The drier Pamir Plateau does not generate sufficient discharge which results in the prevalence of low slopes corresponding to low erosion rates.

The magnitude of erosion is similar to rates determined across the south Himalayan escarpment and Tibetan Plateau (e.g. Godard et al., 2010; Andermann et al., 2012; Burbank et al., 2012; Lupker et al., 2012; Scherler et al., 2014), although both climatic and tectonic conditions are different in Pamir (e.g. Fuchs et al., 2013). In the Himalayas, a much higher amount of summer precipitation allows that the landscape adjusts to uplift conditions and fluvial processes compensate for variations in precipitation (e.g., Burbank et al., 2012). In the much drier Pamir, this adjustment is not reached. Incision clearly exceeds uplift. Basin-wide erosion rates do not balance the up to 10 times faster OSL-based incision rates measured along the Panj river (Fuchs et al., 2014). This significant discrepancy implies a transient landscape, for which precipitation is the limiting factor for hillslope adjustment to fluvial incision and for which we propose that river captures are responsible for the strong base level drop that drives incision along the Panj.

The limited coupling of erosion and incision has important implications on landscape evolution models and geohazard prediction (e.g., Gruber and Mergili, 2013). The dry conditions/low winter precipitation may limit the hillslope response to base level lowering to the close vicinity of the river channel itself, and hence, may intensify effects from hillslope length and channel network density. The strong incision and narrow wavelength of hillslope response suggest local relief steepening with increasing risks of sudden slope failures and resulting debris flows or landslides. Additionally, the case of the Pamir shows not only the complex interplay of tectonic and climatic factors, but highlights especially the importance of internal feedbacks in an evolving drainage system, here in form of river captures, that require implementation in landscape models.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank the Department of Meteorology and Hydrology of Tajikistan for the support and organization during fieldwork in 2011. We are also grateful for the support of the DREAMS operator team facilitating AMS beam time, with special thanks to René Ziegenruecker, Shavkat Akhmadaliev and Stefan Pavetich. And we thank the DFG for funding our research associated with the TIPAGE project (GI362/4-1). We used GMT (Wessel, P. and W. H. F. Smith, New, improved version of the Generic Mapping Tools released, EOS Trans. AGU, 79, 579, 1998), QGIS (<http://qgis.org/>) and the R environment (<http://www.r-project.org/>) for most of the topographic data processing and the resulting figures. MODIS MCD12Q1 and ASTER GDEM data products were obtained through the online Data Pool at the NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC), located at the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center, Sioux Falls, South Dakota (https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/data_access).

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5.3 Implications on the topographic evolution

The ^{10}Be -based erosion rates highlight very fast material removal at the Pamir margins (roughly 0.9 - 1.4 mm/yr) and much longer material residence at the inner Pamir Plateau (roughly 0.2 - 0.1 mm/yr). This demarcation corresponds to the topographic pattern (Paper I, chapter 2.2) of high altitude variations and local base level changes at the Pamir margins, while at the plateau large flat areas dominate local base levels for erosion. In the Pamir, the control of topography on erosion especially relates to the frequencies of the steepest slopes (0.75 quartiles) that allow fast material delivery to the river channels. In the river channels, it is then the fluvial capacity that regulates further sediment transport and consequently, also suggests a climatic component in basin-wide erosion.

The pattern of erosion indicates a northward increase that coincides with moisture supply by the Westerlies. Precipitation or coverage of permanent snow and ice alone do not show a correlation with erosion but precipitation correlates in multiple linear regression when also including slope. This illustrates that steep slopes are an important precondition for the efficiency of precipitation in erosive processes. The highest erosion rates characterize steep basins at the north-western margin that receive precipitation mostly in the form of snow. Effects on erosion consequently depend on the release of the 'accumulated precipitation' in form of concentrated discharge during the melting season. The predominance of winter precipitation from the Westerlies suggests an increased efficiency of concentrated discharge at the north-western Pamir margin. The coincidence with high erosion rates indicates that peak discharge facilitates basin-wide erosion by removing the sediment supplied from adjacent hillslopes. This constitutes an efficient way to maintain steep slopes and triggers high, basin-wide sediment flux and low storage times at the Pamir margins.

The opposite is true for the Pamir Plateau. The drier conditions lead to less annual snow accumulation available for peak discharge during the melting season. Lower peak discharge corresponds to reduced evacuation of sediments supplied from adjacent hill slopes. The very low erosion rates integrate conditions of the whole Holocene and suggests that sediments of the deglaciation since the last glacial cycle are still at the plateau. Given that the erosion from the Pamir margin progrades into the plateau through the east-west trending rivers, an increase in erosion may affect the inner plateau reaches. However, from the very little incision observed for plateau river reaches time constraints about an increase or persistence of process rates is difficult as the ^{10}Be signal averages over 10^4 years, while sediments at marginal positions record the process intensity for time scales at the order of 10^2 years to 10^3 years. However, the contrast also suggests that fluvial processes at the plateau are not yet established. Links to marginal conditions are buffered by low local base level variations, and depend on the distance to the drainage-wide local base level set by the Panj river.

Compared to the OSL-based incision rates along the Panj (Paper IV, chapter 4.2), the general pattern of basin-wide erosion rates recorded along the Panj outlines an overall agreement of erosion and incision. However, two things need to be noted. First, erosion rates are about 10 times lower compared to fluvial incision. This implies that the Panj is very efficient in transporting sediments out of the orogen and maintaining steep hillslopes. Second, erosion reveals a northward increase in rates that is masked in incision rates probably due to the low sensitivity to local conditions resulting from already high drainage area and respective discharge (cf. chapter 4.3). Consequently, it is suggested that the basin-wide erosion rates are advanced in revealing any influence of climatic factors compared to fluvial incision rates.

6 Conclusions

The surface processes in Pamir highlight the complex feedbacks with tectonic and climatic control factors. The specific configuration of factors in the Pamir relates to the ongoing, intra-continental deformation and climatic gradients imposed by two atmospheric circulation systems, but overall dry conditions. The patterns of process response provide new insights into the controls of mountain evolution and whether relations found in other orogens are also evident in the Pamir.

The geomorphometric evidences, fluvial incision and basin-wide erosion reveal a clear demarcation of surface response processes between the Pamir Plateau and its margins, as well as across major tectonic structures of the Pamir. The process measures are sensitive to tectonic and climatic conditions at different time scales. Geomorphometric proxies integrate over geologic time scales of 10^6 yr, while the fluvial incision rates resolve the time since the last glaciation at ~ 26 kyr, and the basin wide erosion rates average recent conditions at the scale of 10^3 yr. Consequently, individual measures also reveal changes over time and effects of paleo-conditions inherited in ongoing processes.

The presented cumulative thesis comprises relative and absolute measures of surface processes in Pamir as well as methodological implications for luminescence dating of sediments from high mountain areas. The key findings demonstrated in the chapters 2 to 5 concern the following issues:

- Geomorphometric evidences of river captures driving the drainage evolution in Pamir
- Luminescence data processing routines and material-related aspects of high mountain sediments
- Dominance of structural controls on intensity of OSL-based incision rates
- Dominance of topographic factors over precipitation on triggering basin-wide erosion rates

Geomorphometric evidences of river captures driving the drainage evolution in Pamir

The geomorphometric proxies of surface processes reveal the differential response to tectonic and climatic factors between the Pamir Plateau and its margins. But the patterns also outline that not a single factor controls the surface response. Instead, it is the combination of tectonic units and climatic gradients that drive the recent processes and impose effects at different spatial and temporal scales. The scale-dependence has important implications on the persistence of features from earlier conditions and their imprints in process proxies. The spatio-temporal variations of tectonic factors and their topographic manifestation are characterized by:

- Northward crustal shortening induced topographic rise in the form of predominantly east-west oriented mountain ranges parallel to tectonic structures

- The Cenozoic domes form an elevated plateau-topography with wide, flat inner-plateau valley that indicates long-term persistence of the westward drainage orientation
- Pamir margins show high topographic variability and fluctuating base levels indicative of fast landscape changes, the deep incised valleys coincide with neotectonic activity along orogen- and probably also dome-bounding faults as well as with orographic precipitation

The resulting elevated topography of the Pamir exposes the mountain ranges to the 'destructive' forces of climatic factors. The location of the Pamir implies a dry, continental climate in the transition between two atmospheric circulation systems, the Westerlies and the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM). Feedbacks of climatic factors with the orogen's topography comprise:

- Orographic precipitation concentrated at the north-western and southern Pamir margins and resulting rain shadow towards the eastern Pamir Plateau
- The prevalent Westerlies impose a threefold gradient from the western to the eastern Pamir corresponding to the increasing altitudes at the western Pamir margin, and deliver most of the precipitation during winter in form of snow
- The precipitation induced from the ISM strongly attenuates with an up to fivefold gradient from the southern Hindu Kush towards to eastern Pamir
- The north-westward displacement of permanent snow and ice illustrates the sensitivity to low temperature of high altitudes superimposed by the precipitation limited conditions in the central-eastern Pamir
- Late Quaternary glaciations drive processes at the Pamir Plateau during several cycles over the last $\sim 10^5$ yr, but of successively reduced extent corresponding to an aridification in Central Asia

The Pamir drainage network aligns to the structural-induced, prevalent east-west orientation of mountain ranges. The elongated basin architecture links the plateau discharge with the western Pamir margin. Northward flowing reaches of the trunk stream, the Panj, connect the elongated basins close to the drainage divide. The river and valley morphometry along the trunk stream describe an alteration of fluvial incision independent of lithologic or climatic control. Instead, the pattern indicates long-term persistence of westward draining reaches and local perturbances by successive river captures across major tectonic structures. Evidences of river captures controlling the evolution of the Panj river system comprise:

- Prevalent westward drainage orientation, while the trunk stream, the Panj, shows multiple northward deflections of flow direction that connect elongated sub-basins close to the western drainage divide
- Graded zones in the longitudinal profile and widened valleys determine local base levels for river reaches parallel to southern dome boundaries
- The major convex zones in the longitudinal profile agree to steep valleys, where northward reaches cut across the southern Pamir margin, the Shakh dara and the Yazgulom domes
- Upstream increasing convexity compared to graded profiles indicates different stages of river adjustment to recent conditions

River captures evidence the dominance of structural control on evolution of the Panj river network rather than effects from climate. An influence from tectonic base level lowering along dome bounding faults is suggested by the convex zones in the Panj profile, which is not resolved in thermochronologic data.

Luminescence data processing routines and material-related aspects of high mountain sediments

The investigations on luminescence data processing and material-related signal properties outline the adequate techniques for dating applications in high mountains. Three *R* code templates provide an exemplary routine for reproducible and transparent data processing using the *R* package 'Luminescence'. The templates illustrate how to use the functions available in the **R** package and how to organize outputs in variables for consecutive processing steps including:

- Data input and analyses of signal decay and dose-response properties including the calculation of signals from signal-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocols and of equivalent doses (D_e)
- Dose distribution analyses with focus on kernel density estimate (KDE)-based plots and using descriptive statistics to infer bleaching and/or sediment mixing based on skewness or evidence of mixed multiple components
- Age modeling with focus on the minimum age model (MAM) but also including the finite mixture model (FMM) for illustration of how to apply further age models

Apart from this data processing perspective, the investigations on material related properties highlight differences between multiple and single grain, as well as between the minerals quartz, K-feldspar and plagioclase. But results also show different luminescence behavior for the same mineral type from different source areas. This implies that sediments from high mountain areas require tests on the luminescence properties of each single sample to ensure reliable measurement setup and data processing. The main outcomes from the analyses of the challenging rock glacier material are:

- Quartz signals of overall low luminescence intensities and often poor dose-response behavior that contrast much better luminescence properties for one location with lithologically different source material
- K-feldspar shows much brighter signals of mostly reliable dose-response behavior while plagioclase fails to yield robust luminescence signals
- Quartz and feldspar results are comparable within uncertainties but vary in certain drawbacks that require attention for applications to sediment from high mountains
 - Highly dynamic processes promote the use of quartz because of faster bleaching
 - Low signal may limit measurements to multiple grain analyses when using quartz
 - For old sediments feldspar may be adequate as residual signals become less important
 - The generally low temperatures seem to reduce effects from anomalous fading
- Single grain analyses allow for sophisticated dose distribution analyses of differential bleaching and sediment mixing but rely on sufficient signal intensities

- Multiple grain aliquots may also be suitable for quartz of medium to low signal intensities as only few grains contribute to the aliquot's signal
- But multiple grain aliquots induce averaging effects to dose distributions and limit age modeling to minimum dose approaches, while fake dose populations would result in component un-mixing when using the finite mixture model
- Changing the overdispersion between 0.05 and 0.5 shows little effects on paleodoses using the finite mixture model

The results of luminescence analyses highlight that the luminescence sensitivity and process-related bleaching and sediment mixing are the central questions when selecting quartz or feldspar for dating applications in high mountains. Single grain analyses allow for an advanced dose distribution analyses but comparable results suggest that multiple grain aliquots may be used for quartz analyses as well. The variations of luminescence properties between minerals, and also for the same minerals from different locations outline that there is no single answer to which techniques suits in general. The measurement setup and data analytics need to be adjusted to the properties of individual samples.

Dominance of structural controls on intensity of OSL-based incision rates

OSL-based incision rates determine strong variations in the magnitudes of fluvial incision across the main structural units of the Pamir. The pattern confirms the alteration of relative fluvial incision proxies that suggest successive river captures in upstream direction. The robust interpretation of a structural control essentially relies on the quality of terrace dating by OSL techniques. Reliable OSL ages are ensured by adjusting the measurement setup according to the results from preheat and dose recovery tests, by using different aliquot sizes, and by age modeling due to dose distribution statistics. OSL analyses yield the following results:

- Preheat and dose recovery tests show reliable dose-response relations for lower preheat and cut-heat temperatures (160–230°C)
- 4 mm aliquots yield luminescence signals of sufficient intensities and adequate reproducibilities, while 2 mm aliquots suffer from low signals above the background and higher uncertainties in the dose-response behavior
- Dose distributions indicate differential bleaching by high scatter and skewness
- Differential bleaching is addressed by calculating terrace ages based on the minimum age model (MAM)

Resulting terrace ages represent local, short-term fluvial sedimentation at the western Pamir margin, where fluvial incision prevails. The relation between terrace age and heights above the river reveals important aspects for the interpretation of a dominant structural control over influences from paleo-climatic fluctuations:

- Older terraces indicate sedimentation triggered by glacial cycles by synchronous timing and terrace location at the confluence with westward rivers draining the Pamir Plateau

- Terraces younger than 5 kyr occur independent of glacial cycles at the plateau and plateau-draining river reaches
- Fluvial incision rates correlate with terrace location rather than with age and consequently, suggest differences in spatial factors controlling incision at the western Pamir margin
- Terraces along the Panj reach cutting across the Shakhdara Dome show persistent high fluvial incision of 7–10 mm/yr over the last ~26 kyr
- Much lower incision rates of 2–4 mm/yr characterize graded river reaches that respond to local base levels at southern dome boundaries
- The transient stage of fluvial incision at the north-western Pamir margin is perturbed by increased incision of ~6 mm/yr across the Darvaz Fault Zone

The OSL-based rates complement the morphometry-based interpretation of successive river captures by quantitative data on magnitude and contrasts of fluvial incision. The overall high elevation of the Panj river profile above the regional base level explains the prevalence of incision also in graded river reaches, where the Panj develops local base levels within the Pamir. The high incision rates across the Shakhdara Dome exceed the Pamir average of ~5.6 mm/yr. The consistent high rates also for older terraces imply that the river capture across the dome occurred before 26 kyr. The convexity of the river profile indicates recently active dome boundaries. Related local base level changes pronounce incision and may have contributed to the river capture across the Shakhdara Dome.

Dominance of topographic factors over precipitation on triggering basin-wide erosion rates

The basin-wide erosion rates determine a fast average topographic evolution with ~0.65 mm/yr for the entire Pamir, but highlight the different pace at the Pamir Plateau compared to marginal positions. The conditions also differ between the southern and (north-)western margins. The erosion pattern describes the natural background conditions at millennial scale with only plateau-erosion averaging over the Holocene and related effects from deglaciation. The magnitudes of erosion and their spatial variations demonstrate:

- Consistent erosion rates of basins along the Panj suggesting high sediment flux out of the Pamir without significant storage periods at the Pamir margins, and similarity of erosion rates at the southern Pamir margin with the Pamir average
- Elongated basins draining the Pamir to the west display high erosion contrasts
- High erosion of 0.55–1.43 mm/yr characterize the western, marginal sub-basins, while plateau-related sub-basins reveal low erosion of 0.05–0.17 mm/yr
- Northward increasing erosion in marginal sub-basins at the western Pamir margin

The strong contrasts in erosion correspond to the morphometric differentiation between plateau-related and marginal process domains. Additionally, the highest erosion at the north-western margin suggests an influence from climatic factors on the erosion pattern. Linear regression analyses characterize the influence of basin properties on erosion by:

- Steep slopes (0.75 quartiles of basin values) explaining $\sim 80\%$ of the erosion's variability (R^2 of 0.82)
- No or only weak correlation with erosion outline low effects of precipitation (R^2 of ~ 0.2) or permanent snow and ice cover (R^2 of ~ 0.6)
- Multiple linear regression identifies steep slopes as an important precondition for the efficiency of precipitation with the frequency of high values (0.75 quartiles) as the best predictor for erosion rates (R^2 of 0.93)

The steep slopes driving fast material flux to the basin's river channels imply control from either tectonic uplift or base level lowering. It then depends on the capacity of rivers to transport the sediment out of basins in order to maintain steep slopes over time. The influence of river discharge suggests a climatic component that becomes evident in multiple linear regression analyses between erosion, slope and precipitation. The highest erosion rates coincide with the Westerlies delivering orographic precipitation predominantly during winter. Resulting peak discharge during the melting season seems to induce the highest erosion rates at the north-western Pamir margin as it allows effective sediment transport out of basins. The lower erosion at the southern margin highlights the precipitation-limited conditions in Pamir.

The limited water available for erosion contrasts conditions in the Himalayas, although the magnitude of erosion is similar. In the dry Pamir, fluvial incision is not in steady state and clearly exceeds tectonic uplift. The significant discrepancy between basin-wide erosion rates and up to 10 times higher fluvial incision at the western Pamir margin implies a transient landscape. River captures induce high fluvial incision along the Panj by the strong base level drop. The fast valley deepening generates steep slopes favorable for high erosion, but low precipitation limits the hillslope adjustment at the basin scale.

Implications on the Pamir evolution and further research questions

The variable surface processes and their complex relations with controlling factors highlight a spatially differential evolution of the Pamir. Very low process rates represent a relatively stable, slowly evolving plateau, where fluvial incision is not yet fully established and glacial processes are restricted to high altitudes. High process rates at the Pamir margin result from feedbacks between major tectonic structures and river captures controlling strong base level drops, and orographic precipitation.

Scattered seismicity provides evidence of neotectonic activity along dome bounding faults as potential drivers of the drainage re-organization. Recent activity remains unresolved along the Southern Pamir Shear Zone bounding the Shakh dara Dome to the south. But clustering seismicity along the Gunt Shear Zone to the northern of the Shakh dara Dome and also at the Yazgulom Dome potentially contributed to the river captures across the domes. Respective reaches of the Panj are parallel to major fault systems such as the Darvaz Fault Zone and the Bakhdashan Fault that bound the Pamir to the west. Elongated tributaries of the Gunt and Shakh dara rivers also coincide with this north-south orientation. Such evidences of tectonic control on the evolution of the western Pamir margin is not studied yet.

Potential effects on marginal base level lowering and drainage organization may be elucidated by further data on the variability of fluvial incision in westward river reaches tapping the plateau drainage. In this context, the massive debris flow-like mountain collapses damming the Yashilkul and Sarez Lakes are of interest. Their consequences on sediment transport and fluvial

discharge across the plateau edge may be derived by comparison to rivers without such natural dams such as the Shakh dara river and an upper tributary of the Gunt that drains the Jelondy area. Additionally, the fluvial incision along the southern Panj indicates another major event of drainage re-organization but lacks quantitative data on process rates. Geochronological data on the timing of the river captures along the Panj are needed to further elucidate the control from tectonic structures or synchrony with changes in climatic conditions, and to determine the response rate of the Panj drainage system to major re-organization events.

The fluvial incision along the Panj drives erosion by generating steep slopes, while precipitation limits hillslope sediment flux to the river channels. The dry conditions result in a 10 times faster valley deepening compared to basin-wide erosion at the south(-western) Pamir margin. At the north-western margin, higher Westerlies-derived winter precipitation and related seasonal discharge allows for a certain adjustment of erosion to the roughly ~ 3 times faster incision along the Panj. The availability of water increases the sediment flux from hillslopes out of basins driving high basin-wide erosion and less pronounced valley deepening.

Studied basins average the erosion over relatively large areas, while the contribution of individual source areas to the average sediment flux out of basins remains unknown. Uneven contributions of sediment can result from, for example, slope aspect-related variations in precipitation or glaciated areas, and related changes in the dominating process. Also mass wasting processes such as debris flows potentially affect sediment yields averaged by the millennial CN-based erosion rates, but respective data on magnitude-frequency distributions are not available. Such scale-dependent effects highlight the need for further, small scale data to reveal the distinct factors controlling the sediment flux within the basins and within shorter time intervals. In this context, especially data from river sediment loads and hydrological modeling promises new insights into the relations between sediment load and water discharge, and its short-term cyclicity related to seasonal or even daily variations.

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A Supplementary material for paper II (chapter 3.2)

- Supplementary Data -
**Data processing in luminescence dating analysis:
an exemplary workflow using the R package
'Luminescence'**

Quaternary International

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1 R.Luminescence template 1: OSLsignal

```

1 #=====
2 # R template for luminescence data analyses using the R package 'Luminescence' #
3 # PART 1 >> OSL signal analysis
4 #-----#
5 #
6 # requirements:  - R package 'Luminescence' (version 0.3.3)
7 #
8 # input data:   - .BIN file
9 #               - single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol
10 #
11 # description:  - read .BIN file data to R
12 #               - analyse and plot luminescence signals
13 #               - analyse and plot dose response curves
14 #               - calculate equivalent dose data
15 #
16 # contact: http://www.r-luminescence.de
17 #=====
18
19 warning("Example_data_only_!_Please_consider_modification_of_script_and
20         !_function_parameters!")
21
22 #=====
23 # 1.1 PREPARATION -----
24 #=====
25
26 # load the package R.Luminescence
27 library("Luminescence")
28
29 # set working directory to the directory that contains the example data
30 # replace directory with your own path
31 setwd("[YOUR_PATH]")
32
33 # provide name of BIN file (convenient for output file names)
34 sample <- "TA110817N13-14_OSL_4_ed"
35
36
37 #=====
38 # 1.2 READ BIN.file -----

```

```

39 #=====
40
41 BINfile <- readBIN2R( file = paste(sample, ".BIN", sep=""))
42
43 # show BINfile >> @METADATA[ID, DATA]
44 # - measurement sequence ... for example ...
45 BINfile@METADATA[1:30, c(2, 7, 8, 9, 22, 31, 45, 21)]
46 #colnames(BINfile@METADATA)
47
48 # - number of measured aliquots ($POSITION)
49 max(BINfile@METADATA$POSITION)
50
51
52 # show BINfile >> @DATA[[ID]]
53 # - luminescence signals for selected positions
54 BINfile@DATA[BINfile@METADATA$POSITION == 2]
55
56 # - luminescence signals for selected curve data (row ID)
57 BINfile@DATA[[2]]
58
59
60 #=====
61 # 1.3 SELECT aliquot.position -----
62 #=====
63
64 # ... all positions
65 aliquot.position <- min(BINfile@METADATA$POSITION):
66                       max(BINfile@METADATA$POSITION)
67
68 # ... or certain range / position
69 aliquot.position <- 1:20
70
71 # ... store aliquot selection for further analyses
72 a.min <- min(aliquot.position)
73 a.max <- max(aliquot.position)
74
75
76 #=====
77 # 1.4 PLOT signals of each stimulation cycle -----
78 #
79 # plot_BINfileData()
80 #=====
81
82 # plot to .pdf with convenient name (saved in working directory defined above)
83 # open plot device, i.e. pdf
84 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_aliquot", a.min, "-", a.max, "_signal.pdf", sep = ""))
85
86 # set plot margins
87 par(mar = c(2, 2, 3, 2))
88
89 # plot actual .BIN-file data
90 plot_Risoe_BINfileData(BINfileData = BINfile,
91                        position = aliquot.position,

```

```

92         sorter = "POSITION",
93         ltype = "OSL",
94         cex = 1.3)
95
96 # turn off plot device, this is important if no further pdf-output is desired
97 dev.off()
98
99
100 # ===== #
101 # 1.5 ANALYSE measured SAR signals ----- #
102 #
103 # Analyse_SAR.OSLdata()
104 #       requires: BINfile <- readBIN2R("sample.BIN")
105 #       calculates: LnLxTnTx data, recycling ratio and recuperation
106 #                   for selected aliquot.positions
107 # ===== #
108
109 # INPUT parameters
110 # .....
111 signal.integral <- 1:5           # provide channels (integral) used for
112                                # signal calculation
113
114 background.integral <- 200:250   # provide channels (integral) used for
115                                # background calculation
116
117 # SAR analyses
118 # .....
119 SAR <- Analyse_SAR.OSLdata(input.data = BINfile,
120                            signal.integral = signal.integral,
121                            background.integral = background.integral,
122                            position = aliquot.position,
123                            info.measurement = paste(sample, sep = " "),
124                            output.plot = TRUE)
125
126 # show results
127 SAR
128
129 # plot results from SAR analyses to .pdf
130 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_aliquot", a.min, "-", a.max, "_AnalyseSAR.pdf", sep = ""))
131
132 Analyse_SAR.OSLdata(input.data = BINfile,
133                    signal.integral = signal.integral,
134                    background.integral = background.integral,
135                    position = aliquot.position,
136                    info.measurement = paste(sample, sep = " "),
137                    output.plot = TRUE)
138 dev.off()
139
140
141 # ===== #
142 # 1.6 ANALYSE dose response data ----- #
143 #
144 # - recycling ratio and recuperation from SAR >> recycling.ratio & recuperation

```



```

198
199
200 # 1.6.4 Write De data to data frame -----
201 # create new empty data frame
202 De.data.sel <- data.frame(De = NA, De.Error = NA, RR = NA, recuperation = NA)
203
204 # get De-value and De error (growth.curve@data$De) and store in data frame
205 RLum.data.sel <- get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")
206 RLum.data.sel
207
208 De.data.sel[,1] <- RLum.data.sel[1]
209 De.data.sel[,2] <- RLum.data.sel[2]
210 De.data.sel[,3] <- recycling.ratio[select.aliquot]
211 De.data.sel[,4] <- recuperation[select.aliquot]
212
213
214 # 1.6.4 Rejection Criteria -----
215
216 # set rejection criteria [RR: recycling ratio, RC: recuperation]
217 # e.g., for 10% set RR or RC to 0.1
218 RR <- 0.1
219 RC <- 0.05
220
221 De.data.sel[,1] <- ifelse(sqrt((1 - recycling.ratio[select.aliquot])^2) < RR,
222                          get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[1],
223                          NA)
224 De.data.sel[,2] <- ifelse(sqrt((1 - recycling.ratio[select.aliquot])^2) < RR,
225                          get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[2],
226                          NA)
227
228 De.data.sel[,1] <- ifelse(recuperation[select.aliquot] < RC,
229                          get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[1],
230                          NA)
231 De.data.sel[,2] <- ifelse(recuperation[select.aliquot] < RC,
232                          get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[2],
233                          NA)
234
235
236 # 1.6.5 Evaluate and write De data to data frame in a loop -----
237 # automatically loop through entire data set, only realised for versions 0.3.1 and higher
238 # create empty data.frame
239 De.data <- data.frame(De = NA, De.Error = NA, RR = NA, recuperation = NA)
240 colnames(De.data) <- c("De", "De.error", "RR", "recuperation")
241
242 # plot to .pdf with convenient name (saved in working directory defined above)
243 # open plot device, i.e. pdf
244 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_aliquot", a.min, "-", a.max, ".pdf",
245                 sep = ""), paper = "special")
246
247 # start loop
248 for(i in a.min:a.max) {
249
250   # get LxTx data

```

```

251 LxTx.data <- as.data.frame(cbind(SAR[[1]][[i]][c(2, # Dose
252                               12, # LxTx
253                               13, # LxTx.Error
254                               6)])) # TnTx
255
256 # calculate and plot growth curves for aliquot i
257 growth.curve <- plot_GrowthCurve(sample = LxTx.data,
258                                 fit.method = "EXP",
259                                 fit.weights = TRUE,
260                                 fit.includingRepeatedRegPoints = TRUE,
261                                 NumberIterations.MC = 100,
262                                 xlab = "s",
263                                 output.plot = TRUE,
264                                 output.plotExtended = TRUE,
265                                 cex.global = 1.3)
266
267
268 # write evaluations to result data frame
269 De.data[i,1] <- get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[1]
270 De.data[i,2] <- get_RLum.Results(growth.curve, data.object = "De")[2]
271 De.data[i,3] <- recycling.ratio[i]
272 De.data[i,4] <- recuperation[i]
273 }
274
275 # turn off plot device, this is important if no further pdf-output is desired
276 dev.off()
277
278 # show De.data results
279 De.data
280
281
282 # 1.6.6 Rejection Criteria 

---


283
284 # set rejection criteria [RR: recycling ratio, RC: recuperation]
285 # e.g., for 10% set RR or RC to 0.1
286 RR <- 0.1
287 RC <- 0.075
288 De.data.RC <- De.data
289
290 # start loop
291 for(i in a.min:a.max) {
292
293 De.data.RC[i,1] <- ifelse(sqrt((1 - De.data[i,3])^2) < RR,
294                           De.data[i,1], NA)
295
296 De.data.RC[i,2] <- ifelse(sqrt((1 - De.data[i,3])^2) < RR,
297                           De.data[i,2], NA)
298
299
300 De.data.RC[i,1] <- ifelse(De.data[i,4] < RC,
301                           De.data[i,1], NA)
302
303 De.data.RC[i,2] <- ifelse(De.data[i,4] < RC,

```

```

304         De.data[i,2], NA)
305
306
307     }
308
309     #show results
310     De.data.RC
311
312
313     #=====
314     # 1.7 CONVERT De.data from seconds to Gray -----
315     #
316     # Second2Gray()
317     #=====
318
319     # 1.7.1 Set parameters and do initial calculations -----
320     measurement.date <- "2013-01-10"      # e.g. "2012-08-27"
321     calibration.date <- "2008-03-01"
322     calibration.dose.rate <- 5.95         # in Gy/min
323     calibration.error <- 0.04
324
325     # calculate and show day since source calibration
326     decay.time <- as.Date(c(measurement.date, calibration.date))
327     decay.days <- decay.time[1] - decay.time[2]
328     decay.days
329
330     # calculate dose rate of source at date of measurement [Gy/min]
331     measurement.dose.rate <- (calibration.dose.rate) *
332         exp((-0.6931 / 10402.5) * as.numeric(decay.days))
333     measurement.dose.rate.error <- (calibration.error) *
334         exp((-0.6931 / 10402.5) * as.numeric(decay.days))
335
336     # convert to [Gy/s]
337     measurement.dose.rate.sec <- measurement.dose.rate / 60
338     measurement.dose.rate.error.sec <- measurement.dose.rate.error *
339         (measurement.dose.rate.error / measurement.dose.rate)
340
341     measurement.dose.rate.sec
342     measurement.dose.rate.error.sec
343
344
345     # 1.7.2 Convert De [s] to De [Gy] and show result -----
346     De.data.sec <- De.data[,1:2]
347     De.data.RC.sec <- De.data.RC[,1:2]
348
349     De.data.Gray <- Second2Gray(De.data.sec, c(measurement.dose.rate.sec,
350                                                 measurement.dose.rate.error.sec))
351     De.data.RC.Gray <- Second2Gray(De.data.RC.sec, c(measurement.dose.rate.sec,
352                                                       measurement.dose.rate.error.sec))
353
354
355     # write dose rate [Gy] to De.data data set
356     De.data[,1:2] <- De.data.Gray

```

```
357 De.data.RC[, 1:2] <- De.data.RC.Gray
358
359 # 1.7.3 save De data set as ASCII file to working directory
360 write.table(De.data, file = paste(sample, "_De_Gy.txt", sep = ""))
361 write.table(De.data.RC, file = paste(sample, "_De_Gy_select.txt", sep = ""))
```

2 R.Luminescence template 2: D_e Distribution plot

```

1 # =====#
2 # R template for luminescence data analyses using the R package 'Luminescence' #
3 # PART 2 >> De distribution statistics
4 # =====#
5 #
6 # requirements:  - R package 'Luminescence' (version 0.3.3)
7 #
8 # input data:   - .txt file (two columns: equivalent doses and errors)
9 #               - De.data (from R template PART 1)
10 #
11 # description:  - load equivalent dose data to R
12 #               - analyse and plot dose distribution
13 #
14 # contact: http://www.r-luminescence.de
15 # =====#
16
17 warning("Example_data_only. Please_consider_modification_of_script_and
18         function_parameters!")
19
20 # =====#
21 # 1.1 PREPARATION -----#
22 # =====#
23
24 # load the package R.Luminescence
25 library("Luminescence")
26
27 # set working directory to the directory that contains the example data
28 # replace directory with your own path
29 setwd("[YOUR_PATH]")
30 sample <- "TA110817N13-14_OSL_4_ed"
31
32 # =====#
33 # 1.2 READ De data -----#
34 # =====#
35
36 De.data <- read.table(paste(sample, "_De_Gy.txt", sep = "))
37
38 # show De data
39 De.data
40

```

```

41
42 #=====
43 # 1.3 PREPARE data -----
44 #=====
45
46 # select De and error, only these are needed. Necessary if additional columns
47 # (e.g. recycling.ratio, recuperation) are present
48 De.data <- De.data[,1:2]
49
50 # remove NA values
51 De.data <- na.omit(De.data)
52
53 # sort in ascending order (required for further analyses, e.g. age models
54 # (cf. template PART 3))
55 De.data <- De.data[order(De.data[,1], decreasing = FALSE),]
56
57 # if necessary, convert to data frame (required for function plot_KDE)
58 De.data <- as.data.frame(De.data)
59
60
61 #=====
62 # 1.4 PLOT De distribution as kernel density estimate (KDE) -----
63 #=====
64
65 # plot to .pdf with convenient name (saved in working directory defined above)
66 # open plot device, i.e. pdf
67 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_DeDistribution_KDE.pdf", sep = ""),
68     paper = "special")
69
70 # set plot margins
71 par(mar = c(4, 4, 3, 2))
72
73 # create KDE plot with further statistical information
74 plot_KDE(data = De.data,
75          centrality = c("kdemax", "mean"),
76          stats = c("n", "mean", "seabs", "sdrel", "skewness"),
77          stats.pos = "topright",
78          main = expression(paste( D[e], "_Distribution")),
79          mtext = sample,
80          fun = FALSE,
81          cex = 1.0)
82
83 # optional lines for e.g. quartiles, plotted separately for better control
84 q.25 <- quantile(x = De.data[,1], probs = 0.25)
85 q.75 <- quantile(x = De.data[,1], probs = 0.75)
86 median <- median(x = De.data[,1])
87
88 abline(v = median, col = "grey", lty = 1, lwd = 0.75)
89 abline(v = q.25, col = "grey", lty = 2, lwd = 0.75)
90 abline(v = q.75, col = "grey", lty = 2, lwd = 0.75)
91
92
93 # turn off plot device, this is important if no further pdf-output is desired

```

```
94 dev.off()
95
96
97 #=====#
98 # 1.5 PLOT De distribution as Radial plot -----#
99 #=====#
100
101 # open plot device, i.e. pdf
102 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_DeDistribution_RadialPlot.pdf", sep = ""),
103     paper = "special")
104
105 # set plot margins
106 par(mar = c(4, 4, 3, 2))
107
108 # create radial plot
109 plot_RadialPlot(data = De.data,
110                plot.ratio = 0.5,
111                summary = c("n", "mean", "seabs", "sdrel"))
112
113 # turn off plot device, this is important if no further pdf-output is desired
114 dev.off()
```

3 R.Luminescence template 3: age models

```

1 # =====#
2 # R template for luminescence data analyses using the package "Luminescence"
3 #
4 # PART 3 >> age models
5 # =====#
6 #
7 # requirements:  - R package 'Luminescence' (version 0.3.3)
8 #
9 # input data:   - .txt file (two columns: equivalent doses and errors)
10 #
11 #               - De.data (from R template PART 1)
12 #
13 # description:  - load equivalent dose data to R
14 #               - apply finite mixutre model (FMM)
15 #               - apply minimum age model (MAM)
16 #               - plot dose distribution and age model results
17 #
18 # contact: http://www.r-luminescence.de
19 # =====#
20 warning("Example_data_only. Please_consider_modification_of_script_and
21         function_parameters!")
22 # =====#
23 # 1.1 PREPARATION -----#
24 # =====#
25
26 # load the package R.Luminescence
27 library("Luminescence")
28
29 # set working directory to the directory that contains the example data
30 setwd("[YOUR_PATH]")
31
32 # provide name of BIN file (convenient for output file names)
33 sample <- "TA110817N13-14_OSL_4_ed"
34
35 # =====#
36 # 1.2 READ De data -----#
37 # =====#

```

```

38
39 De.data <- read.table(paste(sample, "_De_Gy.txt", sep = ""))
40
41 # show De data
42 De.data
43
44 #=====
45 # 1.3 PREPARE data -----#
46 #=====
47 # select De and De error, only these are needed. Necessary if additional columns
48 # (e.g. recycling.ratio, recuperation) are present
49 De.data <- De.data[,1:2]
50
51 # remove NA values
52 De.data <- na.omit(De.data)
53
54 # sort in ascending order (required for further analyses, cf. template part 3)
55 De.data <- De.data[order(De.data[,1], decreasing = FALSE),]
56
57 # if necessary, convert to data frame (required for function plot_KDE)
58 De.data <- as.data.frame(De.data)
59
60 #=====
61 # 1.4 Finite Mixture Model -----#
62 #=====
63
64 # set input parameters
65 sigmab.De <- 0.42
66 n.components <- 2
67
68
69 # 1.4.1 calculate finite mixture model -----
70 FMM <- calc_FiniteMixture(input.data = De.data,
71                           sigmab = sigmab.De,
72                           n.components = n.components,
73                           n.iterations = 200,
74                           grain.probability = FALSE,
75                           plot.proportions = TRUE,
76                           main = paste(sample, "_FMM", sep = ""))
77
78
79 # 1.4.2 get component with highest proportion -----
80 FMM.results <- get_RLum.Results(FMM, data.object = "components")
81 FMM.results
82
83 # extract component and associated error with highest proportion
84 FMM.max.ID <- which(FMM.results[4,] == max(FMM.results[4,]))
85 FMM.max.dose <- FMM.results[1, FMM.max.ID]
86 FMM.max.error <- FMM.results[3, FMM.max.ID]
87
88 # show summary
89 paste("component_", FMM.max.ID, ":",
90       FMM.max.dose, "\u00B1",

```

```

91     FMM.max.error , sep = "")
92
93
94 #=====
95 # 1.5 Minimum Age Model 3 -----
96 #=====
97
98 # 1.5.1 calculate minimum age model 3 -----
99 MAM3 <- calc_MinDose3(input.data = De.data ,
100                      sigmab = sigmab.De,
101                      log = TRUE,
102                      gamma.xlb = 0.1 ,
103                      gamma.xub = max(De.data[,1] + max(De.data[,2]/2)),
104                      sigma.xlb = 0.001 ,
105                      sigma.xub = 5.00 ,
106                      init.gamma = 10 ,
107                      init.sigma = 1.2 ,
108                      init.p0 = 0.3 ,
109                      output.plot = FALSE,
110                      output.indices = 3)
111
112 # 1.5.2 extract average dose and confidence intervals -----
113 MAM3.results <- get_RLum.Results(object = MAM3, data.object = "results")
114 MAM3.mindose <- MAM3.results$mindose
115 MAM3.error <- c(MAM3.results$X68ci_lower , MAM3.results$X68ci_upper)
116
117
118 # show summary
119 paste("MAM3: ", round(MAM3.mindose, digits = 2), " (", "+",
120       round(MAM3.error[2] - MAM3.mindose, digits = 2), " / ", "-",
121       round(MAM3.mindose - MAM3.error[1], digits = 2), ")", sep = "")
122
123
124
125 #=====
126 # 1.6 plot MAM and FMM results into kernel density estimate (KDE) plot -----
127 #=====
128
129 # plot to .pdf with convenient name (saved in working directory defined above)
130 # open plot device, i.e. pdf
131 pdf(file = paste(sample, "_FMM-MAM-sigmab-", sigmab.De, "_n.compFMM-",
132                 n.components, ".pdf", sep=""), paper = "special")
133
134 # set plot margins
135 par(mar = c(4, 4, 3, 2))
136
137 # define statistical summary output
138 summary.plot <- c("n", "mean", "seabs", "kdemax")
139
140 # create KDE plot
141 KDE <- plot_KDE(data = De.data ,
142                centrality = c("mean", "kdemax"),
143                stats = summary.plot ,

```

```

144         stats.pos = "topright",
145         main = expression(paste(D[e], "\u0394Distribution")),
146         output = TRUE,
147         fun = FALSE)
148
149 # add subheading with sample information
150 mtext(text = paste(sample, "\u0394sigmab\u0394", sigmab.De),
151       line = 0.5,
152       col = "grey")
153
154 # add vertical lines with FMM component positions
155 n.comp <- 2 # number of component(s) to be plotted, change as desired
156 for(i in 1:n.comp) {
157   abline(v = FMM@data$components[[i]][1], col = "blue")
158 }
159
160 # add vertical line with MAM dose
161 abline(v = MAM3.mindose, col = "chartreuse3")
162
163 # create FMM information for component with highest contribution
164 FMM.info <- paste("FMM_comp.\u0394", FMM.max.ID, ":\u0394",
165                 round(FMM.max.dose, 2), "\u0394\u00B1\u0394",
166                 round(FMM.max.error, 2), sep = "")
167
168 # create MAM3 information for component with highest contribution
169 MAM3.info <- paste("MAM3:\u0394",
170                 round(MAM3.mindose, 2), "\u0394+",
171                 round(MAM3.error[2] - MAM3.mindose, 2), "\u0394-",
172                 round(MAM3.mindose - MAM3.error[1], 2), sep = "")
173
174 # read out legend positions and paste text below function-defined legend
175 text(x = par()$usr[2] * 0.95, y = par()$usr[4] * 0.80,
176      adj = c(1, 1),
177      labels = FMM.info,
178      col = "blue")
179 text(x = par()$usr[2] * 0.95, y = par()$usr[4] * 0.80,
180      adj = c(1, 1),
181      labels = paste("\n", MAM3.info, sep = ""),
182      col = "chartreuse3")
183
184 # turn off plot device, this is important if no further pdf-output is desired
185 dev.off()

```

4 Overview of R.Luminescence functions

Name	Description
<code>analyse_IRSAR.RF()</code>	Function to analyse IRSAR RF measurements on K-feldspar samples, performed using the protocol according to Erfurt et al. (2003)
<code>analyse_SAR.CWOSL()</code>	The function performs a SAR CW-OSL analysis on a <code>RLum.Analysis</code> object including growth curve fitting.
<code>Analyse_SAR.OSLdata()</code>	The function analyses SAR CW-OSL curve data and provides a summary of the measured data for every position. The output of the function is optimised for SAR OSL measurements on quartz.
<code>analyse_SAR.TL()</code>	The function performs an SAR TL analysis on a <code>RLum.Analysis</code> object including growth curve fitting.
<code>apply_CosmicRayRemoval()</code>	The function provides several methods for cosmic ray removal and spectrum smoothing for an <code>RLum.Data.Spectrum S4</code> class objects
<code>apply_EfficiencyCorrection()</code>	The function allows spectral efficiency corrections for <code>RLum.Data.Spectrum S4</code> class objects
<code>BaseDataSet.CosmicDoseRate</code>	Collection of data from various sources needed for cosmic dose rate calculation
<code>calc_AliquotSize()</code>	Estimate the number of grains on an aliquot. Alternatively, the packing density of an aliquot is computed.
<code>calc_CentralDose()</code>	This function calculates the central dose and dispersion of the D_e distribution, their standard errors and the profile log likelihood function for sigma.
<code>calc_CommonDose()</code>	Function to calculate the common dose of a D_e distribution.
<code>calc_CosmicDoseRate()</code>	This function calculates the cosmic dose rate taking into account the soft- and hard-component of the cosmic ray flux and allows corrections for geomagnetic latitude, altitude above sea-level and geomagnetic field changes.
<code>calc_FadingCorr()</code>	This function runs the iterations that are need to calculate the corrected age including the error for a given g -value according to Huntley & Lamothe (2001).
<code>calc_FiniteMixture()</code>	This function fits a k -component mixture to a D_e distribution with differing known standard errors. Parameters (doses and mixing proportions) are estimated by maximum likelihood assuming that the log dose estimates are from a mixture of normal distributions.
<code>calc_FuchsLang2001()</code>	This function applies the method according to Fuchs & Lang (2001) for heterogeneously bleached samples with a given coefficient of variation threshold.
<code>calc_HomogeneityTest()</code>	A simple homogeneity test for D_e estimates
<code>calc_MaxDose3()</code>	Function to fit the maximum age model to D_e data. This function is a modified version of the three parameter minimum age model after Galbraith et al. (1999) using a similiar approach described in Olley et al. (2006).
<code>calc_MinDose3()</code>	Function to fit the (un-)logged three parameter minimum dose model (MAM 3) to D_e data.

continued ...

Name	Description
<code>calc_MinDose4()</code>	Function to fit the (un-)logged four parameter minimum dose model (MAM 4) to D_e data.
<code>calc_OSLxTxRatio()</code>	Calculate $L_x x/T_x$ ratios from a given set of CW-OSL curves.
<code>calc_Statistics()</code>	This function calculates a number of descriptive statistics for D_e -data, most fundamentally using error-weighted approaches.
<code>calc_TLLxTxRatio()</code>	Calculate L_x/T_x ratio for a given set of TL curves.
<code>CW2pHMi()</code>	This function transforms a conventionally measured continuous-wave (CW) OSL-curve to a pseudo hyperbolic modulated (pHM) curve under hyperbolic modulation conditions using the interpolation procedure described by Bos & Wallinga (2012).
<code>CW2pLM()</code>	Transforms a conventionally measured continuous-wave (CW) curve into a pseudo linearly modulated (pLM) curve using the equations given in Bulur (2000).
<code>CW2pLMi()</code>	Transforms a conventionally measured continuous-wave (CW) OSL-curve into a pseudo linearly modulated (pLM) curve under linear modulation conditions using the interpolation procedure described by Bos & Wallinga (2012).
<code>CW2pPMi()</code>	Transforms a conventionally measured continuous-wave (CW) OSL-curve into a pseudo parabolic modulated (pPM) curve under parabolic modulation conditions using the interpolation procedure described by Bos & Wallinga (2012).
<code>ExampleData.BINfileData</code>	Example data from a SAR OSL and TL measurement for package Luminescence directly extracted from a Risoe BIN-file and provided in an object of type <code>Risoe.BINfileData-class</code>
<code>ExampleData.CW_OSL_Curve</code>	data frame containing CW-OSL curve data (time, counts)
<code>ExampleData.DeValues</code>	25 equivalent dose (D_e) values measured for a fine grain quartz sample from a loess section in Rottewitz (Saxony/Germany).
<code>ExampleData.FittingLM</code>	Linearly modulated (LM) measurement data from a quartz sample from Norway including background measurement. Measurements carried out in the luminescence laboratory at the University of Bayreuth.
<code>ExampleData.LxTxData</code>	$L_x T_x$ data from a SAR measurement for the package Luminescence.
<code>ExampleData.LxTxOSLData</code>	L_x and T_x data of continuous wave (CW-) OSL signal curves.
<code>ExampleData.RLum.Analysis</code>	Collection of different <code>RLum.Analysis</code> objects for protocol analysis.
<code>ExampleData.XSYG</code>	Example data from a SAR OSL measurement and a TL spectrum for package Luminescence imported from a Freiberg Instruments XSYG file using the function <code>readXSYG2R()</code> .

continued ...

Name	Description
<code>fit_CWCurve()</code>	The function determines the weighted least-squares estimates of the component parameters of a CW-OSL signal for a given maximum number of components and returns various component parameters. The fitting procedure uses the <code>nls</code> function with the port algorithm.
<code>fit_LMCurve()</code>	The function determines weighted nonlinear least-squares estimates of the component parameters of an LM-OSL curve (Bulur 1996) for a given number of components and returns various component parameters. The fitting procedure uses the function <code>nls</code> with the port algorithm.
<code>merge_Risoe.BINfileData()</code>	Function allows merging Risoe BIN files or <code>Risoe.BINfileData</code> objects.
<code>plot_AbanicoPlot()</code>	A plot is produced which allows comprehensive presentation of data precision and its dispersion around a central value as well as illustration of a kernel density estimate of the dose values.
<code>plot_DRTResults()</code>	The function provides a standardised plot output for dose recovery test measurements.
<code>plot_GrowthCurve()</code>	A dose response curve is produced for luminescence measurements using a regenerative protocol.
<code>plot_Histogram()</code>	Function plots a predefined histogram with an accompanying error plot as suggested by Rex Galbraith at the UK LED in Oxford 2010.
<code>plot_KD_e()</code>	Plot a kernel density estimate of measurement values in combination with the actual values and associated error bars in ascending or D_e . Optionally, statistical measures such as mean, median, standard deviation, standard error and quartile range can be provided visually and numerically.
<code>plot_RadialPlot()</code>	A Galbraith's radial plot is produced on a logarithmic or a linear scale.
<code>plot_Risoe.BINfileData()</code>	Plots single luminescence curves from an object returned by the <code>readBIN2R()</code> function.
<code>plot_RLum.Analysis()</code>	The function provides a standardised plot output for curve data of an <code>RLum.Analysis</code> S4 class object
<code>plot_RLum.Data.Curve()</code>	The function provides a standardised plot output for curve data of an <code>RLum.Data.Curve</code> S4 class object
<code>plot_RLum.Data.Spectrum()</code>	The function provides a standardised plot output for spectrum data of an <code>RLum.Data.Spectrum</code> S4 class object
<code>plot_RLum()</code>	Function calls object specific plot functions for <code>RLum</code> S4 class objects.
<code>readBIN2R()</code>	Import a *.bin or a *.binx file produced by a Risoe DA15 and DA20 TL/OSL reader into R.
<code>readXSYG2R()</code>	Imports XSYG files produced by a Freiberg Instrument lexsyg reader into R.

continued ...

Name	Description
<code>Risoe.BINfileData2RLum.Analysis()</code>	Converts values from one specific position of a <code>Risoe.BINfileData</code> S4-class object to an <code>RLum.Analysis</code> object.
<code>Risoe.BINfileData2RLum.Data.Curve()</code>	The function converts one specified single record from a <code>Risoe.BINfileData</code> object to an <code>RLum.Data.Curve</code> object.
<code>Second2Gray()</code>	Conversion of absorbed radiation dose in seconds (s) to the SI unit gray (Gy) including error propagation. Normally used for equivalent dose data.
<code>writeR2BIN()</code>	Exports a <code>Risoe.BINfileData</code> object in a *.bin or *.binx file that can be opened by the Analyst software or other Risoe software.

5 Supplementary data sets

5.1 R.Luminescence templates 1 - 3

5.2 Example data BIN file: TA110817N13-14 OSL 4 ed

5.3 Example data txt file

B Supplementary material for paper III (chapter 3.3)

- Supplementary Data -
**Exploring the potential of luminescence methods
for dating Alpine rock glaciers**

Quaternary Geochronology 18 (2013) 17–33
(doi: 10.1016/j.quageo.2013.07.001)

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B1 The influence of the overdispersion on the FMM based palaeodose

We have no suitable, well bleached material from the study area to determine the overdispersion of our samples. Therefore, we tested the influence of the overdispersion on the finite mixture model (FMM, Galbraith and Green, 1990) based palaeodose. The FMM component used for calculations represents the highest proportion. Black data points highlight overdispersion values of 0.2 - 0.4 found for fluvial sediments (e.g. Arnold et al., 2007; Arnold and Roberts, 2009) and for sediments from the Swiss lowland (Gaar and Preusser, 2012). The grey line represents the maximum of the probability density function for comparison.

B2 Table showing the results of FMM calculations (main component)

overdispersion	GiG2 IRSL SG [Gy]	SAL1 OSL MG [Gy]	SAL1 OSL SG [Gy]	SAL1 IRSL SG [Gy]
od 0.05	13.5 ± 0.7	18.5 ± 2.1	23.6 ± 0.5	28.0 ± 0.7
od 0.10	13.7 ± 0.7	18.8 ± 2.4	23.7 ± 0.5	27.8 ± 0.8
od 0.15	13.6 ± 0.8	19.4 ± 3.2	23.9 ± 0.6	27.9 ± 0.9
od 0.20	13.5 ± 0.9	22.1 ± 3.7	24.7 ± 1.0	27.9 ± 1.0
od 0.25	13.5 ± 1.1	22.4 ± 3.4	26.4 ± 0.7	28.1 ± 1.3
od 0.30	13.4 ± 1.2	22.8 ± 3.8	26.9 ± 0.8	28.6 ± 1.5
od 0.35	13.3 ± 1.3	23.4 ± 4.5	27.3 ± 0.8	29.3 ± 1.7
od 0.40	13.3 ± 1.4	24.1 ± 9.7		30.0 ± 1.9
od 0.45	13.2 ± 1.5	26.6 ± 19.7		
od 0.50	13.2 ± 1.7			
PDFmax	16.7	21.2	24.5	28.4

overdispersion	SUV2 OSL MG [Gy]	SUV2 IRSL SG [Gy]	SUV3 OSL SG [Gy]	SUV4 IRSL SG [Gy]
od 0.05	21.3 ± 1.7	26.5 ± 0.7	14.4 ± 0.9	13.5 ± 0.8
od 0.10	21.4 ± 1.9	25.8 ± 0.9	14.5 ± 1.0	13.4 ± 1.0
od 0.15	21.5 ± 2.1	25.3 ± 1.0	14.6 ± 1.0	13.3 ± 1.1
od 0.20	21.6 ± 2.3	25.0 ± 1.2	14.7 ± 1.1	13.4 ± 1.2
od 0.25	21.7 ± 2.6	24.8 ± 1.4	14.8 ± 1.2	13.6 ± 1.3
od 0.30	21.8 ± 3.0	24.7 ± 1.6	14.9 ± 1.4	13.9 ± 1.2
od 0.35	22.2 ± 3.5	24.6 ± 1.8	15.0 ± 2.0	14.6 ± 1.3
od 0.40	22.9 ± 4.3	24.6 ± 2.0	15.1 ± 1.6	14.6 ± 2.0
od 0.45	24.1 ± 5.5	24.6 ± 2.2	15.2 ± 1.8	
od 0.50	25.1 ± 5.4	24.7 ± 2.4	15.4 ± 1.9	
PDFmax	17.9	27.8	15.3	13.0

B3 The influence of the overdispersion the detection of FMM components

GIG2 - IRSL single grains

For each sample of >15 equivalent dose values, we calculated the FMM components using a range of overdispersion from 0.05 to 0.50 and plotted the results for illustration along with determined equivalent doses and dose distribution parameters.

FMM components are plotted as lightblue dashed lines, the main component (with highest proportion) is shown as a solid line. We determined two to three components in our samples. In all our samples the highest proportion was determined for the lowest component, except for SAL1 OSL multiple grain analysis with the second as the main component.

For comparison, the MAM (Galbraith et al., 1999) result using the same overdispersion is plotted as a green line.

GiG2 - IRSL single grains

SAL1 - OSL multiple grain aliquots (4 mm)

SAL1 - OSL multiple grain aliquots (4 mm)

SAL1 - OSL single grains

SAL1 - OSL single grains

SAL1 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

SAL1 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

unable to resolve FMM components
for higher values of overdispersion

SUV2 - OSL multiple grain aliquots (4 mm)

SUV2 - OSL multiple grain aliquots (4 mm)

SUV2 - OSL multiple grain aliquots (4 mm)

SUV2 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

SUV2 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

SUV2 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

SUV3 - OSL single grains

SUV3 - OSL single grains

SUV3 - OSL single grains

SUV2 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

SUV2 - IRSL K-feldspar single grains

unable to resolve FMM components
for higher values of overdispersion

B4 Measurement protocols

sample-method	preheat		luminescence stimulation				cutheat temp [°C]	SAR sequence		IR test [s]	
	temp [°C]	time [s]	light source	temp [°C]	time [s]	counting [s/channel]		initial [channel]	BG		testdose [s]
SAL 1 - OSL MG	260	10	blue LED	125	50	0.2	1-5	200-250	20	50 - 100 - 150 - 250 - 0 - 100	100
SAL 1 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
SAL 1 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20
SUV 1 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
SUV 2 - OSL MG	260	10	blue LED	125	50	0.2	1-5	200-250	20	50 - 100 - 150 - 250 - 0 - 100	100
SUV 2 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
SUV 2 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20
SUV 3 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
SUV 3 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20
SUV 4 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
SUV 4 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20
GiG 1 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
GiG 1 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20
GiG 2 - OSL SG	260	10	green laser	125	2	0.02	5-10	80-100	20	45 - 150 - 400 - 800 - 0 - 150	20
GiG 2 - IRSL SG	280	10	IR laser	30	5	0.01	5-10	400-500	99	100 - 300 - 600 - 1000 - 0 - 100	20

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C Acknowledgments

Acknowledgments

*"We are like dwarfts on the shoulders of giants,
so that we can see more than they and for a greater distance,
not by any virtue of our own but because we are carried high and raised aloft by their stature"
(Bernard of Chartres)*

During the last several years of my scientific work I was lucky to meet many people who supported, taught and inspired me, and filled me with energy and passion for the things I do. Each person has its own special contribution, and made it a bit more possible to finally submit this thesis.

I had great support from my supervisors, Richard Gloaguen and Matthias Krbetschek, and probably it says more than anything that I want to continue working with both, only that one of them is not with us anymore and I deeply miss his advise and his ideas. I thank Johannes Heitmann, Frank Preusser, Andreas Lang and Lutz Schirrmeister for their trust in my work and constant support through scientific exchange but also with administration issues.

I was lucky to meet people through work who became friends that were always there and I could count on immediate help, never too tired for feedback or for a smile or joke. Many thanks for that to Michael Dietze, Sebastian Kreutzer, Eric Pohl, Fiona Mulvey.

I experienced an unbelievable good collaboration through my work with the R 'Luminescence' developer team. I can't imagine a better collaboration with this high dynamic exchange and all the fun we have developing and implementing new things or just discussion until late night. The immediate replies, comments and the high work output is motivation for returning such great support wherever possible. Exchange of experience and discussion of challenges is central and one of the vivid parts of science and with this respect, the communication and meetings of the Junge Geomorphologen was a great chance. I also want to thanks my colleagues from the remote sensing group in Freiberg, where I could build and improve my skills in numerical analyses and where I could learn and enjoyed so much working in this international team.

There are many more people, I have to thank for great, open and uncomplicated collaboration, I am lucky that many became my friends. Here the names may stay beyond the size of this pages and I will thank all of those in person who are not given by name.

D Declaration

Declaration

I hereby declare that I completed this work without any improper help from a third party and without using any aids other than those cited. All ideas derived directly or indirectly from other sources are identified as such. In the selection and in the use of materials and in the writing of the manuscript I received support from the following persons:

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Markus Fuchs
Adam Szulc
Frank Preusser
Markus Egli
Ralph Böhlert
Silke Merchel
Christoff Andermann
Vasila Sulaymonova
Georg Rugel

Persons other than those above did not contribute to the writing of this thesis. I did not seek the help of a professional doctorate-consultant. Only persons identified as having done so received any financial payment from me for any work done for me. This thesis has not previously been submitted to another examination authority in the same or similar form in Germany or abroad.

Location, date

Margret C. Fuchs